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Abbreviations

CED: CE Delft

Col: Community of Interest

CS1: Case Study 1

CS2: Case Study 2

CS3: Case Study 3

CS4: Case Study 4

CUE: Coventry University Enterprises, Ltd

DoW: Description of Work

ITS: Intelligent Transport System

MIT: Massachusetts Institute of Technology

NEWBITS: New Business Models for ITS

TTS: TTS Italia

UAB: Autonomous University of Barcelona (Spain)

VNA: Value Network Analysis

WP: Work Package

Executive summary

The NEWBITS project intends to develop novel business models in four case studies, effectively involving the target core stakeholders into a Value Network Analysis (VNA) modelling method. NEWBITS Consortium developed tailor-made value network approach to examine and set out a networked business model for each of our case studies. The model is based on a five-step approach:

1. Network – inputs from case studies;
2. Actors – qualitative stakeholder analysis;
3. Value flow maps – quantitative analysis;
4. Crafting value propositions – ideation workshops;
5. Design of networked business models;

The explored VNA model includes a qualitative analysis that defines and discusses the operational context of each stakeholder in their network identifying its main needs and objectives as main drivers to keep the stakeholder active by adapting their competences and outcomes to satisfy other stakeholder's innovation needs. The qualitative analysis also elaborates and completes basic value flow maps that capture the interactions between all actors (section 2).

The quantitative analysis is explained in great detail in section 3 and it assigns numeric scores to each value flow, a pre- and post-validation ranking and an expert ranking via direct interaction with stakeholders and experts. For this purpose, the project deployed 4 ideation workshops at local (case study based) level, and one joint group discussion workshop in which the representatives of each case study, interacted to assess the ranks of the value flows, and subsequently the business modelling process. The case-study oriented ideation workshops were organised in:

- Spain
- Italy
- the Netherlands
- and the United Kingdom

from the respective NEWBITS case study leaders, whereas the group discussion level workshop was organised after the completion and the gathering of the results of the local workshops. The aim of the joint workshop was to inform the experts about the NEWBITS networks, the business models and create a mutual learning atmosphere of lessons learnt in the four networks. They performed a re-ranking of the value flows for all four cases.

In addition, the quantitative analysis provided examples of specific value loops from each network that brought useful insights about the central stakeholder's interactions with multiple actors. Also based on the validated ranks of value flows, we could reveal the major direct value flows in each case. This allowed a simplification in understanding the complex value flow maps and a distillation of important conclusions.

Finally, all the data and information collected from the stakeholders allowed the NEWBITS consortium to delineate a design of networked business modelling that sets out the practical process and complements the provided recommendations in section 4.

1 Introduction

The key to creating successful service business models is to understand how value is created by a desired integration of complementary firms' competences in the value network. With the value network concept, what modern studies suggest is that innovative companies no longer focus on a specific firm or industry, but rather on the value creating system *per se*, within which the network actors (suppliers, partners, allies, public authorities, private customers and end-users) work in cooperation to co-produce the value¹. In theory, actors of the network convert their expertise or core competence into tangible and intangible deliverables that have value for other actors of the network. However, in the ITS industry the reality perhaps deviates slightly from the theoretical models due to the complex nature of the markets (both ITS and C-ITS) and technological innovations. One stakeholder from the network may not have all the capabilities required to offer value-added services, so they face a challenge of how to integrate a cluster of network actors for creating and delivering value to the customers, and also understand the perceptions of customers and end-users of such value.

As it was thoroughly researched in D4.1, the literature review has demonstrated an enormous progress in the fields of network formation, business ecosystem dynamics and networked business models². It is recognised that networks are a good basis for the development of new business models and the business ecosystems offer a broader perspective to understanding business structures and novel strategies to succeed with innovative technologies³.

1.1 Description of NEWBITS WP4

This deliverable D4.3 describes the overall methodology applied in WP4 as a practical tailor-made Value Network Approach, which is an integral part of both the project NEWBITS, and the particular work package. Then it elaborates on the methods and techniques that were used. There are five main objectives to be achieved and they rein in our work.

WP4 Objectives:

- 1) Focus on economic and commercial aspects of C-ITS and ITS markets;
- 2) Define the network context based on the theoretical perspectives and elaborate on new business models;
- 3) Apply the Value Network Approach to generate sufficient information about value flows among stakeholders in the C-ITS and ITS networks;

¹ See more in: Allee, V., (2008) "Value network analysis and value conversion of tangible and intangible assets", Journal of Intellectual Capital, Vol. 9 Issue: 1, pp.5-24; 2) Amit R., Zott C., (2012), "Creating value through business model innovation", MIT Sloan Management Review 53(3): 41-9; 3) Clarysse B., Wright M., Bruneel J., Mahajan A., (2014), "Creating value in ecosystems: Crossing the chasm between knowledge and business ecosystems", Research Policy 43 (2014) 1164-1176

² NEWBITS D4.1: Formalization of NEWBITS modelling method and systemic business dynamics, Submitted on 22/12/2017 as part of WP4, No: 723974

³ Wulf A., Butel L., (2017), "Knowledge sharing and collaborative relationships in business ecosystems and networks: A definition and a demarcation", Industrial Management and Data Systems, Vol. 117 Issue 7, p. 1407-1425

- 4) Implement the analysis to the case studies in order to extract specific details about the competitive environment;
- 5) And set-up the grounds for a systemic approach to business modelling⁴

In more detail, the WP4 is divided into two tasks that have created the conceptual and operational framework for launching the Value Network Analysis (VNA), or T4.1. And WP4 deployed the VNA in a process that included the organization and implementation of small-scale workshops with stakeholders, and ultimately provided the relevant components of the business models for the project's case studies (T4.2). NEWBITS introduced the case-based reasoning to analyse and establish a structure for running the VNA. By engaging in network analysis, we can identify ***principal aspects of new C-ITS and ITS services and determine the new business models.***

For the purposes of the NEWBITS project, the following operative descriptions explained in D2.1⁵ are used:

- Initiative – they are defined as FP7-Horizon2020 projects, scientific reports, policy papers, research reports, other strategic reports and communications;
- Case Studies (CS) – case studies are envisaged to emphasize contextual analysis of a limited number of stakeholders and roles. They will bring understanding of the complexities of ITS and provide knowledge about the existing value creation systems;
- Application – the project considers applications as the use given to ITS in order to achieve a purpose, so this is a combination of several technologies in order to fulfil user requirements related to a transport mode. Applications are aligned with the concept of service.
- Services – examples of ITS services are traffic jam warning, green light optimal speed advisory, V2V merging assistance, etc.

The established four case studies are as follows:

- CS1: ITS Platform for inter-urban carpooling services
- CS2: C-ITS to monitor the drivers' behaviour crossing traffic lights intersections
- CS3: New ICT method to increase efficiency in logistic chain of ports
- CS4: A knowledge-based approach to understanding railway safety

Overall, figure 1 describes the main interrelations between tasks of NEWBITS project and their links to WP4.

Interrelations T4.1 & T4.2 – in T4.1 a solid literature review was performed to delineate the framework for tailor-made value network analysis in Task 4.2, which was recorded in D4.1.

Interrelations T6.1 & T4.2 – T4.2 has been executed on a case study basis and as such the links to T6.1 are described by the Community of Interest (CoI), which in the case of D4.2 and D4.3 means extensive interactions and communication with the networks' stakeholders. The business models are understood as a network of actors that create and deliver value together,

⁴ NEWBITS (2016), Description of Work, Project No: 723974

⁵ NEWBITS, D2.1 "Overview of ITS initiatives in the EU and US", March 2017

and thus, it is shared value and shared risks among all of them that is of our concern. The concept of Col in T6.1 supports the advancement of the business modelling, and these links are explained in Webinar 2 as part of WP7.

Interrelations T5.1, T5.2, T5.3 and T4.2 – the outputs of workshops explained in D4.2, and the VNA results of each case study collected in D4.3 will be vital inputs in all tasks of WP5 that focuses on guiding, training and making policy recommendations.

Interrelations WP2, WP3 and WP4 – all tasks of WP4 built upon the results from WP2 and WP3. The taxonomy of the case studies that described the distinct networks by the selected relevant criteria in their categorization (WP2) has been thoroughly followed and applied in the work of WP4. The scope of WP4 is entirely devoted to the meso-level (a case-based evidence approach). In addition, the outputs of T3.1 Market research analysis and T3.2 Perform conjoint analysis to analyse user-preferences have been considered in the analysis of T4.2.

Figure 1: Interrelations within NEWBITS

1.2 Value Network Analysis in the frame of NEWBITS

In the NEWBITS, the tailor-made Value Network Approach applies the term value flow to outline the output of one stakeholder as an input to another. In a way, the flow represents the delivery of *value* from one stakeholder to another.

Thus, a five-step process has been identified to describe the VNA for NEWBITS:

Figure 2: A five step process of designing a networked business model

The methods and techniques applied in our model are as follows:

1) Network – using a baseline stakeholder map from D3.1⁶ as initially identified by WP3 leader and advanced it later in due course of WP4;

2) Actors – stakeholder objectives, needs and inputs/outputs – these details were requested by the stakeholders of each network, primarily their roles, objectives and needs in order to trace the inputs that each stakeholder receives from others. This task was performed in WP3 during the period of September – October 2017;

3) Mapping value flows – identifying value flows through running two surveys and assigning scores to value flows – this information was collected from the stakeholders in WP4 in December 2017 via two questionnaires and numeric scores were assigned to each value flow. This task as part of T4.2 was primarily based on the methods developed by MIT System Architecture Research Group⁷;

4) Validation of value flow interactions and rankings over the period of (January – March 2018): In the framework of both NEWBITS project and WP4, four case study-based ideation workshops were organized and carried out from our consortium members in the following locations:

- CS1 Workshop: Barcelona, Spain (coordinated by partner UAB)
- CS2 Workshop: Verona, Italy (coordinated by partner TTS)
- CS3 Workshop: Venlo, the Netherlands (coordinated by partner CED)
- CS4 Workshop: Coventry, UK (coordinated by partner CUE)

These workshops verified the results from step 3 with all present stakeholders.

In the context of WP4, the workshops in WP4 performed a major role in steering local debates

⁶ NEWBITS, D3.1 “Market Research Analysis of C-ITS / ITS”, Oct. 2017

⁷ Sutherland T., (2009), “Stakeholder Value Network Analysis for space-based earth observations”, MSc in Aeronautics & Astronautics, MIT, Cambridge

with the involvement of professional moderators in order to accumulate knowledge from the stakeholders directly that were not apparent from the surveys ran in December 2017. In addition, the workshops provided the opportunity to have a face-to-face interaction with the stakeholders and validate the surveys' results, particularly major value flows and ranks during the period of Jan-March 2018. The goal of the workshops was to enable logical reasoning behind any discussion about network relations, crafting value propositions or identification of barriers, as part of the VNA. The main objectives were:

1. **Validation of the Value Flow Scores** – this was the second iteration of the VNA, where we expected the stakeholders to make their final ranking. The objective of the validation process is to perform enough verifications to establish general confidence in the model and NEWBITS method that will be an enabler for the future CoIs in WP6. It is worthwhile noting the importance that networks are not static. They are enhanced by a dynamic mechanism to adapt value flows according to market changes and uncertainties. Thus, in CS1 the dynamic elements were introduced and validated by changes in the ranking of the value flow scores in three different network milestones. The validation also signals how well the stakeholders understand each other's needs and roles.
2. **Stimulation of local debates** about each network's value propositions and proposed business models' main components.

A joint group discussion was also implemented in Barcelona (Spain) involving only consortium members and external experts:

- Joint Group Discussion: Barcelona, Spain (coordinated by partner UAB)

The goal of this group discussion meeting was to share the results of the case-study oriented workshops, discussed about the next steps in WP4 methodological implementation, ensured cohesion of follow-up activities and strengthened links with Community of Interest (CoI) operation in WP6. In addition, the third iteration of the VNA happened at the same time. The discussions with policy-makers took place later in Brussels (23-24th April).

5) Design of networked business models – a performed analysis based on VNA results was the final step to align and shape the models.

1.3 Knowledge blocks defined in D4.1

Time framework

The overall action plan and tasks of WP4 are spread over the period of September (M12) 2017 until June (M21) 2018, with T4.1 having taken place between September and December in order to formalize the theoretical framework of the applied VNA, and with T4.2 having developed between December 2017 and June 2018. The time plan is described in Fig. 3.

All workshop related activity was deployed in the time framework from M15 until M19. This temporal span includes the necessary preparatory activities for the workshops (i.e. action plan

development, workshop preparation guidelines definition and validation, invitation of participants, etc.); the actual implementation of the workshops; and the gathering of information regarding its implementation in the form a report to be sent to WP4 leader.

Project month	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21
T4.1 and D4.1 submitted							
T4.2 Surveys							
WP4 workshops							
Preparatory and design activities							
CS1 workshop in Barcelona							
CS2 workshop in Verona							
CS3 workshop in Rotterdam							
CS4 workshop in Coventry							
Joint Discussion in Barcelona					D4.2		
Consolidation of VNA results							D4.3

Figure 3: Time plan of Task 4.2

Knowledge blocks

Before beginning with the practical application of the tailor-made VNA in T4.2, by December 2017 (M15) T4.1 led by partner INTELS identified knowledge blocks to facilitate our understanding of the applied methodological framework and concepts. In terms of networked business model, Table 1 (below) has been extracted from D4.1 to clarify how we relate these theoretical terms into practical NEWBITS elements as business modelling is fairly conceptual. This knowledge accumulation in T4.1 also helps us to comprehend the links between the VNA value flow results and the potential outline of a business model⁸, which are examined later in this document. The networks described in NEWBITS have been orchestrated before the launching of the project, so therefore during the project duration we already explore the distinct network entities and existing stakeholders. Each network has its own unique characteristics, and some stakeholders come from other industries (e.g. ICT), which lead to cross-sectorial transformation.

⁸ NEWBITS D4.1: Formalization of NEWBITS modelling method and systemic business dynamics, Submitted on 22/12/2017 as part of WP4, No: 723974

Key elements of concept	What lessons learned per concept	Elements related to NEWBITS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A network-level BM is a powerful tool for individual companies to innovate with, particularly when the partners recognise that important competencies needed but not available in-house can be accessed through a partnership with other firms. • Compared to single-firm models, the network-level BM has a much stronger focus on the basics of how joint innovation can ultimately create new values accompanied by diminishing costs for the stakeholders involved. • Dynamic business models are conceptualized as the emergent outcomes of pre-conceived network structures built through the development of routines that guide problem solving. • Three kinds of measurements that might influence the success of collaborative networks are explored in this paper: (1) Input to the collaboration, that is the contribution of each participant; (2) Mechanism of the collaboration, that is the health of the collaboration; (3) Output of the collaboration, that is the results of the collaboration activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Four types of BM identified currently: Asset Builders; Service Providers; Technology Creators; Network Orchestrators • Network Orchestrators These companies create a network of peers in which the participants interact and share in the value creation. They may sell products or services, build relationships, share advice, give reviews, collaborate, co-create and more. Examples include eBay, Red Hat, Visa, Uber, Tripadvisor, and Alibaba. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Few companies operate as Network Orchestrators. Today's network-based BM require new technologies and competencies. The (C-) ITS applications and solutions developed in the CS cover the requirements of today's network-based BM. • To become a NO and create more value and better performance, leaders must connect to and activate their networks, tapping into new sources of value, both tangible and intangible. The power of the networks of each CS is that their stakeholders are from different sectors – industries, thus creating a new cross-industry transformation.

Table 1: Knowledge accumulation and filtering on network business models

2 Qualitative Stakeholder Analysis

This section presents the key aspects of the performed qualitative stakeholder analysis. It is a method that can help provide an in-depth understanding of the numerous stakeholders within any system. It is very useful to shed light on the complex interactions between the stakeholders as well as their needs and objectives. When one looks at the inputs and outputs of each stakeholder, this method allows us to visualise how value is created and delivered throughout the system. It also provides an indication of the level of connectedness that exists among the stakeholders, and what they really expect from the rest of the network.

The qualitative analysis involves the following steps:

1. Identifying stakeholders;
2. Developing a stakeholder map;
3. Describing stakeholder needs and objectives;
4. Determining the interactions (value flows) between each stakeholder;
5. Mapping value flows;

As already mentioned in S1.2 and S1.3, this work was spread over WP3 and WP4 to gather the requested information and analyse it. There are more details provided in D3.1 and D4.2, here for the purposes of informing the reader, a summary is written.

2.1 Identification of stakeholders

The first step was to identify the stakeholders and stakeholder groups that were to be included in the analysis and characterise their objectives and needs. For all case studies of NEWBITS, the stakeholders were considered from the point of view of the network's core activity (CS1 – carpooling; CS2 – monitoring drivers' behaviour; CS3 – container transporting; CS4 – improving railway safety). In general, stakeholders are those who:

- (1) have a direct or indirect involvement in the core activity;
- (2) receive direct or indirect benefits from the core activity;
- (3) possess a significant, legitimate interest in this core activity (regulators). In the stakeholder network each stakeholder is treated as a node with links to the rest of the network.

Table 2 below presents the final lists of stakeholders for all our four cases, which was refined by WP4. Similarly, a full description of all stakeholders is provided in D3.1 and D4.2. Based on this information, initial maps of stakeholders were drawn too.

CS1 List of Stakeholders	CS2 List of Stakeholders	CS3 List of Stakeholders	CS4 List of Stakeholders
1. UAB Management 2. UAB Mobility Unit 3. UAB Living Lab CORE 4. UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit 5. Aslogic S. L. 6. FrontierCities 7. Websays 8. Members of the university community 9. Government (Spain) 10. Educators	1. Verona Municipality 2. AUDI 3. ATV 4. Swarco Mizar 5. Taxi_Operators 6. Citizens 7. TelecomItalia 8. Government (Italy) 9. Educators	1. Dinalog 2. FleetM 3. ICTdev 4. ITO 5. LIOF 6. PoR 7. PortDat 8. Shipper 9. TNO 10. TrackT 11. WarehouseL 12. Government (the Netherlands) 13. Educators	1. Network Rail 2. Alstom 3. CUE 4. ORR – regulator 5. RSSB – regulator 6. Serco 7. Virgin Trains 8. Public (UK) 9. Government (UK) 10. Educators

Table 2: Refined lists of stakeholders

2.2 Stakeholders objectives, needs and inputs/outputs

The next step of the analysis was to gather information from the stakeholders in order to understand how each of them contributes to and derives value from the network. To clearly see the interactions among stakeholders and whether they were satisfied with the inputs received from other stakeholders, we followed a template that concisely specify their role, objectives, needs, inputs and outputs, costs and revenues.

The three figures below (Fig. 4, 5, 6) describe three of the stakeholders of CS1, populated with the necessary information, collected by the CS Leader by following the template. The profiles of the rest of CS1 stakeholders, as well as the stakeholders' profiles of CS2, CS3 and CS4 are included in the appendices – supporting materials 6.1, 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4.

Initially, the network CS1 VaoPoint included one more stakeholder CRUE, which is the Association of Universities in Spain, but with the development of the model, and the better understanding of the high-value outputs provided by each, it was agreed to exclude this stakeholder from the network. These templates were also updated with more information in due course, particularly for CS3, a lot of updates materialised and led to changes in the identified inputs/outputs of stakeholders' profiles once the CS3 Leader began to interview the major stakeholders separately. Thus, the value network analysis and its stages appeared to

be very dynamic and intense in some of the NEWBITS' cases. Some of the information was provided directly by the stakeholders, other was collected from their websites or public documents. In this regard, the meaning of "specific needs" indicates the resources necessary by the stakeholder to achieve their objectives. The inputs fulfil one or another specific need, and they are usually provided by other stakeholders in the network.

We take a specific need of Aslogic in CS1 as an example: to create science and technical knowledge for the network, to do so they need mobility data, ITS science knowledge, skilled workforce, commercial funding to operate and information about the future plans of UAB and other potential customers.

Additionally, by talking directly to the stakeholders ensured us that the interests of every stakeholder were fully captured by our analysis.

Moreover, the *value flow* indicates the output of one stakeholder as the input to another, and Fig.7 and Fig. 8 show the value flows into and out of four stakeholders. For instance, stakeholder "**Aslogic**" receives commercial funding from clients and the network; acquired mobility data from the network; ITS knowledge from the UAB LOGA; future plans exchange from the UAB mobility unit and the rest of the network; skilled workforce from the educators. Simultaneously, "Aslogic" provides analysed mobility data to FrontierCities and UAB LOGA; new interoperability standards VAO Point to UAB Smart Cities CORE; technology transfers to UAB Smart Cities CORE; and mobility derived products & services to the end users. The value flows are shown in different colours in order to identify them as flows of different types.

The other stakeholder, **FrontierCities**, receives EU funding and does cost sharing with UAB mobility unit and UAB LOGA; plans and reports of progress from UAB mobility unit and UAB management; mobility data from the network; science opinions from the university (UAB); opinion and support from the members of community (end-users) and European cities; and informative content from social media outlets. Simultaneously, "FrontierCities" provide FIWARE technology to UAB Smart cities CORE; collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options to the end-users, and informative content to the government.

Similarly, Fig. 8 describes the value flows into and from the stakeholder "**Websays**" and the stakeholder "**UAB mobility unit**". Repetitively, this process has been done for all stakeholders of each case study. Then as a next step, the value network model has been visually created by linking all value flows within one case. Different types of value flows are coloured in: 1) red – knowledge & information; 2) blue – monetary; 3) green – policy flows; 4) light mocha – data, technology & services; 5) smokey mocha – skilled workforce & public benefits.

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acquired mobility data (Other stakeholders and partners) 2. Commercial funding 3. ITS Science knowledge (UAB) 4. Future Plans Information Exchange (UAB Mobility Unit, Network stakeholders) 5. Skilled workforce (Educators) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Aslogic</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: ITS Service Provider</p> <p>Role: Responsible for the development and deployment of ITS technology that aims to improve & optimise performance of logistic operators</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Provide ITS services and consultancy *Provide data services *Provide IT support to UAB Mobility Unit by identifying transport needs and market opportunities *Empower transport operators/users/managers/administration with cutting-edge ITS as cloud services removing access barriers and unjustified investments *Research and transfer of technologies <p>Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collaboration with other stakeholders to design incentives to foster dissemination policies that can attract new users 2. Science and technical knowledge 3. Interaction with end-users 4. Resources (budgetary, human, technical) 5. Regulatory change of service's payment <p>Cost Structure: Not available</p> <p>Revenue Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Revenue model is based on VAO Point obtained licence *The service is provided to universities, policy-makers and administrators (public/private) <p>Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technological innovations 2. Digital and transport services 3. Analysed mobility data 4. New standards for VAO Point interoperability
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Figure 4: CS1 stakeholder description - ASLOGIC

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acquired mobility data (Other stakeholders and partners) 2. Cost sharing (UAB Mobility Unit, UAB LOGA) 3. EU funding (Public taxation) 4. Plans and Reports of progress (UAB Mobility Unit, UAB Management) 5. Opinion & support (European cities, Members of Community) 6. Science opinions (UAB) 7. Informative content (Social Media) 	<p style="text-align: center;">FrontierCities</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: Funder and Promoter</p> <p>Role: Responsible to support SMEs and start-ups to develop smart mobility applications for cities across Europe by providing funding, technical support and business advice. It also accelerates new research and prototypes into market-ready technologies</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Manage resources to promote SmartCities apps *Identify potential markets *Introduce new products *Develop a new Cities Programme dedicated to supporting and developing the network of cities that apply FIWARE-enabled solutions. (The FIWARE Community is an independent open sustainable ecosystem around public, royalty-free and implementation-driven software platform standards.) *Offer Financing & Partnership Acceleration Service <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical) 2. Mobility acquired data to support objectives 3. Launch services 4. Programme coordination / management 5. Knowledge of Cities needs 6. Knowledge of SMEs, start-ups capabilities and objectives 7. General information (scientific, technical, social, etc.) <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure:</p> <p>FrontierCities Programme's expenses - €1.6 million provided as grant funding across two Open Call strands (FI-TECH and MAG Grants) to SMEs and start-ups to develop & commercialise FIWARE-powered smart-cities applications</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <p>Not defined, it is publicly funded</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) 2. Smart Applications applied in multiple vertical sectors 3. FIWARE technology - shared protocols, a common language, an analysis of interaction within the Internet of Things
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Figure 5: CS1 stakeholder description - FrontierCities

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Skilled workforce (Educators) 2. Future Mobility Plans information (UAB Management) 3. Mobility acquired data from various sources (UAB campuses, others) 4. Science knowledge (UAB) 5. Informative & entertaining content (Social Media) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Websays</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: Others Social Media Marketing Company</p> <p>Role: Engage end-users through a continuous analysis of their opinions, tweets, locations and feelings in regards to VAOPoint offered services and rewards incentives</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Keep a constant monitoring of end-users social network trends at university's campuses *Identify new mobility trends in other markets *Enhance VAOPoint customers by disseminating high-quality information and turn them into Brand advocates *Assess incentives and applied rewards mechanisms to maintain VAOPoint end-users engaged leaders in social data analysis technologies <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources to implement its objectives (budgetary) 2. Technical resources to adapt semantic analysis of each particular field, so that individual preferences are properly understood 3. Motivated workforce to guide and keep alive the mobility social networks 4. Expert/public opinions on social network topics <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure: Not available</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <p>Websays provide assessment services to public companies, private companies, and individual customers. It is also open to different collaboration strategies to penetrate through VAOPoint in the mobility data analysis sector</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Assessed mobility trends - individual preferences; collective preferences and shortfalls 2. Aggregated analysed data regarding mobility in the context of Universities' needs 3. Social data analysis technologies
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Figure 6: CS1 stakeholder description - Websays

VALUE FLOWS INTO		VALUE FLOWS OUT
<p>1. Acquired Mobility Data Network's stakeholders</p> <p>2. Commercial funding Commercial clients</p> <p>3. Commercial funding Network's stakeholders</p> <p>4. Skilled workforce Educators</p> <p>5. ITS knowledge UAB</p> <p>6. Future plans information exchange UAB Mobility Unit</p> <p>7. Future plans information exchange Network's stakeholders</p>	<p>ASLOGIC</p>	<p>1. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products End-users</p> <p>2. Analysed mobility data FrontierCities, UAB LOGA</p> <p>3. New standards for VAO Point interoperability UAB Smart Cities CORE</p> <p>4. Technology transfer UAB Smart Cities CORE</p>

VALUE FLOWS INTO		VALUE FLOWS OUT
<p>1. Acquired Mobility Data Network's stakeholders</p> <p>2. EU funding Public taxes</p> <p>3. Cost sharing UAB Mobility Unit UAB LOGA</p> <p>4. Opinion & Support Members of community; European Cities</p> <p>5. Plans & reports of progress UAB Mobility Unit UAB Management</p> <p>6. Science opinion UAB</p> <p>7. Informative content Social media</p>	<p>FrontierCities</p>	<p>1. Informative & disseminative content Government</p> <p>2. Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options Members of Community (end-users)</p> <p>3. FIWARE technology - shared protocols, a common language, an analysis of interaction within the Internet of Things UAB Smart Cities CORE</p>

Figure 7: Value flows into and out of stakeholder: ASLOGIC and FrontierCities

<p>VALUE FLOWS INTO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acquired Mobility Data from various sources Members of Community 2. Skilled workforce Educators 3. Science knowledge UAB 4. Future mobility plans information UAB Management 5. Informative & entertaining content Social Media 6. Funding - Operators, UAB Management, Members of community 7. Policy Collaboration (engaging the end-users) 	<p>Websays</p>	<p>VALUE FLOWS OUT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Informative & disseminative content (assessed mobility trends) Government, UAB LOGA 2. Informative & entertaining content Members of Community (end-users) 3. Policy collaboration (aggregated analysed data) UAB Smart Cities CORE
<p>VALUE FLOWS INTO</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Funding Government 2. Cost sharing with UAB UAB Management 3. Policy collaboration (engaging end-users) Municipality Other public administration Members of community 4. Mobility planning UAB Management Transport operators Other public administration 5. Future plans information exchange UAB Management Other public administration Transport operators 6. Monetary rents Commercial operators 7. Skilled workforce Educators 	<p>UAB Mobility Unit</p>	<p>VALUE FLOWS OUT</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Future plans information exchange UAB LOGA UAB Management Aslogic 2. Cost sharing UAB Management 3. Plans and reports of progress FrontierCities Government 4. Mobility planning and know-how UAB Management Other public administration 5. Employment Members of community

Figure 8: Value flows into and out of stakeholder: Websays and UAB Mobility unit

CASE STUDY 1 VALUE FLOW MAPS

Figure 9: Monetary value flows in CS1: VaoPoint Network

In Figure 9, the focus is on the monetary value flows and monetary exchanges, all coloured in blue among all 10 stakeholders. There are four major types of interaction among the stakeholders:

- 1) funding; 2) cost sharing; 3) monetary rents and 4) taxes.

The cost sharing is mainly between the UAB as an institution and its research units. Also, cost sharing takes place between FrontierCities and UAB Mobility unit as well as FrontierCities and UAB LOGA. The private stakeholders pay taxes that are collected for the government, and then public funds are allocated to educators and UAB management as public organisations.

Figure 10: Monetary and knowledge & informative value flows in CS1: VaoPoint network

In Figure 10, we add the knowledge & informative content value flows that move between the stakeholders. First, there is an outflow of scientific knowledge (ITS, transport-related) from the university (UAB) to the other stakeholders. Second, there is a separate circle of informative content that begins from Websays, then goes to FrontierCities and the governmental institutions. Third, an individual flow of “planning reports” moves between the external transport operators, the UAB mobility unit and then it is redistributed among the university’s units, advanced and moved forward to FrontierCities, Aslogic.

Figure 11: Monetary, knowledge & informative and policy value flows in CS1: VaoPoint Network

In Figure 11, more interactions are added, including the policy collaboration and engagement, to the existing monetary and knowledge value flows. What is observable, two separate loops are identified:

- 1) Policy directions flow from the EU & Intergovernmental agencies to the national government of Spain, and then to the UAB Mobility Unit, which is utilised in the policy-collaboration process of the university; and
- 2) Policy engagement process that involves all private stakeholders, including the members of university community (end-users), and this flow continues to the research units of UAB (UAB LOGA, UAB CORE, UAB Mobility unit), which exchange further information between themselves, and then forward final policy directions to the UAB Management.

Figure 12: Monetary, knowledge & informative, policy & opinions, data, technology & services and skilled workforce value flows in CS1: VaoPoint Network

Figure 12 represents all value flows (about 100 direct interactions) that are exchanged among ten stakeholders of CS1. It includes the flow of skilled workforce from the educators to the rest of the network. Also, another circle identifies the flow of data, new interoperable standards and technology transfers that moves from Aslogic to the UAB Smart Cities CORE. Websays detects data too from the university's campuses, which is statistically analysed and utilised by UAB LOGA and UAB CORE. Some of this analysed and structured mobility data flows into FrontierCities (from Aslogic and UAB units). Aslogic, of course, acquires mobility data from the network, so there is an extensive exchange of data among all actors. For instance, data is obtained via the developed app by ASLOGIC for the services, and then it flows to the UAB Mobility Unit.

CASE STUDY 2 VALUE FLOW MAPS

Figure 13: Monetary value flows in CS2: VERONA Municipality

Figure 13 represents CS2 or Verona Municipality that runs a C-ITS platform to deliver information to drivers (speed advice and time to red lights). All nine stakeholders are involved in the process of value creation. There are two separate circles:

- 1) one describes the public funding and EU-funding (predominantly through research & innovation projects);
- 2) and the second circle describes the taxation from the private actors to the government.

In this flow of R&D funds, the Municipality of Verona does cost sharing with the EU institutions. In CS2 the network relies heavily on public funding, both national and European, which supports the improvement of the city public services. The educators have an indirect role.

Figure 14: Monetary and knowledge & informative value flows in CS2: VERONA Municipality

In Figure 14, the knowledge and informative content interactions have been added. In contrast to the CS1, where a strong cluster of UAB research units was leading the knowledge-intensive activities of the Barcelona’s case, in CS2 there is no major university or academic institution as a network leader. The municipality of Verona is the ultimate network orchestrator. As such the generic knowledge is provided by the educators (Italian colleges and universities) that educate the workforce and distribute general and technical information. However, at a more specialised and scientific level, the R&D departments of three of the stakeholders (AUDI, Swarco Mizar and Telecom Italia) focus heavily on ITS-transport related research projects and as a result they disseminate scientific knowledge to the other departments of the companies.

The other major interaction is between all private stakeholders and the municipality. In principles, all actors would be expected to inform the city-hall about their future plans in relation to the C-ITS platform. Similarly, the company of the private taxi operators would also be expected to deliver the necessary information to the authority. However, it might be difficult to happen all the time since commercial actors have reduced their business involvement in recent days and the municipality holds the sole ownership of the C-ITS platform. This was,

nevertheless, the case during the pilot trial but dynamic forces lead to changes within the network continuously.

Figure 15: Monetary, knowledge & informative and policy value flows in CS2: VERONA Municipality

In Figure 15, the policy value flows are added. In CS2, there is one major policy value circle.

The Italian government receives policy information and directions (directives & regulations) from the European and inter-governmental agencies in relation to the ITS sector. These policy directions are then distributed to the local authorities such as Verona municipality, the telecom industry, ITS providers and educators. In addition, the municipality exchanges any policy-directed information with Telecom Italia, which provides the services of sending information (speed advice and time to red lights) to the drivers' mobile phones or the dashboard of the car. In contrast to CS1, there is no continuous policy collaboration with the rest of the stakeholders when it comes to the current policy-making of Verona authorities. At the time of the testing of the C-ITS platform in 2014, all major stakeholders were fully engaged such as ITS provider, Telecom operator, OEMs, bus operator and citizens.

The municipality has a strategic mobility plan that is followed by the private actors. It currently runs the mobility control centre which supervises through numerous technologies, tools and devices, the road traffic conditions across the whole city.

Figure 16: Monetary, knowledge & informative, policy & opinions, data, technology & services and skilled workforce value flows in CS2: VERONA Municipality

Figure 16 provides a complete picture of all value flow interactions (about 60 exchanges of value flows) among all nine stakeholders. We added two categories of value flows: 1) skilled workforce & public benefits, and 2) data, technology & services.

Therefore, one major circle is the flow of skilled workforce from the educators to all private stakeholders completed by the provision of students from the citizens to the colleges. This includes employment opportunities for the citizens delivered by the private actors.

Another major value loop is the flow of data and transit signal priority. The operations of the network heavily depend on the exchange of real-time data. These are the specific data flows in CS2 as identified by the survey. As it has been already revealed the commercial actors have reduced their involvement in recent days:

- Verona municipality grant access to traffic signal data to Swarco Mizar;
- Audi via their vehicle fleet make vehicle location data available to the C-ITS platform;
- ATV via their fleet similarly make location data available to the C-ITS platform;
- Taxi Operator via their car fleet similarly make location data available to the platform.

In addition, ITS mobility services are delivered to: 1) Verona municipality; 2) Telecom Italia and the end-users; 3) to ATV and taxi-operators.

Verona authority and Swarco Mizar develop online mobile apps for the citizens as the municipality owns the infrastructure and Swarco Mizar provides the software solutions. Telecom Italia provides the 4G infrastructure to deliver the required connectivity between the vehicles involved in the trials and the C-ITS platform.

CASE STUDY 3 VALUE FLOW MAPS

Figure 17: Monetary value flows in CS3: Rotterdam - Limburg corridor

Figure 17 presents the monetary value flows in CS3, which focuses on the improved efficiency of the synchro-modal container corridor between Rotterdam and Limburg. The logistics operations are important in this case. There are three main circles:

- 1) co-financing of projects between Dinalog and the network;
- 2) a flow of public funds from the European institutions for various projects to the national government, and then to educators and Dinalog; there are general public funds flowing from the Dutch government to LIOF (regional development company), but not project specific;
- 3) corporate and public taxation of network's actors, which monetary flows go into the government's treasury.

Figure 18: Monetary and knowledge & informative value flows in CS3: Rotterdam - Limburg corridor

In CS3, the stakeholder TNO (Research) leads the network at the early stage of its development, mainly during the start-up stage until all stakeholders define their roles and a business model, at which point TNO withdraws from the entity. The major role of TNO is to provide the ITS scientific, technical knowledge and information to all actors. Then this role is undertaken by the platform developer and information service provider. The main loops are coloured in red as follows:

- 1) planning & container status info flows from the shipper, the warehouse and the inland terminal operator, the sea-shipping company and the deep-sea terminal to the platform developer;
- 2) knowledge & informative & disseminative content moving from TNO and Dinalog to the Dutch government, educators and LIOF as well as other Consortium's partners;
- 3) technical knowledge relating to the ITS apps from the platform developer and TNO as well as business case knowledge flow to all stakeholders; and the logistic chain information flows from all stakeholders to platform developer;
- 4) information on future plans from TNO and Dinalog is delivered to the governmental institutions. This is mainly information about the project progress.

Figure 19: Monetary, knowledge & informative and policy value flows in CS3: Rotterdam - Limburg corridor

In Figure 19, the policy value flows have been added (coloured in green) and the major circles are:

- 1) policy directions from the EU institutions in regards to multi-modality, mode shift, mobility and climate change move towards the Dutch government;
- 2) LIOF (regional development company) also shares policy developments with Dinalog, TNO and Port of Rotterdam;
- 3) shared policy goals are distributed among the platform developer, Portdat, TNO, Dinalog, the governmental departments of the Netherlands, and Port of Rotterdam.

To sum it up, policy flows are understood as policy-making goals to increase modal shift from road to inland waterways and increase transport efficiency by optimally using ICT and ITS to reach the logistics goals.

Figure 20: Monetary, knowledge & informative, policy & opinions, data, technology & services and skilled workforce value flows in CS3: Rotterdam - Limburg corridor

Figure 20 provides a complete value flows map of more than 120 interactions among all 13 stakeholders, plus customers, citizens, the sea-shipping company and the deep-sea terminal. The educators (colleges, universities) provide the skilled workforce to all private and public actors of the network.

The network's stakeholders (FleetM, Portdat, Platform developer) rely heavily on the authorisations for data sharing, particularly from the inland terminal operator, the sea-shipping company and the deep-sea terminal. In addition, the platform developer receives real-time data from AISHUB⁹ and NDW¹⁰. All this volume of data is analysed and structured on the ICT/ITS platform, then transferred as real-time container status data to the shipper, the warehouse

⁹ AISHUB – AIS data sharing service which provides access to real time ship positions for vessel tracking systems

¹⁰ NDW – National Data Warehouse for Traffic information

operator and the inland terminal operator. The early delivery of goods to the customers depend very much on the level of predictability (the higher, the better) of the delivery from the deep-sea terminal and inland terminal operators. Future contracts are negotiated among the shipper, the warehouse operator, the inland terminal and the platform developer.

CASE STUDY 4 VALUE FLOW MAPS

Figure 21: Monetary value flows in CS4: Railway safety

Figure 21 represents the monetary exchanges among 10 stakeholders in the UK railway network (CS4). The UK railway industry is a natural monopoly, which is heavily monitored by the regulators – Office of Rail and Road (ORR); Railway Safety and Standard Board (RSSB). Grants and public funds flow from the UK government to the railway public bodies, Network rail and Train manufacturers. In addition, the train operators compete for franchising contracts from the UK government. Coventry University and its unit CUE shares costs with Network rail and RSSB on various research projects.

All actors of the network, including the public, pay taxes that shift to the government's treasury.

Figure 22: Monetary and knowledge & informative value flows in CS4: Railway safety

In Figure 22, the knowledge and informative flows are added to the diagram, where the major transfer of scientific knowledge is from the Coventry University to the rest of the stakeholders. This is predominantly technical knowledge related to ITS, transport-wide and railway safety.

The regulatory bodies (ORR, RSSB) inform the university of new regulations and standards, which updates are taken into consideration from different research units of the university. They also inform the government of any regulatory changes.

Alstom transport creates science systems for Virgin train and Network rail. To develop these systems, Alstom transport receives the future plans from Coventry university and Network rail, in addition to any scientific and technical knowledge.

Educators (colleges, schools) provide the educational courses to the public and private actors. The IT service provider “Serco”, as a public service provider usually receives information about the future plans of the UK government. All actors receiving monetary value flows from the UK government in response submit reports about their annual progress.

Figure 23: Monetary, knowledge & informative and policy value flows in CS4: Railway safety

Figure 23 presents the policy & opinions value flows (in green). There are two major well defined value loops:

- 1) The public provides feedback about the railway safety through its interaction with the governmental institutions via public polls, surveys and direct interviews;
- 2) Policy directions come from EU and intergovernmental agencies to the UK government, which are transferred to the Department for Transport (London) and Transport for Scotland (Edinburg), which then flow to the industry’s regulators – ORR, RSSB. Serco also provides policy advice to the UK government. The industry’s regulators prepare policy documentation on the basis of all policy directives related to the railway sector and transfer this information

to Network Rail, which uses it as an input to their decision-making. Network Rail is the manager of the railway infrastructure in the United Kingdom.

Figure 24: Monetary, knowledge & informative, policy & opinions, data, technology & services and skilled workforce value flows in CS4: Railway safety

Figure 24 presents a complete value flows map of about 60 interactions among all ten stakeholders of CS4. The educators provide all skilled workforce to the rest of the network.

There are a few significant points:

- 1) the public expect to get employment contracts from the private and public actors of the network;
- 2) the public enjoy new launched services by Network Rail, the Train operator “Virgin” in cooperation with the data analytics services of Coventry University;
- 3) the public receive more accurate data about the train services as a result of data analytic applications;
- 4) the public pay fair prices, which are monitored by the regulatory authority, ORR;
- 5) the public expect health and safety protection standards to be forced in implementation by the industry’s regulators and the government.

The big data analytic services performed by the research units of Coventry university depend heavily on the exchange of real-time data, which is collected by the train operator “Virgin” while testing the infrastructure of Network Rail. This data is analysed and structured, then transferred to the relevant stakeholders – industry’s regulators and governmental departments.

2.3 Summary of Qualitative Analysis

The qualitative analysis in this D4.3 builds upon the stakeholder analysis launched in D3.1 and provides a thorough understanding of how each NEWBITS case study delivers value to the entire network of stakeholders. There are five main points identified throughout:

- Via the qualitative analysis we summarised a list of stakeholders for each CS;
- The objectives and specific needs of each stakeholder were discussed;
- A template for each stakeholder’s profile has been applied;
- The inputs to each stakeholder were used to develop value flow maps in each CS;
- Different categories of value flows, quantifiable and non-quantifiable, were represented on the maps via differing colours.

By nature, the value flows are only qualitative in this analysis, but all maps of value flows establish the foundation for the quantitative stakeholder analysis and model described later in this report. Section 2.4 describes a summary of CS1 and CS2 as they are business-to-customers cases. Section 2.5 describes a summary of CS3 and CS4 as business-to-business cases.

2.4 CS1, CS2

The value flow maps in **CS1** provide a qualitative indication of all UAB mechanisms as a public institution, creating scientific knowledge and innovations, delivers value to the stakeholder network in Barcelona. This model shows the direct interactions between all units of UAB and the rest of the stakeholders, as well as the relevant direct interactions among other stakeholders. We can see instantly from the maps the connectedness of each stakeholder to

the rest of the network. Also, certain stakeholders, such as members of university community (end-users) and the Government have direct interactions with the UAB management through the policy collaboration and engagement. The end-users or the public are also linked to the government institutions through expressing public opinions or participating in different polls. They play an important role in the delivery of value throughout the network.

One of the significant type of value flows that are categorised as knowledge & information or policy & opinions are not easily quantifiable or monetizable, however, we include them in this analytical technique which gives us the opportunity to complete our understanding of the ultimate value delivered by the Barcelona network. In this network, the knowledge is treated as a public good and the knowledge-intensity of the network is high.

In **CS2**, the value flow maps demonstrate qualitatively how the city authority of Verona (Italy) as a public service unit delivers value to the stakeholder network. The model of this case shows all direct interactions between the municipality and the national government (EU agencies) on one side, and the relevant interactions among the rest of the network, on the other side. The final map identifies thoroughly the connectedness of each stakeholder to the rest. Swarco Mizar provides all the innovative ITS mobility services to the municipality. Municipality is responsible for maintaining the digital infrastructure and delivering the mobile apps to the citizens of Verona (end-users).

Knowledge & information and policy & opinions value flows are also included in the CS2's network interactions, although there is no huge volume of such exchanges among all stakeholders. The ITS scientific knowledge is produced by the R&D departments of the three major private actors and disseminated within the company internally. In this respect, when it comes to the knowledge-intensity of the network, it is more of a closed entity where the creation of knowledge is treated as private goods & services concentrated in a few stakeholders, which are sold to the public sector later, and then disseminated to the public. This is in contrast to the CS1 and CS4 where knowledge is considered a public good.

2.5 CS3, CS4

In **CS3**, the value flow maps qualitatively indicate how a research organisation, co-financed by the network's stakeholders and the government, can lead the network entity in the starting-up stage and deliver value to all of them. As the model suggests there is very close connectedness between TNO and the rest of the stakeholders. The Dutch government transfers its policy directions and instructions via LIOF, Dinalog, TNO and Port of Rotterdam to the industry.

Knowledge & information value flows as non-quantifiable categories suggest an intensive flow of scientific and technical knowledge between TNO and the stakeholders. TNO also keep close relations with the educators in order to update them on technical topics and provide them with educational materials from the industry whenever necessary. The other stakeholders such as the information service provider, platform developer, Portdat and FleetM

that are involved with the operation of the ITS /ICT platform, whenever they detect ITS challenges, they communicate with the TNO which cooperates with educators in order to find solutions to these issues.

The network in CS3 is very dependent on the sharing of data between logistics partners and data transfer to the platform developer. It shows how value can be delivered among logistics partners in addition to other network stakeholders' interactions. It is a data-driven operational entity and a knowledge-intensive network with an opening sharing of knowledge, information and data among all 13 stakeholders.

In **CS4**, the qualitative value flow maps demonstrate how additional big data analytics services offered by Coventry University Group to the Network Rail can create new value delivered to the stakeholder network. The university was not an originator of this network, the initiative was triggered by Network Rail that tries on a daily basis under the ORR's instructions to reduce its losses. The university's research unit was hired to deliver the big data analytic services. However, as the model suggests there is close connectedness between the university and the rest of the stakeholders via the knowledge value flows.

The monopoly nature of the railway industry predefines the relations between the regulators and the industry's players. The UK government has set up the framework within which the industry operates a long time ago. Department for Transport and Transport Scotland transfer its policy directions to the industry's regulators, which then inform the major actors of the railway sector how to comply with them.

In our particular CS4, as the offered service in the North-west region of the United Kingdom relates to the exchange / analysis of data and its sharing with stakeholders, the network's operations are data-driven and knowledge-intensive. Coventry university transfer scientific and technical knowledge to the rest of the network. All 10 stakeholders benefit from the value created by the exchange of structured and analyzed data, which supports them in offering better and safer railway services in the UK. This in return leads to a better feedback coming from the UK public to the governmental institutions about the public satisfaction of the railway services. As there is a direct interaction between the citizens and the UK government, in CS4 the public plays a crucial role in the delivery of value throughout the stakeholder network.

3 Quantitative Value Network Analysis

In this section, the focus is on the quantitative results collected via surveys and workshops in a sequence of three VNA iterations ran between December 2017 and April 2018. While the qualitative analysis in the previous section identified the total interactions among the stakeholders in each of our four case studies, the quantitative analysis emphasizes the most significant stakeholders, value flows and value loops within the networks.

The objective of the quantitative analysis is to identify:

- 1) stakeholders with more relevant roles in each of the four networks – dividing them into primary and secondary actors;
- 2) the highest value-producing interactions among stakeholders in each of the four networks;

This section 3 will explain in detail the methodology applied in quantifying the value flows of our model, which includes the following steps:

- i) running a survey with two formal questionnaires to obtain the quantitative scores to each value flow. This was done in parallel for the four case studies;
- ii) running workshops' debates with local stakeholders to validate the quantitative scores;
- iii) running a joint workshop's debates with experts to validate and re-rank quantitative scores of each value flow. As part of it, a discussion with the policy-makers took place in Brussels.

To calculate the value flow scores, NEWBITS project applies a tailor-made VNA based on the MIT (Cambridge) approach used to analyse the aeronautics & astronautics industry in the United States¹¹. A thorough justification of the applied methodology is provided in D4.1, therefore the focus here is on the results of the value network approach¹².

Following the MIT approach, two questionnaires about satisfaction of need and importance of source were run over a period of three weeks in December 2017.

For each specific need, we asked two questions, where stakeholders were able to rank the intensity and importance of their major interactions within their defined ITS network:

- 1) Categorising the intensity of each **specific need** of a stakeholder
Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfilment of this need?

- 2) Defining the **source importance**
Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be in fulfilling the need?

¹¹ Sutherland T., (2009), "Stakeholder Value Network Analysis for space-based earth observations", MSc in Aeronautics & Astronautics, MIT, Cambridge

¹² NEWBITS D4.1: Formalization of NEWBITS modelling method and systemic business dynamics, Submitted on 22/12/2017 as part of WP4, No: 723974

Satisfaction / Regret

Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfillment of this need?

Responses: A response of A, B, C, D or E will be chosen. Answer E corresponds to “must-have” need.

- A. I would be satisfied by its presence, but do not regret its absence
- B. I would be satisfied by its presence, but would somewhat regret its absence
- C. I would be satisfied by its presence and do regret its absence
- D. Its presence is needed
- E. Its presence is absolutely essential

The surveys were translated into the local language of each NEWBITS case. A response “A” corresponds to a “fair” need, while “E” corresponds to a “must-have” need. The alphabetical responses are then converted into numeric scores via a log scale that creates greater differentiation between the “absolutely essential” needs and the less essential needs. The scale begins at 0.11 for response “A”, and every other response is a factor of 1.7 higher than the next lowest response.

Importance of Source

Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be?

Responses: A response of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 can be chosen. The response 5 corresponds to “extremely important”.

- 1. Not important
- 2. Somewhat important
- 3. Important
- 4. Very important
- 5. Extremely important

The second question asks about the importance of a certain source in fulfilling a stakeholder's specific needs. Number 1 corresponds to "not important", while number 5 corresponds to "extremely important. Again, these responses are converted into numeric scores via a linear scale beginning at 0.11 for the lowest response (Sutherland, 2009).

Finally, the "satisfaction/regret" and "source importance" scores for each value flow are multiplied to produce a *value flow* score. This process of scoring has been done individually for each case study. The original questionnaires have been attached in the appendixes as supporting materials of NEWBITS cases. The Case Study Leaders interviewed about 4-7 stakeholders in Spain, Italy, the Netherlands and the UK that were well aware of how the networks operate. These included senior and junior personnel of companies. Each of the interviewees answered first, question 1 "satisfaction/ regret" and second, question 2 "source importance", after which all filled-in questionnaires were revised whether there were major differences among all responses. Finally, the combined value flow score was determined by the average of the individual scores in each case.

For instance, in CS1 (Barcelona) all stakeholders' answers were converted into their numeric equivalent. By multiplication, it was obtained the final value scores of each representative and the combined scores, which assess the stakeholder preferences in terms of how they use different sources to fulfil their needs.

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	&R1	&R2	&R3	&R4	COMBINED	Pre-Validation
							Scores	Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.96	0.96	0.31	0.96	0.80	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.44	0.96	0.26	0.44	0.53	3
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.44	0.96	0.18	0.56	0.54	2
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.01	0.44	0.44	0.76	0.41	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.26	0.44	0.31	0.56	0.39	6
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.18	0.44	0.31	0.56	0.37	7
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.11	0.44	0.44	0.96	0.49	4

Table 3: ASLOGIC stakeholder's combined scores and pre-validation ranks

To the stakeholder "ASLOGIC" there are 5 flows, going as inputs that are necessary for Aslogic to operate and achieve its business targets, as well as to produce the final outputs:

1. Acquired mobility data
2. Commercial funding
3. Science knowledge (ITS)
4. Future plans information exchange
5. Skilled workforce

There are 5 different sources where the identified inputs come from:

1. Network's stakeholders
2. Commercial clients
3. UAB

- 4. UAB Mobility Unit
- 5. Educators

From the surveys' results, it becomes clear that the top 3 most important value flows for ASLOGIC are as follows:

- 1st - Acquired mobility data from the network
- 2nd - Commercial funding from Commercial clients (external partners)
- 3rd - Funding from the networks' stakeholders (co-funding or cost-sharing)

As the network evolves during its life time, and interacts with the external environment, its capabilities define the level of services and the impacts to the society in a compatible way. This process leads to adaptations of the cooperative behaviour of the stakeholders too, as the network reaches higher levels of maturity over time. Thus, the quantitative analysis in CS1 has been extended with a dynamic evolution discretized in three different milestones. It is worthwhile to note that the concept of business ecosystem was introduced in D4.1 as a dynamic view of business networks which behaviour is considered as a complex adaptive system (CAS), which typically includes multiple loops and multiple feedback paths between many interacting entities, as well as inhibitory connections and preferential reactions. Therefore, to explain the *dynamic evolution* of the business ecosystem (and the distinct network) as identified in D4.1, we assume that the business ecosystem goes through three cycles:

- I. Cycle 1 – starting-up
- II. Cycle 2 – growing
- III. Cycle 3 – maturing

The main value flow that drives the innovations is the science knowledge. Therefore, it can be divided into three categories:

Science Knowledge

- 1. ITS-knowledge
- 2. Transport-wide knowledge
- 3. Social science knowledge (social media, communication, dissemination)

We take first, Cycle 1 with the value flow “science knowledge” and hypothetically assign the preferences:

Value flow “science knowledge”	Stakeholder Preference (hypothetical)
Cycle 1	Cycle 1
ITS-knowledge	High
Transport-wide knowledge	Medium
Social science knowledge	Low

For Cycle 2, the same:

Value flow “science knowledge” Cycle 2	Stakeholder Preference (hypothetical) Cycle 2
ITS-knowledge	Medium
Transport-wide knowledge	High
Social science knowledge	Low/Medium

For Cycle 3, the same:

Value flow “science knowledge” Cycle 3	Stakeholder Preference (hypothetical) Cycle 3
ITS-knowledge	Low/Medium
Transport-wide knowledge	Medium
Social science knowledge	High

The rationale for assigning the hypothetical preferences is that in the starting-up stage (cycle 1), the network really needs ITS-science related knowledge in order to be innovative and establish the technology. During the growing stage, the network needs to expand its markets, and therefore wider transport or logistics-related knowledge is in high demand. And in cycle 3, during the maturing stage, stakeholders need to influence the decision-making of customers, for this reason the need of social science-related knowledge is of high preference. This dynamic evolution also leads to stakeholders changing their roles and functions through the life cycle of their ecosystem.

With the introduction of the preferences for ITS-science knowledge through each cycle, the results for the actor “Aslogic” show how the importance of ITS science knowledge diminishes through the life-cycle of the business ecosystem while the need of other science knowledge increases. As such the value flow “ITS Science knowledge” ranks 5 in Cycle 1, and then drops to rank 7 in Cycle 2 and Cycle 3. To score the science knowledge of medium preference, its importance was reduced by a factor of $(1/1.7) = 0.59$, which is a one-step drop in the satisfaction/regret scale (Sutherland, 2009). Similarly, the science-knowledge of low preference, its importance was reduced by a factor of $(0.59 * 0.59) = 0.35$, which is a two-step drop in the satisfaction / regret scale.

This scientific experiment with the assignment of hypothetical preferences was performed only in CS1 to demonstrate the importance of different science-related knowledge through the cycles of the ecosystem. Particularly, the importance of ITS-knowledge has been reduced to provide an opportunity for other scientific knowledge to replace it in due course. The results, for instance, for stakeholder “ASLOGIC” are shown in Table 4, and they were discussed with the rest of stakeholders. The discussion focused on what other knowledge is more important

in Cycle 2 or Cycle 3 for the stakeholders than in Cycle 1 for the whole Barcelona network, and how would they rank this type of knowledge.

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High	Pre-Validation	Cycle 2/Medium	Pre-Validation	Cycle 3/Low	Pre-Validation
			COMBINED Score	Rank	COMBINED Score	Rank	COMBINED Score	Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	0.80	1	0.80	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	0.53	3	0.53	3
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	0.54	2	0.54	2
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.41	5	0.24	7	0.14	7
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	6	0.39	5	0.39	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	7	0.37	6	0.37	6
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	0.49	4	0.49	4

Table 4: ASLOGIC stakeholder's combined scores for all three cycles

Similarly, this process has been repeated for two other stakeholders in CS1 – Members of University Community (end-users) and WEBSAYS – since the “science knowledge” value flow is an input for their operational processes. In the case of Government and Educators as stakeholders, we assume that they will always have high preference for ITS knowledge to design and prepare policy/educational frameworks despite the life-cycle of any business ecosystem.

3.1 CS1 VaoPoint inter-urban carpooling services in Barcelona, Spain

3.1.1 Introduction

CS1's network, originated as a knowledge hub around the University Autonomous Barcelona, evolving through three cycles into a distinct network, is an example of how the modern sharing economy has gained grounds to alter people's way of consumption. It offers an intelligent carpooling service for daily mobility to the campus, where members of the university community can access numerous carpooling offers. It matches users to vehicles that minimize trajectory deviations and promotes the reduction of users' carbon foot by increasing the average occupancy of vehicles.

As described in the previous sections, there are ten stakeholders in this CS1's network and four of them were surveyed with a keen familiarity of how the network operates within the university's ecosystem. These were ASLOGIC, UAB LOGA, UAB Smart Cities, and UAB Mobility Unit – the representatives were predominantly senior personnel of these organisations.

3.1.2 Survey Results and Value Flow Scores

The original questionnaires are attached in the appendix 6.1. The value flow scores were calculated for CS1 following the methodology described in section 3. The survey was used as a first iteration of collecting broader knowledge from the stakeholders with the experiment to test the dynamic changes in the ecosystem. Only in CS1, the data has been collected for three cycles in the case of some actors.

3.1.3 2nd iteration – workshop’s debates to validate

To validate the obtained results, NEWBITS project ran an ideation workshop in Barcelona on 18th January 2018 with representatives of the stakeholders, who were asked to discuss the obtained results from the surveys and also to give relative ranking to the value flow inputs. The objective of the validation process was to create general confidence in our understanding of the CS1 and the applied model. That’s why only a subgroup of value flows was validated, for which it was managed to reach representatives of these stakeholder groups.

As mentioned, all four individuals that filled-in the surveys possessed good understanding of the network’s operations. They scored the value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the questions within the entire model. However, each interviewee did not have detailed information regarding the specific needs of the rest of the stakeholders. Thus, the workshop’s debate of the results provided the representatives with a good platform to interact and explain to the rest of the stakeholders’ network what their specific needs are. It also helped the NEWBITS partners to consult with the representatives from different stakeholder groups and understand better the interactions between all actors. More specifically, the expressed opinions follow below:

ASLOGIC (all cycles)

- One of the results that was considered unexpected was a rank 5 for ITS science knowledge from UAB. After discussing it, the stakeholders came to the conclusion that for Aslogic, unlike any other partner, as it is a technology-based company founded from the university itself and having members of the scientific community on the board of directors, the access to scientific knowledge is simple and internalized. We are sure that for any other company without this resource, the importance would be much greater; becoming surely ranked number 1, but in this case the number 5 looks correct. In the same way, the survey highlighted that where knowledge acquired increases, the feeling about the importance of knowledge decreases. In any case, in cycle 2, nothing would have happened if the rank was 5 but this aspect was not discussed in depth, it was simply mentioned.
- There was an important agreement to reduce the ranking of “commercial funding” from commercial clients, currently ranked 2 when stakeholders proposed a rank 7, moving it to the last position in cycle 1, but keeping it in 2 in the rest of cycles.

Members of University Community (end Users) (Cycle 1)

- On the part of the academia, as a potential user, the only discordance exposed in cycle 1 was about Informative & entertaining content from social media when rank 6 was suggested, instead science knowledge from UAB with a rank 4. Students (i.e. end-

users) represented at the workshop as members of the university community, somehow agreed, they proposed re-ranking of Informative and entertaining content from Websays with a rank 2 and from social media 3 and decreasing science knowledge from UAB down to 10.

- Students suggested, as in cycle 1, re-ranking Informative and entertaining content from Websays with a rank 3 in cycle 2 and also in cycle 3. Leave with 4 Informative and entertaining content from social media in cycle 2 and re-rank with 5 in cycle 3. On the other side, academia validated ranks for cycles 2 and 3.

Rest of stakeholders

The importance of taxes for the Government is perceived with low value, probably a rank of 3 would be much more appropriate.

Despite the unexpected absence of Frontier Cities at the last moment, the rest of the stakeholders concluded that some aspects may be overrated:

- Opinion & Support from Members of Community with a rank 1 suggested to move to 3
- Plans & reports of progress from a rank 2, suggested to move to 4
- UAB Mobility unit validated all the results except mobility planning from “other public administration”, which should be ranked 1
- The stakeholder UAB Management re-ranked funding from government with 4 and mobility planning and know-how from UAB mobility unit with 3

Overall, the workshop’s debate was valuable in providing insights that were not apparent from the original surveys’ results. The representatives from ASLOGIC, the members of university community, the research units of UAB that participated in the validation process provided high confidence in those scores. In addition, interviews with policy-makers in Brussels were conducted that validated the surveys’ results on behalf of the “government” stakeholder.

3.1.4 3rd iteration – expert workshop’s debates to validate

In the third iteration of the tailor-made VNA the experts were involved as a modified Delphi method, where they re-ranked the post-validation ranks of the value flow scores in some occasions, in others the ranks remained the same. To achieve it, the NEWBITS consortium ran a joint group discussion in Barcelona on 22nd March (a sample of the questionnaire is attached in section 6.5).

The final results are as follows. The colours are used merely to distinguish the same value flows from the rest:

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High Pr COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	7		7
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		5
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		3
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.41	5	5		4
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	6	6		Less
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	7	2	Importance	2

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Medium Pr COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	2		2
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		3
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		6
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	5	5		5
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	6	6		Less
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.24	7	7	Importance	7

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 3/Low Pr COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	2		2
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		3
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		6
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	5	5		5
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	6	6		Less
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.14	7	7	Importance	7

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Informative Content & Entertaining Content (social media)	WEBSAYS	Social media	0.73	1	1	↓	1
Mobility Acquired data from UAB campus, others	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.43	2	2		2
Funding	WEBSAYS	Operators	0.34	3	3		3
Skilled workforce	WEBSAYS	Educators	0.34	3	3		3
Future Mobility Plans info	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.29	4	4		4
Funding	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.28	5	5		5
Funding	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	5	
Policy Collaboration (engaging the end-users)	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	Less	5
Science Knowledge	WEBSAYS	UAB	0.27	6	6	Importance	6

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Med Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Cycle 3/Low Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Informative Content & Entertaining Content (social media)	WEBSAYS	Social media	0.73	1	1	0.73	1	1	1
Mobility Acquired data from UAB campus, others	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.43	2	2	0.43	2	2	2
Funding	WEBSAYS	Operators	0.34	3	3	0.34	3	3	3
Skilled workforce	WEBSAYS	Educators	0.34	3	3	0.34	3	3	3
Future Mobility Plans info	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.29	4	4	0.29	4	4	4
Funding	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5	5
Funding	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5	5
Policy Collaboration (engaging the end-users)	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5	5
Science Knowledge	WEBSAYS	UAB	0.16	6	6	0.09	6	6	6

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High pr	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Score	Rank	Rank		
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1		1
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		1
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		2
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		3
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	6		6
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		5
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.31	6	4		4
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	7	7		7
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	8	8		8
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	9	9		9
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	9	9		Less
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	9	9	Importance	9

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Med Pr	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Score	Rank	Rank		
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1		1
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		1
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		2
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		3
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	4		4
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		5
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	6	6		6
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	7	7		7
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	8	8		8
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	8	8		8
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	8	8		Less
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.18	9	9	Importance	9

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 3/Low Pr	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Score	Rank	Rank		
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1		1
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		1
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		2
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		3
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	4		4
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		5
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	6	6		6
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	7	7		7
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	8	8		8
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	8	8		8
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	8	8		Less
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.108	9	9	Importance	9

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Scores	Rank	Rank	Rank
Public Opinions	GOVERNMENT	Members of Community	0.75	1	1	2
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	EU agencies	0.60	2	2	1
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	Other intergovernmental agencies	0.60	2	2	1
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	UAB Mobility Unit	0.49	3	3	3
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	UAB Management	0.46	4	4	3
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	FrontierCities	0.38	5	5	6
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Websays	0.38	5	5	6
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Social media	0.36	6	6	6
Taxes	GOVERNMENT	Members of Community	0.35	7	3	4
ITS Science Knowledge	GOVERNMENT	UAB	0.30	8	7	5
Opinion & Support	FrontierCities	Members of Community	0.49	1	3	3
EU funding	FrontierCities	Public taxes	0.49	1	1	1
Plans and reports of progress	FrontierCities	UAB Mobility Unit	0.47	2	2	2
Plans and reports of progress	FrontierCities	UAB Management	0.47	2	2	2
Acquired Mobility Data	FrontierCities	Network's stakeholders	0.46	3	3	3
Opinion & Support	FrontierCities	European Cities	0.46	3	3	3
Informative content	FrontierCities	Social media	0.41	4	4	4
Science opinions	FrontierCities	UAB	0.31	5	5	5
Cost sharing	FrontierCities	UAB Mobility Unit	0.30	6	6	6
Cost sharing	FrontierCities	UAB LOGA	0.30	6	6	6

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Scores	Rank	Rank	Rank
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Municipality	0.59	1	4	4
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Members of Community	0.59	1	1	1
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Transport operators	0.57	2	2	2
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.52	3	3	3
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.48	4	1	1
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Transport operators	0.44	5	5	5
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.41	6	6	6
Funding	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Government	0.41	6	6	6
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.39	7	7	7
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.37	8	8	8
Skilled workforce	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Educators	0.36	9	9	9
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.28	10	10	10
Monetary rents	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Commercial operators	0.15	11	11	11
Policy Collaboration	UAB Management	UAB Unit	0.62	1	1	1
Policy Collaboration	UAB Management	Other Public Administration	0.54	2	2	2
Funding	UAB Management	Government	0.53	3	4	4
Mobility Planning and know-how	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.47	4	3	3
Funding	UAB Management	Operators	0.45	5	5	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.43	6	6	6
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	Public Administration	0.39	7	7	7
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	Operators	0.39	7	7	7
Skilled workforce	UAB Management	Educators	0.38	8	8	8
Cost sharing	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.21	9	9	9
Funding	UAB Management	Members of Community	0.14	10	10	10

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Educational Material	EDUCATORS	UAB	0.61	1	1	1
Science Knowledge	EDUCATORS	UAB	0.58	2	2	2
Inspired students	EDUCATORS	Members of Community	0.52	3	3	3
Informative content	EDUCATORS	Social Media	0.39	4	4	4
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government (Public taxes)	0.35	5	5	5
Access to existing Research programmes	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	EU programmes	0.78	1	1	1
ITS Science funding	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB	0.57	2	2	2
Acquired Mobility Data	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Network's stakeholders	0.55	3	3	3
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Mobility Unit	0.43	4	4	4
Skilled workforce	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Educators	0.42	5	5	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Management	0.41	6	6	6
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Management	0.38	7	7	7
Informative content	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Social media	0.28	8	8	8
Technology transfers	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.73	1	1	1
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB	0.55	2	2	2
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	IT Service Unit	0.52	3	3	3
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.52	3	3	3
Smart City Acquired data	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.44	4	4	4
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.33	5	5	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB Management	0.31	6	6	6
Skilled workforce	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Educators	0.29	7	7	7
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	IT Service Unit	0.26	8	8	8
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB Management	0.21	9	9	9

Table 5: CS1 stakeholders' combined value flow scores

3.1.5 Value loops, measures and conclusions

Value Loops

By calculating some value loops, this document aims to demonstrate the quantification of stakeholders' interactions that may not only be direct, but also in a value chain of two or three stakeholders. A value loop is a value chain that begins and ends with the same stakeholder. In CS1, the most important value loops will be the ones that begin and end with the UAB Group/ Management, since the university is leading the network from its start.

Value loops show us how value is created and delivered throughout the network. They also illustrate interactions between the actors that are not immediately obvious. The calculation of value loop scores involves a multiplication of each value flow score within the loop (Sutherland, 2009). Usually "larger value loops" are likely to score lower numbers than the shorter value loops, since logically it is more difficult to deliver value by engaging four or five stakeholders than via two or three stakeholders. All figures 25, 26, 27, 28 and 29 below demonstrate examples of value loops with a different length. In Fig. 25 four stakeholders are involved – ASLOGIC, UAB Smart Cities CORE, UAB Mobility Unit, UAB Management / UAB Group (university). The calculation follows below:

ITS Science knowledge from UAB Management → ASLOGIC in Cycle 1

0.41

New Standards, Technology from ASLOGIC → UAB Smart Cities CORE **0.73**

Policy Collaboration from UAB CORE → UAB Mobility Unit **0.52**

Mobility Planning and know-how from UAB Mobility Unit → UAB Management **0.47**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.73 * 0.52 * 0.47 * 0.41 = \mathbf{0.07314}$$

Figure 25: Example of value loop in CS1

In our second example, Fig. 26 only three stakeholders are involved – UAB Mobility unit, Educators and Government, and the interactions follow below:

Plans and reports of progress from UAB Mobility Unit → Government **0.49**

Funding from Government → Educators **0.35**

Skilled workforce from Educators → UAB Mobility Unit **0.36**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.49 * 0.35 * 0.36 = \mathbf{0.06174}$$

Figure 26: Example of value loop in CS1

Both examples demonstrate how the value flows change from one type to another throughout the value loop. In Fig. 25, the ITS science knowledge flow to ASLOGIC becomes data, technology, new standards flow to the UAB Smart Cities CORE, which becomes a policy flow to the other unit of UAB, and subsequently returns to the UAB management as a policy planning flow. In Fig. 26, the future plans and progress reports flow from the UAB Mobility unit to the Government becomes a monetary flow to the Educators, which becomes a skilled workforce flow to the UAB Mobility unit.

In both of the previous examples the UAB Group (university) is a central stakeholder of the network. Since there are more than 100 direct interactions among actors of CS1, the expected loops are likely to be more than 1,000.

In the next example of CS1 (Fig. 27), a very short direct loop is presented with the involvement of the UAB Group/ Management and UAB Mobility unit, which has got a high value creation process. It represents the internal value exchanges between the university as a group and its research units. In this case, the university has a massive influence over the inputs and they can allocate the resources towards the outcomes appropriately. The higher-scoring value loops present better possibilities for the stakeholders to affect the value flows (inputs/outputs) of the network. Note that a low-scoring value loop between the UAB Management and UAB

Mobility Unit presents an event that could easily jeopardise the functioning of the entire business network.

Cost sharing on projects of UAB Management → UAB Mobility unit **0.28**

Mobility Planning and know-how from UAB Mobility unit → UAB Management **0.47**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.28 * 0.47 = \mathbf{0.1316}$$

Figure 27: Example of value loop in CS1

In Fig. 28, we present an indirect value loop where the score can be calculated for the three different life cycles of the network due to the fact that the science knowledge value score varies for each cycle as assumed initially.

In cycle 1:

Science knowledge from UAB Management → Members of community (students) **0.31**

Policy collaboration (engaging end-users) → to UAB Mobility unit **0.59**

Future plans information exchange (UAB Mobility unit) → UAB Management

0.43

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.31 * 0.59 * 0.43 = \mathbf{0.0786}$$

Figure 28: Example of value loop in CS1

In Cycle 2:

Science knowledge from UAB Management → Members of community (students) **0.18**

Policy collaboration (engaging end-users) → to UAB Mobility unit **0.59**

Future plans information exchange (UAB Mobility unit) → UAB Management **0.43**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.18 * 0.59 * 0.43 = \mathbf{0.0457}$$

In Cycle 3:

Science knowledge from UAB Management → Members of community (students)	0.108
Policy collaboration (engaging end-users) → to UAB Mobility unit	0.59
Future plans information exchange (UAB Mobility unit) → UAB Management	0.43

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.108 * 0.59 * 0.43 = \mathbf{0.0274}$$

This dynamic evolution of value loop scores presented above in regards to the need of science knowledge is not just a characteristic of CS1, it could rather be extrapolated to other business networks which reach markets with a mature product but no chance of further evolution.

In Fig. 29, the following flows are presented:

Employment opportunities from UAB Group /Management → Members of community	0.23
Mobility data picked at the campuses from Students → Websays	0.43
Information content from Websays → to UAB LOGA	0.28
Cost sharing between UAB LOGA and UAB Group → UAB Management	0.38

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.23 * 0.43 * 0.28 * 0.38 = \mathbf{0.0105}$$

Figure 29: Example of value loop in CS1

If these value loops are arranged, it reveals that the direct interactions between the central stakeholder (UAB Management) and its research units create and deliver higher value than the other interactions between UAB and the rest of stakeholders.

Rank	Score	FROM	TO	Value Flow Type
1.	0.13	UAB Management	UAB Mobility unit	Knowledge, Funding
2.	0.078 C1	UAB Management	Members of community, UAB Mobility unit, UAB Group/ Management	Science knowledge, Policy collaboration, Future plans

3.	0.073	UAB Management	ASLOGIC, UAB CORE, UAB Mobility unit and UAB Management	Science knowledge, standards, technology, policy collaboration and mobility planning
4.	0.06	UAB Mobility Unit	Government, Educators, and UAB	Future plans, funding, skilled workforce
5.	0.04 C2	UAB Management	Members of community, UAB Mobility unit, UAB Group/ Management	Science knowledge, Policy collaboration, Future plans
6.	0.027 C3	UAB Management	Members of community, UAB Mobility unit, UAB Group/ Management	Science knowledge, Policy collaboration, Future plans
7.	0.01	UAB Group / Management	Members of community, WEBSAYS, UAB LOGA and UAB Group	Employment, Information content Data, Cost sharing

Table 6: CS1 ranking of value loops

In addition, the table below summarises the most important value flows for the CS1's network with rank 1. The combined scores are in the range of [0.49 – 0.80]. All scores of the network are in the range of [0.10 – 0.80]. Of these 13 most significant value flows for the Barcelona network, in 85% of the cases the stakeholders validated ranks and the expert ranks coincided. There is a slight disagreement only about the value input “Public Opinions” and “Compliance with EU/intergovernmental agencies” between the stakeholders and the experts when it comes to the governmental role in the network and their needs (coloured in pale blue in the table). The UAB Group is involved in 33% of the important interactions.

Stakeholder	Value Flow	SCORE	Stakeholders validated rank	Expert rank
1. ASLOGIC	Acquired Mobility Data	0.80	1	1
2. UAB LOGA	Access to existing EU Research programmes	0.78	1	1
3. UAB CORE	Technology transfers	0.73	1	1

4. UAB Management	Policy Collaboration	0.62	1	1
5. UAB Mobility unit	Policy Collaboration engaging Members of university community	0.59	1	1
6. FrontierCities	EU funding	0.49	1	1
7. Websays	Informative & entertaining content (social media)	0.73	1	1
8. Members of Community	1. Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	0.49	1	1
	2. Rewards	0.49	1	1
9. Government (indirect role)	1. Public opinions	0.75	1	2
	2. Compliance with EU policy directions	0.60	2	1
	3. Compliance with intergovernmental policy directions	0.60	2	1
10. Educators (indirect role)	Educational material	0.61	1	1

Table 7: CS1 stakeholders' most important direct value flows

3.2 CS2 C-ITS City mobility platform in Verona, Italy

Responsible Partner: TTS

3.2.1 Introduction

CS2 demonstrates how public authorities aim to reduce negative effects of externalities. The City of Verona institutionally established the externality market as a Network Orchestrator. The case focuses on the urban road transport mode, with the primary involvement of private users and public transport (secondary). It is restricted to the City of Verona in Italy, but the model has been already sold to a few North European cities. Communications are based on cooperative-ITS real-time messages that can both run on short-range and long-range communication systems (by Telecom Italia). It is intended to improve the urban traffic performances, through improving driving behaviours' and control systems.

As mentioned before, CS2's network consists of nine stakeholders who together create the value delivered through the network. Two major stakeholders were interviewed – Municipality of Verona and Swarco Mizar – plus two citizens from the city representing the end-users. The Case study leader conducted the interviews in Italian with two senior representatives from the municipality and Swarco Mizar. Verona municipality has a vital role in organizing the activities of the network, and Swarco Mizar delivers the ITS services.

3.2.2 Survey Results and Value Flow Scores

The original questionnaires are attached in the appendix 6.2 after the profiles of all stakeholders. The value flow scores were calculated for CS2 following the methodology described in section 3. The survey was used as a first iteration of collecting broader knowledge from the Italian stakeholders.

3.2.3 2nd iteration – workshop's debates to validate

To validate the obtained results, NEWBITS project ran an ideation workshop in Verona on 22nd February 2018 with representatives of the stakeholders, who were asked to discuss the obtained results from the surveys and also to give relative ranking to the value flow inputs. The objective of the validation process was to create general confidence in the thorough understanding of the CS2 and the applied VNA model. That's why only a subgroup of value flows was validated, for which it was managed to reach representatives of these stakeholder groups. Some of the commercial actors were not easy to contact due to business trips or work.

As mentioned, the major stakeholders' individuals that filled-in the surveys possessed broader understanding of the network's operations. They scored the value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the questions within the entire model. However, each interviewee did not have detailed information regarding the specific needs of the rest of the stakeholders. Thus, the workshop's debate of the results provided the representatives with a good platform to interact and explain to the rest of the stakeholders' network what their specific needs are. It also helped the NEWBITS partners to consult with the representatives from different

stakeholder groups and understand better the interactions between all actors. More specifically, the expressed opinions follow below. In addition, interviews with policy-makers in Brussels were conducted that validated the surveys' results on behalf of the "government" stakeholder.

A comprehensive discussion took place to present the results of the value flow survey analysis results undertaken in December 2017 as it was needed to go through the objectives, methodology and results of the analysis since several participants had not taken part in the survey. This ensured a much wider participation to the survey validation exercise undertaken with the attending stakeholders. It was therefore decided to go through the relevant survey results with each of the stakeholder group's representative at the workshop, so that their feedback and any suggestion could be discussed properly.

In more details:

- **ATV** - they agreed in full with the pre-validation ranking made, but also highlighted the Transit Signal Priority input coming from sources such as Swarco Mizar and Verona Municipality as the most important to them. Therefore, they justified the greater deviation from the value flow score in 3rd position, i.e. general knowledge.

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Agree/Disagree
			SCORE	Rank	If not, please re-rank
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Swarco Mizar	0.50	2	
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Municipality of Verona	0.56	1	
Funding	ATV	FP7 Research funding - European	0.25	5	
Traffic acquired data / purchase of traffic data	ATV	Telecom Italia	0.06	6	
General knowledge (technical, social)	ATV	Network's stakeholders	0.31	3	
Skilled Workforce	ATV	Educators	0.30	4	

- **Verona Municipality** - they also validated the results presented with ITS innovative services being in the first position. In addition, they stated that their primary objective is to keep the technological infrastructure and services developed and tested so far up to speed, while keeping up the pace with rapid technological advancements and trying to minimize the high maintenance costs.
- **Swarco Mizar** - the pre-validation ranking was confirmed by Swarco who made one single observation and suggestion for a change. They changed the value flow denomination "Acquired Traffic Data" with "Traffic Data Access" since they did not need to acquire any data for realising the Verona C-ITS service, but they would rather need Verona municipality to grant them access to traffic data.
- **ACI (end-users association)** - they confirmed the value flow ranking, although they would have probably interchanged value flows at ranks 2 and 3. However, they admitted that they presented a slightly different score, and validated everything in the end without any change.

Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.42	3	
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.37	5	
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AVT	0.33	7	
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Telecom Italia	0.36	6	
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AUDI	0.40	4	
General knowledge and information	CITIZENS (end-users)	Educators	0.57	1	
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.57	1	
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Swarco Mizar	0.52	2	

- **Italian Ministry of Transport** - they were in full agreement with the value flow ranking presented and confirmed that the impact on taxes is definitely the most important value flow interaction to them.

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED SCORE	Pre-Validation Rank	Agree/Disagree If not, please re-rank
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	EU agencies	0.21	4	
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	Other intergovernmental agencies	0.21	4	
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.18	6	
Science knowledge	GOVERNMENT	Educators	0.19	5	
Public opinions	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.47	2	
Innovative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.28	3	
TAXES	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.49	1	

Later in April 2018, interviews with policy-makers in Brussels were conducted in order to validate the rankings of the stakeholder “government”.

3.2.4 3rd iteration – expert workshop’s debates to validate

In the third iteration of the tailor-made VNA the experts were involved on the basis of an applied modified Delphi method, where they re-ranked the post-validation ranks of the value flow scores in some occasions, in others the ranks remained the same. To achieve it, the NEWBITS consortium ran a joint group discussion in Barcelona on 22nd March 2018.

The final results are as follows. The colours in the tables below are merely used to distinguish the same value flows from the rest:

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED SCORE	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Municipality of Verona	0.56	1	1	↓ Less Importance	1
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Swarco Mizar	0.50	2	2		2
General knowledge (technical, social)	ATV	Network's stakeholders	0.31	3	3		3
Skilled Workforce	ATV	Educators	0.30	4	4		4
Funding	ATV	FP7 Research funding - European	0.25	5	5		5
Traffic acquired data / purchase of traffic data	ATV	Telecom Italia	0.06	6	6		6
Mobility acquired data (AUDI purchase of Skilled Workforce)	AUDI	Swarco Mizar	0.76	1	1	↓ Less Importance	1
Mobility acquired data (AUDI purchase of Skilled Workforce)	AUDI	Educators	0.76	1	1		1
Mobility acquired data (AUDI purchase of Skilled Workforce)	AUDI	Telecom Italia	0.54	2	2		2
Science knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	Network's stakeholders	0.35	3	3		3
Science knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	AUDI R&D department	0.35	3	3		3
General knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	Municipality	0.18	4	4		4
Partial funding	AUDI	FP7 Research funding - European	0.15	5	5	5	

Innovative ITS services	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Swarco Mizar	0.49	1	1	Greater	1
Future Plans information	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Network's stakeholders	0.29	2	2	Importance	2
Future Plans information	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Government	0.28	3	3	↓	3
Skilled Workforce	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Educators	0.15	4	4		4
Cost sharing	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Network's stakeholders (incl. FP7 COMPASS4D project)	0.12	5	5	↓	5
Mobility acquired data	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Telecom Italia	0.04	6	6	Less	6
Mobility acquired data	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	AUDI	0.04	6	6	Importance	6
Educational material	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.47	1	1	Greater	1
Policy direction	EDUCATORS	Government	0.37	2	2	↓	4
Science knowledge	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.27	3	3		2
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government (public taxes)	0.27	3	3	Less	5
Inspired students	EDUCATORS	Citizens	0.22	4	4	Importance	3

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED SCORE	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Taxes	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.49	1	1	↓	5
Public opinions	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.47	2	2		2
Innovative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.28	3	3	↓	6
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	EU agencies	0.21	4	4		1
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	Other intergovernmental agencies	0.21	4	4	↓	1
Science knowledge	GOVERNMENT	Educators	0.19	5	5	Less	3
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.18	6	6	Importance	4
General knowledge and information	CITIZENS (end-users)	Educators	0.57	1	1	Greater	1
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.57	1	1	Importance	1
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Swarco Mizar	0.52	2	2	↓	2
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.42	3	3		3
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AUDI	0.40	4	4	↓	4
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.37	5	5		5
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Telecom Italia	0.36	6	6	Less	6
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AVT	0.33	7	7	Importance	7

Skilled Workforce	SWARCO MIZAR	Educators	0.86	1	1	Greater	7
Traffic data access	SWARCO MIZAR	Verona Municipality	0.70	2	2	Importance	1
Traffic data access	SWARCO MIZAR	ITS platform	0.34	3	3		1
Science knowledge	SWARCO MIZAR	Swarco Mizar R&D department	0.31	4	4		2
Science knowledge	SWARCO MIZAR	Educators	0.31	4	4		6
Public Mobility Services	SWARCO MIZAR	Municipality's strategic plan - Verona	0.30	5	5		5
Partial funding	SWARCO MIZAR	FP7 Research funding - European	0.28	6	6	Less	3
Future Plans information exchange	SWARCO MIZAR	Municipality	0.14	7	7	Importance	4
Pre-existing and innovative ITS services	TAXI-OPERATORS	Swarco Mizar	0.23	1	1	Greater	1
Real-time data	TAXI-OPERATORS	AUDI (cars)	0.22	2	2	Importance	1
Pre-existing and innovative ITS services	TAXI-OPERATORS	Municipality	0.19	3	3		1
Real-time data	TAXI-OPERATORS	Telecom Italia (messages)	0.15	4	4		2
General information	TAXI-OPERATORS	Municipality	0.14	5	5	Less	3
Skilled workforce	TAXI-OPERATORS	Educators	0.03	6	6	Importance	4
Skilled Workforce	TELECOMITALIA	Educators	0.86	1	1	Greater	8
Policy directions in smart services for the public sector	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.26	2	2	Importance	6
Policy directions in smart services for the public sector	TELECOMITALIA	Government	0.26	2	2		6
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.23	3	3		1
Future Plans information exchange	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.22	4	4		4
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Swarco Mizar	0.21	5	5		2
Science knowledge	TELECOMITALIA	Educators	0.18	6	6		8
Science knowledge	TELECOMITALIA	Telecom Italia R&D department	0.14	7	7	Less	5
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Citizens	0.12	8	8	Importance	3

Table 8: CS2 stakeholders' combined value flow scores

3.2.5 Value loops, measures and conclusions

Value Loops

Similarly, with CS1, in this section we will show five examples of value loops from CS2 following the same method for calculating them as in section 3.1.5. The value loop begins and ends with the same stakeholder. Figures 30, 31, 32, 33 and 34 illustrate value loops with a different length, representing the value creation process in our CS2. In Fig. 30 the stakeholders involved are Municipality of Verona, Swarco Mizar, Citizens and the Government. In CS2 the central stakeholder is Municipality of Verona as they initially orchestrated the network and now maintain the digital infrastructure. Therefore, all loops begin and end with the Municipality.

Traffic data access from Verona municipality → Swarco Mizar **0.70**

Online mobile applications from Swarco Mizar → Citizens (end-users) **0.52**

Public opinions from Citizens → Government **0.47**

Public funding from Government → Verona municipality **0.28**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.70 * 0.52 * 0.47 * 0.28 = \mathbf{0.0479}$$

Figure 30: Example of value loop in CS2

In Fig. 31 example, the value loop is shorter with only three stakeholders involved – Municipality of Verona, Telecom Italia and Government. The value created within the loop is fairly low in comparison to the previous example. All five examples of value loop scores in CS2 demonstrate a lower value creation process in comparison to the examples discussed in CS1. Although these are understandably two very different cases, it is interesting to observe how value has been delivered throughout networks in various EU Member states.

- Plans and reports of progress from the municipality → Government **0.18**
- Policy directions in smart services for the public sector → Telecomitalia **0.26**
- Mobility acquired data from Telecomitalia → Verona municipality **0.04**

Value loop score = $0.18 * 0.26 * 0.04 = \mathbf{0.0018}$

Figure 31: Example of value loop in CS2

Both examples demonstrate how the type of value flows change within the same loop. In Fig.30, the data flow from Verona municipality to Swarco Mizar becomes mobile applications flow to the citizens, which turns into public opinions flow to the government, and then becomes public funding from the government back to the municipality. In Fig. 31, plans & reports of progress flow from the Verona municipality to the government, becomes policy directions flow to Telecomitalia, which becomes mobility data flow. Since there are about 60 direct interactions among network's actors, the expected value loops are less than 1,000. Verona municipality participates in 25% of the value flows identified.

In the next example (Fig. 32), it is presented a very short loop with two stakeholders involved – Municipality of Verona as a central actor and Audi.

Technical and social knowledge / content from the Municipality → Audi **0.38**

Mobility acquired data from Audi → Municipality **0.04**

Value loop score = $0.38 * 0.04 = 0.0152$

Figure 32: Example of value loop in CS2

In Fig. 33, the following flows are presented:

Cost sharing with EU agencies → between Municipality and EU agencies **0.12**

Policy direction from EU agencies → Government **0.21**

Future plans information from Government → Verona municipality **0.28**

Value loop score = $0.12 * 0.21 * 0.28 = 0.0070$

Figure 33: Example of value loop in CS2

In Fig. 34, the presented indirect value loop involves only two stakeholders – Municipality of Verona and TelecomItalia. The direct value flows follow below:

Policy directions in smart services for the public sector from Verona municipality → to Telecom Italia **0.26**

Mobility data from Telecom Italia → to Municipality **0.04**

The calculation of the value loop happens by multiplication of the combined value flow scores as described in section 3.1.5.

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.26 * 0.04 = \mathbf{0.0104}$$

Figure 34: Example of value loop in CS2

Even though this value loop is relatively short, the value creation process is comparatively low too, once more than three stakeholders are involved it becomes lower. However, all examples of value loops (indirect and direct) were presented in this report in order to give a better understanding among stakeholders for the value flows that also create and deliver value, but sometimes they seem invisible, hidden behind the direct actors' interactions. Discussions among network's stakeholders should focus on the indirect value loops too, so that they can understand properly the entire process of value creation and enrich their knowledge about the opportunities that the network provides during its life stages.

If the exemplary five value loops are arranged by score, the ranking looks like:

Rank	Score	FROM	TO	Value Flow Type
------	-------	------	----	-----------------

1.	0.047	VERONA Municipality	Swarco Mizar, Citizens, Government, Municipality	Traffic data, mobile apps, public opinions and funding
2.	0.015	VERONA Municipality	AUDI	Knowledge, Data
3.	0.010	VERONA Municipality	Telecom Italia	Policy directions, Data
4.	0.007	VERONA Municipality	EU Agencies, Government	Cost sharing, Policy directions, Future plans
5.	0.0018	VERONA Municipality	Government, Telecomitalia, Municipality	Plans, policy directions and mobility data

Table 9: CS2 ranking of value loops

In addition, the table below summarizes the most important interactions ranked 1 and two ranked #2, #3. There are in total 12 value flows that are inputs to the relevant stakeholders of significant importance. The value flow scores range between [0.23 – 0.86]. All flow scores are in the range of [0.04 – 0.86]. In 58% of the cases, the stakeholders' validated ranks and the expert ranks coincided, obviously there is a higher discrepancy in CS2 than what we observed in CS1. The opinion differences appear regarding inputs to Swarco Mizar, Telecomitalia and the Government (coloured in pale pink and purple in the table 10). In the case of Swarco Mizar and Telecomitalia, their internal R&D departments play a crucial role in the creation and dissemination of knowledge and innovation, which explains the importance put on skilled workforce by the stakeholders. However, the experts felt that in the current status of the Verona network, the traffic data access and sustainable mobility services create higher value, and hence, they are considered as more important value flows in this life stage of the network.

Stakeholder	Value Flow	SCORE	Stakeholders validated rank	Expert rank
1. VERONA Municipality	Innovative ITS services	0.49	1	1
2. AUDI	Mobility data (purchase)	0.76	1	1
	Skilled workforce	0.76	1	1
3. Swarco Mizar	Skilled workforce	0.86	1	7

	Traffic data access	0.70	2	1
4. TelecomItalia	Skilled workforce	0.86	1	8
	Sustainable mobility services from the municipality	0.23	3	1
5. ATV	Transit Signal Priority	0.56	1	1
6. Citizens	General knowledge and information	0.57	1	1
7. Government (indirect role)	Taxes	0.49	1	5
8. Educators (indirect role)	Educational materials	0.47	1	1
9. Taxi Operators	Innovative ITS services	0.23	1	1

Table 10: CS2 stakeholders' most important direct value flows

3.3 CS3 Synchro-modal container transport corridor, Rotterdam - Limburg

Responsible Partner: CED

3.3.1 Introduction

CS3's network establishment was triggered by TNO (a Dutch research organisation) that monitors the early stages of the business ecosystem evolution. After the pilot stage, TNO usually withdraws from any operational activities. The case represents an example of how businesses use analytics to sustain competitive advantages. The innovation lies on the design and deployment of a web-based service allowing logistics agents to monitor data about handling and transporting containers 24/7. It is an information service enabling actors to plan, manage and synchronise available capacity in benefit of the logistic process of the container corridor Rotterdam – Limburg.

CS3's network consists of 13 local stakeholders from the Netherlands, and seven of them were interviewed initially to provide the generic knowledge about the actors' interactions. These stakeholders are TNO, Dinalog, Port of Rotterdam, Shipper, Warehouse operator, Portdat, and Business clients. All of them undertook the surveys in Dutch. Interviewees come from various managerial levels of the companies with very good understanding of the logistics industry.

3.3.2 Survey Results and Value Flow Scores

The original questionnaires in English are attached in the appendix 6.3 after the profiles of all stakeholders. The value flow scores were calculated for CS3 similarly to CS1, CS2 by following the methodology described in section 3. The survey was used as a first iteration of collecting broader knowledge from the local stakeholders.

3.3.3 2nd iteration – workshop's debates to validate

To validate the obtained results, NEWBITS project ran an ideation workshop in Venlo on 14th February 2018 with representatives of the stakeholders, who were asked to discuss the obtained results from the surveys and also to give relative ranking to the value flow inputs. The objective of the validation process was to create general confidence in the understanding of the CS3 and our applied model. That's why only a subgroup of value flows was validated, for which it was managed to reach representatives of these stakeholder groups. However, the case study leader managed to reach a representative of a large proportion of all stakeholders.

As mentioned, the major stakeholders' individuals that filled-in the surveys possessed broader understanding of the network's operations. They scored the value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the questions within the entire model. However, each interviewee did not have detailed information regarding the specific needs of the rest of the stakeholders. Thus, the workshop's debate of the results provided the representatives with a good platform to interact and explain to the rest of the stakeholders' network what their specific needs are. It also helped the NEWBITS partners to consult with the representatives from different stakeholder groups and understand better the interactions between all actors. More specifically, the expressed opinions follow below. In addition, interviews with policy-makers in Brussels were conducted that validated the surveys' results on behalf of the "government" stakeholder.

Value inputs to shipper

- The top 6 value inputs are recognized as being important and it makes sense that the 3 most important inputs come from warehouse L. The service brings value when Warehouse L can improve the predictability in the logistic process and allows for earlier delivery to the retailers. It also reduces any phone discussions on non-conformance in transport time between the shipper and the warehouse operator.
- The extra value flow identified in the survey: “Monitoring of the delivery process, highlighting potential delays” is completely understandable. By including the outbound delivery process from the warehouse, it is considered an important next step in the service development but not a priority at this stage of the network’s evolution.
- The other value flows are qualified more as preconditions.

Value inputs to Warehouse L

- The value flows “Higher predictability of container arrival” delivered by ITO and “easier access to order and planning container info” from the platform service provider: are indeed considered very important inputs resulting from the service to Warehouse L. This is acknowledged by the representative of Warehouse L. For the latter flow it was explained that only an updated planning already brought more ease in the logistics process.
- It is noted that the value flow “Faster/ earlier arrival at warehouse” is ranked 6 whereas “earlier delivery to the retailers” for the shipper is ranked 2. Warehouse L’s representative remarks that if this faster delivery is considered important to the shipper, it should also be considered by Warehouse L as being (more) important.

Value inputs to ITO

- The ranking is recognizable for ITO and the other stakeholders. The number 1 value flow “more reliable container release time at deep sea terminal” is indeed important and influences the needs of the other logistic partners. The container release time in the deep-sea port is one of the most unpredictable events in the logistics process and therefore up-to-date planning information on the container released time is considered very important to be improved by the service. The value flow “improved real time info on container status at deep sea terminal”, which is ranked 2 is supportive.
- It is also considered very important by ITO and the group that the container status is shared with the other logistic partners in a neutral/ transparent way. This will prevent continuously updating by ITO when a container is delayed at the deep-sea port. The port information is already available to ITO, but they value the sharing of the information in a neutral and transparent way.

Value inputs to Information service provider

- The group notes that the distinction between the needs for the information service provider and the platform developer are not always clear. Are the information flows needed to run the service input to the provider or to the developer? In practice it might be the same company taking both roles.
- Most needs are recognized as pre-conditions for running the service.

- The meaning of “skilled workforce” is discussed and interpreted as being able i) to understand the context of the data, ii) to be able to combine the interests of the logistic partners in the service.

Value inputs to Platform developer/ maintainer

- The distinction between the needs for the information service provider and the needs of the platform developer were not always clear.
- Technical knowledge scores with rank 1. Technical IT knowledge is important and it is a key intangible asset for the ICT/ ITS companies. It is therefore not a specific need for the service, but more a precondition. Technical knowledge can also be interpreted as domain knowledge (within the container logistics context), which is needed for the service. It was proposed to rank “technical knowledge from information service provider” with a lower rank.

Value inputs to others

- The value flow to Portdat “authorization to share data”, will not come from ITO. The value flow can be removed.
- The value flow “operational service ...” is considered more important by the Port of Rotterdam than it follows from the ranking. A re-ranking is proposed.
- Many other value flows are considered pre-conditional to develop the service.

3.3.4 3rd iteration – expert workshop’s debates to validate

In the third iteration of the tailor-made VNA the experts were involved on the basis of an applied modified Delphi method, where they re-ranked the post-validation ranks of the value flow scores in some occasions, in others the ranks remained the same. To achieve it, the NEWBITS consortium ran a joint group discussion in Barcelona on 22nd March. (A sample of the questionnaire is attached in section 6.5).

The final results follow below. The colours are solely used to distinguish the same value flows from the rest:

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank		
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.57	1	1	↓	1
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.49	2	2		2
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.47	3	3		3
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.43	4	4		4
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.40	5	5		5
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Deep-sea terminal	0.39	6	6		6
Improved contract conditions with sea shipping company (reduction n costs and time)	Shipper	shipping company/Inland ope	0.33	7	7		7
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.31	8	8		8
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.31	8	8		8
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.30	9	9		9
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Deep-sea terminal	0.29	10	10		10
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.24	11	11		11
Skilled Workforce	Shipper	Educators	0.24	12	12		13
Real-time information container transport	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.22	13	13		12
Technical knowledge	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.17	14	14		14
Technical knowledge	Shipper	TNO	0.14	15	15	Less	15
NEW: MONITORING OF THE DELIVERY PROCESSES, MOSTLY INDICATION OF POTENTIAL DELAYS	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.06	16	16	Importance	Deleted

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank		
Higher predictability of container arrival at warehouse	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.53	1	1	↓	1
Easier access to order and planning container info	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service developer	0.49	2	2		2
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.48	3	3		3
Real-time information container status	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service developer	0.42	4	4		4
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.37	5	5		5
Faster/earlier container arrival at warehouse	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.31	6	6		6
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service provider	0.30	7	7		7
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.23	8	8		8
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.22	9	9		9
Technical knowledge	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service provider	0.22	9	9		9
New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (transport time)	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.21	10	10		10
Skilled Workforce	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Educators	0.20	11	11		11
New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (transport time)	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.18	12	12		Less
Technical knowledge	Warehousing/Logistic Services	TNO	0.17	13	13	Importance	13

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank		
More reliable container release time at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1	↓	1
Improved real-time info on container status at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.55	2	2		2
Total logistic chain visibility (information from all partners at once)	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.43	3	3		3
Neutral/transparent way of sharing container status info with partners	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.42	4	4		4
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.39	5	5		5
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.37	6	6		6
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.36	7	7		7
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.36	7	7		7
Skilled Workforce	Inland terminal operator	Educators	0.33	8	8		8
Earlier container pick-up at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.32	9	9		9
Technical knowledge	Inland terminal operator	Platform operator	0.26	10	10		10
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.23	11	11		11
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.23	11	11		11
New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (transport time)	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.22	12	12		12
Technical knowledge	Inland terminal operator	TNO	0.20	13	13	Less	13
New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (transport time)	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.18	14	14	Importance	14

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Scores	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Technical knowledge	Information service provider	Platform operator	0.60	1	1		1
Skilled Workforce	Information service provider	Educators	0.60	1	1		1
Future contract conditions with platform developer (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Platform developer	0.59	2	2		2
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	Logistic Partners	0.58	3	3		3
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	TNO	0.52	4	4		4
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	LIOF	0.50	5	5		5
Flexibility with respect to platform functionality and information sources	Information service provider	Platform developer	0.47	6	6		6
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Inland terminal operator	0.46	7	7		7
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.45	8	8		8
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Shipper	0.42	9	9	Less	9
Technical knowledge	Information service provider	TNO	0.40	10	10	Importance	10

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Technical knowledge	Platform developer/maintenance	Platform operator	0.75	1	6		7
Authorisation to include container status data in the platform	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.71	2	1		1
Agreements to share/use deep-sea terminal data	Platform developer/maintenance	Deep-sea terminal	0.69	3	2		2
Authorisation to include container status data in the platform	Platform developer/maintenance	Sea-shipping company	0.69	3	2		2
Agreements to share/use deep-sea terminal data	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.67	4	3		3
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Inland terminal operator	0.58	5	4		4
Technical knowledge	Platform developer/maintenance	TNO	0.57	6	7		8
Container status at deep-sea terminal (handling, customs)	Platform developer/maintenance	Deep-sea terminal	0.50	7	5		5
Container status at deep-sea terminal (handling, customs)	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.50	7	5		5
Skilled Workforce	Platform developer/maintenance	Educators	0.48	8	8		9
Vessel arrival info from sea shipping companies	Platform developer/maintenance	Sea-shipping terminal	0.41	9	9		6
Vessel arrival info from sea shipping companies	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.41	9	9		6
Future contract conditions with info service provider (costs, payment structure)	Platform developer/maintenance	Information service provider	0.40	10	10		10
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	AISHUB	0.39	11	11		11
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.39	11	11		11
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Shipper	0.37	12	12		12
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	FleetM	0.37	12	12	Less	12
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	NDW	0.36	13	13	Importance	13

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1		1
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Sea-shipping company	0.57	1	1		1
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Deep-sea terminal	0.52	2	2		2
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Sea-shipping terminals	0.49	3	3		3
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Inland terminal operator	0.45	4	Deleted Flow		Deleted
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Inland terminal operator	0.43	5	4		4
Technical knowledge of the functionality	Portdat	Platform operator	0.37	6	5		5
Shared policy goals with Port of Rotterdam	Portdat	Port of Rotterdam	0.34	7	6		6
Skilled Workforce	Portdat	Educators	0.34	7	6	Less	6
Technical knowledge of the functionality	Portdat	Platform operator	0.24	8	7	Importance	7

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Portdat	0.45	1	1	↓ Less Importance	1
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Government	0.44	2	3		3
Understanding of the functioning of the service to disseminate to others	Port of Rotterdam	Platform developer	0.42	3	4		4
Skilled Workforce	Port of Rotterdam	Educators	0.34	4	5		5
Operational service: real-time data about hinterland container transport	Port of Rotterdam	Platform developer	0.32	5	2		2
Understanding of the functioning of the service to disseminate to others	Port of Rotterdam	TNO	0.31	6	6		6
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Platform service provider	0.28	7	7		7
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	TNO	0.24	8	8		8

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Project funding for pilot (TNO representing the Stakeholders Group)	TNO (RESEARCH)	Dinalog	0.64	1	1	↓ Less Importance	1
Stakeholder input for development of service functionalities	TNO (RESEARCH)	Consortium/Network	0.61	2	2		2
Skilled Workforce	TNO (RESEARCH)	Educators	0.48	3	3		3
Market awareness of business case development of the pilot project	TNO (RESEARCH)	Consortium/Network	0.43	4	4		4
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Government	0.36	5	5		5
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Port of Rotterdam	0.32	6	6		6
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Dinalog	0.32	6	6		6
Pilot results to build-on for new projects	DINALOG	TNO	0.57	1	1		1
Cost-sharing in pilot phase (co-financing of projects)	DINALOG	Consortium/Network	0.47	2	2		2
Skilled Workforce	DINALOG	Educators	0.36	3	3		3
Policy Directions	DINALOG	Government	0.32	4	4	Less	4
Policy Directions	DINALOG	Consortium/Network	0.24	5	5	Importance	5

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert	
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank	
Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	TNO	0.61	1	1	↓ Less Importance	1	
Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Platform service operator	0.56	2	2		2	
Technical and economic info about the service to support market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	TNO	0.43	3	3		3	
Technical and economic info about the service to support market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Platform developer	0.37	4	4		4	
Funding (from Government)	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Government	0.34	5	5		5	
Skilled workforce/ trained employees	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Educators	0.23	6	6		6	
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government	0.28	1	1		1	
Science knowledge of ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.23	2	2		2	
Science knowledge of ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Other Consortium Partners	0.21	3	3		3	
Inspired students for ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Citizens	0.2	4	4		4	
New Educational material related to ICT/ITS challenges	EDUCATORS	TNO	0.18	5	5		Less	5
New Educational material related to ICT/ITS challenges	EDUCATORS	Other Consortium Partners	0.14	6	6		Importance	6

Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	Port of Rotterdam	0.47	1	1	Greater	1
Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.47	1	1	Importance	1
Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.47	1	1		1
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.40	2	2		9
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.38	3	3		2
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.35	4	4		7
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.33	5	5		5
Science knowledge (service related)	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.23	6	6		6
Skilled Workforce	GOVERNMENT	Educators	0.21	7	7		8
Science knowledge (service related)	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.20	8	8		3
Corporate taxes and public taxation	GOVERNMENT	Consortium/Network	0.11	9	9		4
Authorisation for data sharing with platform	FleetM	Inland terminal operator	0.72	1	1		1
Technical knowledge of the functionality	FleetM	Platform developer	0.48	2	2		2
Skilled Workforce	FleetM	Educators	0.43	3	3	Less	3
Technical knowledge of the functionality	FleetM	TNO	0.34	4	4	Importance	4

Table 11: CS3 stakeholders' combined value flow scores

3.3.5 Value loops, measures and conclusions

Value Loops

By calculating five value loops, this section aims to demonstrate the quantification of stakeholders' interactions in CS3 of NEWBITS. These interactions are not only direct, but also in a value chain of two, three or more stakeholders. A value loop is a value chain that begins and ends with the same stakeholder and in CS3 the most important value loops will be the ones that begin and end with the Platform Developer /Maintenance, since they are collecting all data information and returning back to stakeholders the relevant content and functionalities.

In Fig. 35, the value loop involves only three stakeholders – Platform Developer, the Shipper and the Inland Terminal Operator. It is a relatively short loop.

Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services from the Platform Developer to → Shipper **0.24**

Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time from Shipper

to → Inland terminal operator **0.37**

Planning and container status information from the Inland terminal operator

to → Platform Developer **0.58**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.24 * 0.37 * 0.58 = \mathbf{0.0515}$$

Figure 35: Example of value loop in CS3

In Fig. 36, the example represents a larger indirect value loop with five stakeholders involved – Platform Developer, Information service provider, TNO, Inland terminal operator and FleetM. As the logic foresees the larger loops have lower value scores since it is more difficult to deliver value through a longer value chain where more stakeholders are involved and the time factor plays a role. It also shows that the platform developer will have less influence over the inputs, no matter how much efforts towards the outputs are initially allocated. Measuring the impact from such low-scoring value loops is less effective.

Technical knowledge from Platform Developer → Information service provider **0.60**

Stakeholder input for development of service functionalities (in the pilot phase) from Information service provider → TNO **0.61**

General technical knowledge from TNO → Inland terminal operator **0.20**

Authorisation for data sharing with platform from Inland terminal → FleetM **0.72**

Real-time data for trucks from FleetM → Platform Developer **0.37**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.60 * 0.61 * 0.20 * 0.72 * 0.37 = \mathbf{0.0195}$$

Figure 36: Example of value loop in CS3

Similarly, to the previous two cases (CS1, CS2), the examples of CS3 show us how the value flows convert from one type to another within the same value loop. For instance, in Fig. 36 the knowledge value flow from the Developer becomes a service flow to TNO, which turns into general knowledge flow to the Inland terminal, and then becomes authorisation for data sharing value flow that moves to FleetM and returns back to the Developer as a real-time data flow. There are more than 120 direct interactions among all 13 stakeholders, therefore, the expected value loops are more than 1,200. The central stakeholder – Platform Developer – participates in 36% of all value flows.

In the next example (Fig. 37), it is presented a short value loop with a relatively high value creation process. It is an indirect value loop where three network's actors are involved. The calculation follows below:

- Understanding of the functioning of the service from Platform Developer → to Port of Rotterdam **0.42**
- Shared policy goals between Portdat and the PoR → Portdat **0.34**
- Authorisation to include the container status data from Portdat → Platform developer **0.71**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.42 * 0.34 * 0.71 = \mathbf{0.1013}$$

Figure 37: Example of value loop in CS3

In Fig. 38 the following flows are presented:

- Real-time container status data from Platform developer /service provider → Shipper **0.22**
- Project's inputs from Shipper → to TNO **0.61**
- Technical knowledge from TNO → to Information service provider **0.40**
- Future contract conditions from Information service provider → to Platform developer **0.40**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.22 * 0.61 * 0.40 * 0.40 = \mathbf{0.0214}$$

Figure 38: Example of value loop in CS3

In Fig. 39, the following flows are presented:

New educational input related to ICT/ ITS challenges from Developer → to Educators **0.14**

Skilled workforce from Educators → to Platform developer **0.48**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.14 * 0.48 = \mathbf{0.0672}$$

Figure 39: Example of value loop in CS3

This last example presents a direct value loop with the involvement of the central stakeholder (Platform developer /maintenance) and one more stakeholder Educators, who plays a more indirect role in the operational processes of CS3 network by providing the trained and skilled workforce for the activities of each stakeholder. And any discussions with the academic institutions of existing ITS challenges that might affect the educational materials for future students is not that immediately direct, but it happens through discussions at formal and informal meetings of the network and TNO as the leading research organisation. Therefore, the observed value creation process is somehow not very high despite the loop shortness. This relatively low-scoring loop brings an opportunity for the CS3 network to improve it via more cooperation with the educators in order to extract higher value from the relevant interactions.

All five examples of value loops were calculated to present an understanding among the stakeholders about existing indirect interactions that also create and deliver value, as well as bring new information or knowledge that is hidden behind the more obvious direct exchanges. It is often that networks concentrate on their operational activities, which are logically defined by their business processes and miss the indirect value flows and loops. All calculations were based on the value flow scores presented in Table 11 of this section.

The randomly selected and calculated value loops do not describe a full picture of the highly concentrated value interactions in CS3. This is one of the most active networks of all four cases. The relatively low-scoring value loops could be explained with the involvement of many stakeholders (four or five), which interactions and transfers are slowed down by the nature of their business and the time factor. However, once the ICT/ ITS platform begins to fully operate and optimise the processes, it will reduce the time waste and expand the interactions of all stakeholders, which will improve the value creation. In addition, the data stored on the platform will provide the entire network with the appropriate feedback from the Shipper's business clients/ customers or other end-users in order to increase the value extracted from each relevant value flow.

If these five exemplary value loops are arranged by score, the ranking looks like.

Rank	Score	FROM	TO	Value Flow Type
1.	0.10	Platform developer	Port of Rotterdam, Portdat, Platform developer	Service functionality, Policy goals, Authorisation
2.	0.06	Platform developer	Educators, Developer	New educational material inputs; Skilled workforce
3.	0.05	Platform developer	Shipper, Inland terminal operator, Developer	Future contracts and agreements, Reduced discussions on delays, container status information
4.	0.021	Platform developer	Shipper, TNO, Information service provider, Developer	Knowledge, Data, Future contracts, Project's input (design)
5.	0.019	Platform developer	Information service provider, TNO, Inland terminal, FleetM, Developer	Technical knowledge, service functionalities, authorisation of data sharing, real-time data

Table 12: CS3 ranking of value loops

Additionally, the table below presents 18 most important value flows within the Dutch network, which represent the stakeholders' interactions with the highest value creation. The scores range between [0.28 – 0.75]. All value scores range between [0.04 – 0.75]. In 89% of the significant flows, the stakeholders validated ranks coincided with the expert ranks, which gives confidence in our model. The difference in opinions only appear in regards to the platform

developer's value flows ranked 1 and 2 (coloured in pale pink in the table). Similar to CS1, the results in CS3 obtained from the stakeholders and the experts are more in tune. The central stakeholder also participates in more than 30% of the interactions, the same as the CS1's central stakeholder.

Stakeholder	Value Flow	SCORE	Stakeholders validated rank	Expert rank
1. Platform Developer	1. Technical knowledge	0.75	1	7
	2. Authorisation to include container status data in the platform	0.71	2	1
2. TNO	Project funding for a pilot	0.64	1	1
3. LIOF	Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	0.61	1	1
4. FleetM	Authorisation for data sharing with platform	0.72	1	1
5. Information service provider	1. Technical knowledge	0.60	1	1
	2. Skilled workforce	0.60	1	1
6. Portdat	1. Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer from the deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1
	2. Authorisation to share data of port-community system from the sea-shipping company	0.57	1	1
7. Shipper	Higher predictability logistics process	0.57	1	1
8. Warehouse / Logistic services	Higher predictability of container arrival at warehouse	0.53	1	1

9. Inland terminal operator	More reliable container release time at deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1
10. Dinalog	Pilot results	0.57	1	1
11. Port of Rotterdam	Shared policy goals	0.45	1	1
12. Government	1. Compliance with policy directions from TNO	0.47	1	1
	2. Compliance with policy direction from Dinalog	0.47	1	1
	3. Compliance with policy direction from Port of Rotterdam	0.47	1	1
13. Educators	Funding	0.28	1	1

Table 13: CS3 stakeholders' most important direct value flows

3.4 CS4 A knowledge-based data analysis for railway safety, Coventry

Responsible Partner: CUE

3.4.1 Introduction

CS4's network illustrates how predictive maintenance analytics can be used to predict any repairs of infrastructure assets in advance via "smart train" data collection. The case demonstrates how to cut unexpected costs through reducing unscheduled maintenance repairs and improving assets earlier. It focuses on the collection and analysis of infrastructure data for the purpose of informing decision making in order to solve practical/physical problems such as improving infrastructure monitoring mechanisms to support predictive maintenance and provide a better and safer service to the public. The pilot took place on the route London –North West and was executed by Network Rail and Virgin Trains in the UK.

As described in previous sections, CS4 network consists of ten UK stakeholders, and five of them were interviewed. These were Network Rail, CUE, RSSB, Virgin Train and Business clients. In the process of validation, it appeared that it was quite demanding for the Case study leader to put all stakeholders together around the table. For this reason, CUE had to run a number of mini-workshops in the premises of some stakeholders (Coventry and Milton Keynes), predominantly with the senior personnel.

3.4.2 Survey Results and Value Flow Scores

The original questionnaires in English are attached in the appendix 6.4 after the profiles of all stakeholders. The value flow scores were calculated for CS4 similarly to the other cases by following the methodology described in section 3. The survey was used as a first iteration of collecting broader knowledge from the local stakeholders.

3.4.3 2nd iteration – workshop's debates to validate

To validate the obtained results, NEWBITS project ran ideation workshops in Coventry and Milton Keynes between 1st – 12th March 2018 with representatives of the stakeholders, who were asked to discuss the obtained results from the surveys and also to give relative ranking to the value flow inputs. The objective of the validation process was to create general confidence in the understanding of the CS4 and the applied model. All value flows were validated by the representatives of the stakeholder groups. This was a burdensome process in CS4 railway network in the United Kingdom.

As mentioned, the major stakeholders' individuals that filled-in the surveys possessed broader understanding of the network's operations. They scored the value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the questions within the entire model. However, each interviewee did not have detailed information regarding the specific needs of the rest of the stakeholders. Thus, the workshop's debate of the results provided the representatives with a good platform to interact and explain to the rest of the stakeholders' network what their specific needs are. It

also helped the NEWBITS partners to consult with the representatives from different stakeholder groups and understand better the interactions between all actors. More specifically, the expressed opinions follow below.

For the Rail Infrastructure Owners

It was agreed that success of any data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiative in railway would heavily rely on three key elements:

1. Scientific knowledge such as the impact of emerging technologies -hardware such as storage capacity and software related developments in big data, artificial intelligence etc., enabling innovation in infrastructure monitoring. This knowledge is likely to come from academic and research institutions.
2. A skilled workforce able to adopt those innovations for the benefit of the industry, and
3. The role of policy and regulatory advice from government and institutions able to both regulate and guide those innovations so that they benefit all stakeholders, in particular the public.

With this in mind, Table 1 (Network Rail) of section III A. of document “WP4 Validation of Quantitative Results”, was not changed. The three participants strongly agreed with 1 to 3 above and agreed with all other aspects reflected in the table, on the basis that these reflected other stakeholders’ views and did not contradict their perception.

For Train Manufacturers

Agreement was achieved on the fact that train manufacturers would only be able to contribute to successful data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiative if these were driven by future plans of owners of rail infrastructure and if they (manufacturers) were aware of such plans.

Participants were also in agreement with the fact that success of such initiatives would rely on the ability to effectively analyse the data collected from the infrastructure, and that this ability often resides in academic and research organisations.

There was debate on the importance of funding for manufacturers, but overall participants agreed with the rest of the rankings.

For Academic Institutions

For academic institutions, the three key aspects determining success of these initiatives were, in this order, (1) Skills, (2) Access to Data that would enable the analysis, and (3) Funding from government and the industry.

Having changed the priorities of the above, the rest of rankings remained the same.

For Educators

It is interesting to mention that in this particular aspect all participants sought the input from the facilitator as an educator before they were able to give their views. Having had the

facilitator's views, participants agreed that scientific knowledge and funding were, in that order, the two priorities for an educator to work towards success of one of these initiatives in railway.

Government Institutions

The debate here was around whether 'compliance with policy direction from other intergovernmental agencies' was meant to take higher priority. It was agreed that it is as important as 'compliance with policy direction from EU agencies' and the ranking was adjusted accordingly. (Plans and reports of progress from Train Manufacturers took priority over those from IT Companies.)

Rail regulators

There was no contradiction between the results of the analysis and the views of participants in the needs and roles of ORR.

Safety regulators

The role of RSSB was discussed at length. Although it was acknowledged that RSSB do not have an internal team dedicated to the development of data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiatives, it is clear that RSSB supports developments in this area through different means. One of these is funding, which allows for one academic team in the University of Huddersfield to focus on this area and develop applications. Other mechanisms include RSSB's engagement with the Digital Railway section of Network Rail and their involvement in initiatives at national and international level (such as NEWBITS as members of the Advisory Board). These issues explain why the ranking in the corresponding table didn't change after the analysis.

The Public

The Public was a key stakeholder in every conversation, with better services (from the industry), improved health and safety (from regulators), and better prices (from regulators) being their top priorities. The only point for debate in this context was whether RSSB's role was expected to have a higher priority in health and safety protection than that reflected in the ranking, which was agreed by all participants. The rankings were adjusted accordingly.

IT Service Companies

For IT service companies, participants agreed that a skilled workforce from universities who were able to analyse the data collected and present the results to the railway industry, would be the key success factor for data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiatives. This would be followed by the ability of these companies to deliver their contribution to the initiatives, which were down to being financially stable. Hence, no suggestions were made for changes in the proposed rankings.

Train Operating Companies

Train operating companies were considered an essential component of any efforts to develop data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiatives due to two main reasons: their contribution to the solution and the benefits they can expect from the initiatives.

In that sense, it was agreed that the number of franchise contracts from government would be the number one determinant of the TOCs' ability to contribute to successful initiatives, followed by the guarantee that universities and academic institutions would have the skills and capabilities to analyse any data that TOCs are able to collect and contribute. This was in line with the ranking and therefore no changes were suggested.

Later in April 2018, interviews with policy-makers in Brussels took place to validate the rankings of the stakeholder "government".

3.4.4 3rd iteration – expert workshop's debates to validate

In the third iteration of the tailor-made VNA the experts were involved on the basis of an applied modified Delphi method, where they re-ranked the post-validation ranks of the value flow scores in some occasions, in others the ranks remained the same. To achieve it, the NEWBITS consortium ran a joint group discussion in Barcelona on 22nd March.

The final results are as follows. The colours are used to distinguish the same value flows from the rest of them.

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Train Manufacturers (e.g. Alstom Transport)	Future Plans Informati	from Network Rail	0.62	1	1	Importance	1
	Data Analytics Technol	from CUE	0.61	2	2		2
	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.58	3	2		2
	Funding	from Commercial Clients	0.49	4	3		3
	Funding	from Government	0.47	5	4		4
	New Launched Services	from Alstom R&D	0.45	6	5		5
	Future Plans Informati	from CUE	0.33	7	6	Less	6
	New Launched Services	from CUE	0.27	8	7	Importance	7

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Academic Institutions (e.g. Coventry University)	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Virgin Train	0.82	1	2	Importance	2
	Funding	from Government	0.82	1	3		3
	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.71	2	1		1
	Funding	from Network Rail	0.67	3	3		3
	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Alstom Transport	0.64	4	4		4
	Exchange on Regulation	from RSSB	0.59	5	5		5
	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Network Rail	0.55	6	6		6
	Cost sharing	from Network Rail about "Keep Safe" project	0.46	7	7	Less	7
	Exchange on Regulation	from ORR	0.37	8	8	Importance	8

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Educators	SCIENCE Knowledge	from CUE	0.45	1	1	Importance	1
	Funding	from Government (Public taxes)	0.35	2	2		2
	Inspired students	from Public	0.20	3	3		3
	Educational material	from CU Group	0.13	4	4	Less	4

VALUE FLOW	To Stakeholder	From Source	Cycle 1 High Pr	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank	
Railway Infrastructure Owners (e.g. Network Rail)	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.82	1	1		1	
	Policy&Regulatory Advice	from RSSB	0.70	2	2		2	
	Science knowledge	from CUE	0.68	3	3		3	
	Policy&Regulatory Advice	from ORR	0.67	4	4		4	
	Funding	from Transport Scotland	0.66	5	5		5	
	Funding	from Grants, DfT	0.66	5	5		5	
	Commercial charges	from Properties	0.43	6	6		6	
	Commercial charges	from Virgin Trains	0.37	7	7		Less	7
	Science systems	from Alstom Transport	0.25	8	8		Importance	8

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Train Operators (e.g. Virgin Trains)	Franchise contracts	from Government via DfT	0.67	1	1		1
	Data analytics	from CUE	0.51	2	2		2
	Skilled workforce	from Educators	0.44	3	3		3
	Future Plans Info Exchange	from Network Rail	0.43	4	4		4
	Science systems	from Alstom Transport	0.21	5	5		5
	Future Plans Info Exchange	from CUE	0.15	6	6		Less

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
GOVERNMENT	Compliance with policy direction	from EU agencies	0.629	1	1	Importance	1
	Informative & disseminative content	from ORR	0.603	2	2		2
	Informative & disseminative content	from RSSB	0.576	3	3		3
	Compliance with policy direction	from other inter-governmental agencies	0.566	4	1		1
	Taxes	from Public	0.464	5	4		5
	Public opinions	from Public	0.451	6	5		2
GOVERNMENT	Plans and reports of progress	from Network Rail	0.401	7	6		4
	Plans and reports of progress	from RSSB	0.394	8	7		8
	Skilled workforce	from Educators	0.37	9	8		7
	Policy Advice	from Serco	0.31	10	9		6
	Plans and reports of progress	from Virgin Trains	0.276	11	10		10
	Plans and reports of progress	from ORR	0.241	12	11		11
	Plans and reports of progress	from Alstom	0.206	13	12		12
	Plans and reports of progress	from Serco	0.206	13	13		13
	ITS Science knowledge	from CUE	0.201	14	14	Less	3
GOVERNMENT	Railway analysed data	from CUE	0.139	15	15	Importance	9

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
	1. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	0.87	1	1	Importance	1
	2. Science Knowledge & data	<i>from CUE</i>	0.84	2	2		2
	3. Future Policy Direction	<i>from ORR</i>	0.72	3	3		3
	4. Future Policy Direction	<i>from Transport Scotland</i>	0.68	4	4		4
SAFETY REGULATOR:	5. Future Policy Direction	<i>from Government (Department for Transport)</i>	0.68	4	4		4
(RSSB)	6. Financial Resources	<i>from levies from Network Rail</i>	0.66	5	5		5
	7. Public funding	<i>from Government</i>	0.60	6	6		6
	8. Railway analysed data	<i>from CUE</i>	0.60	6	6	Less	6
	9. Cost sharing	<i>with CUE about "Keep safe" project</i>	0.28	7	7	Importance	7

Rail Regulators (e.g. Office of Rail and Road)	1. Policy Direction	<i>from Government</i>	0.93	1	1	1
	2. Financial Resources	<i>from levies, license fees from Network Rail</i>	0.63	2	2	2
		<i>from Virgin Trains</i>	0.45	6	6	6
		<i>from DfT</i>	0.60	3	3	3
	3. Grant from Government	<i>from Transport Scotland</i>	0.48	4	4	4
	4. Scientific Knowledge	<i>from Educators (CU Group)</i>	0.46	5	5	5
	5. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	0.46	5	5	5
	6. Railway acquired data	<i>from Network Rail</i>	0.24	7	7	7

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Public	1. Railway improved safety derived products & services	<i>from Network Rail</i>	0.89	1	1	1
		<i>from CUE</i>	0.40	7	6	6
		<i>from Virgin Trains</i>	0.74	4	4	4
	2. Employment	<i>with Network Rail</i>	0.36	8	7	7
		Alstom Transport	0.34	9	8	8
		<i>with Virgin Trains</i>	0.32	10	9	9
	3. Health & Safety Protection	<i>from ORR</i>	0.82	3	3	3
		<i>from RSSB</i>	0.64	6	3	3
		<i>from Government</i>	0.67	5	5	5
	4. Science Knowledge	<i>from Educators</i>	0.26	11	10	10
	5. Data Analysed Content	<i>from CUE</i>	0.02	12	11	11
	6. Railway Fair Prices	<i>from ORR</i>	0.84	2	2	2
IT Service companies (e.g. Serco)	1. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	0.96	1	1	1
	2. Financial Resources	<i>from Commercial Clients</i>	0.69	2	2	2
		<i>from Government</i>	0.32	5	5	5
	3. International Partnerships	<i>from Government</i>	0.41	3	3	3
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from Government</i>	0.4	4	4	4

Table 14: CS4 stakeholders' combined value flow scores

3.4.5 Value loops, measures and conclusions

Value Loops

In this section, we present five examples of value loops from NEWBITS CS4. The scores are calculated following the method of section 3.1.5. In the first two examples, both value loops are relatively short, and thus with higher value creation. In Fig. 40, there are three stakeholders involved – Coventry University (CUE), Alstom Transport and Network Rail. In CS4, the central stakeholder is CUE or Coventry University Group, since it delivers the additional service to the Network Rail in terms of data collection, storing and analysis. CUE participates in 18% of all value flows identified via the value network analysis.

Data analytics technology from CUE → Train manufacturer **0.61**

Science systems from Train manufacturer (Alstom Trains) → NETWORK RAIL **0.25**

Funding from NETWORK RAIL → CUE (Coventry University) **0.67**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.61 * 0.25 * 0.67 = \mathbf{0.1022}$$

Figure 40: Example of value loop in CS4

In Fig. 41, the value loop involves only two stakeholders – CUE (Coventry university) and RSSB (the safety regulator). The value loop is very short and the value creation is the highest of all examples discussed in all four cases. This is a direct value loop since it involves the

central stakeholder (CUE) and another one. In this example, the scientific knowledge & data value flow from CUE to RSSB becomes an exchange on regulations flow from RSSB to CUE.

Science knowledge & data from CUE → RSSB **0.84**

Exchange on regulations from RSSB → CUE (Coventry university) **0.59**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.84 * 0.59 = \mathbf{0.4956}$$

Figure 41: Example of value loop in CS4

In the next example of CS4 (Fig. 42), a larger value loop is shown with four stakeholders involved – CUE/ Coventry university, the Public, Government and ORR, which presents a lower value score. It is more laborious to deliver value throughout the network with the involvement of the public, government institutions and regulators. Obviously, the CUE (Coventry University) will have less influence on the inputs of such a lower-scoring value loop no matter how much effort they allocate towards the outputs.

- Railway improved safety derived products & services from CUE → Public **0.40**
- Public opinions from the Public → Government **0.45**
- Policy directions from the Government → Office of Rail & Road **0.93**
- Exchange on regulations from ORR → CUE **0.37**

Value loop score = $0.40 * 0.45 * 0.93 * 0.37 = 0.0619$

Figure 42: Example of value loop in CS4

In Fig. 43 an indirect value loop is presented, where the Coventry University have less power on influencing the inputs. It is concluded that in order to increase the value creation in this loop the CUE shall periodically provide ITS scientific knowledge and information to the Department for Transport, London and Transport Scotland, Edinburgh with the intention of influencing future funding for public programmes.

ITS knowledge from Coventry university → Government **0.201**

Public funding (grant) from Government → to RSSB **0.60**

Cost sharing between RSSB and CUE → to CUE **0.28**

$$\text{Value loop score} = 0.201 * 0.60 * 0.28 = \mathbf{0.0337}$$

Figure 43: Example of value loop in CS4

In Fig. 44 a direct value loop is demonstrated with the involvement of the central stakeholder Coventry university (CUE), and the value creation is relatively high. This means that the CUE has bigger influence on the inputs coming from the Train operator, and they can affect the outputs in this process too.

Data analytics from CUE → Train operator (Virgin train) **0.51**

Value loop score = $0.51 * 0.82 = 0.4182$

Figure 44: Example of value loop in CS4

In general, there are less than 100 direct interactions among all 10 stakeholders, so the expected value loops are less than 1,000 in CS4: Railway Safety.

If the exemplary value loops are ranked by score, it seems like the interactions between CUE and the regulators are highly valuable since the regulatory authorities in the UK enforce the standards for safety and security of the public on the rail network. However, all five examples of value loops were presented in the report to give some hints to the stakeholders about indirect interactions that also create and deliver value, often hidden behind the direct operational interactions.

Rank	Score	FROM	TO	Value Flow Type
1.	0.49	CUE	RSSB	Knowledge, data Exchange on regulations
2.	0.41	CUE	Train operator (Virgin Train)	Data analytics, Real-time railway data
3.	0.10	CUE	Train manufacturer, Network Rail, CUE	Technology, science systems, funding
4.	0.06	CUE	Public, Government, ORR, CUE	Railway improved safety services; Public opinions, policy directions, exchange on regulations
5.	0.03	CUE	Government, RSSB, CUE	Knowledge, Public funding (grant), Cost sharing

Table 15: CS4 ranking of value loops

Additionally, the table below presents 13 value flows of the highest significance. The combined scores range between [0.45 – 0.96]. All value flow scores in the network range between [0.02 – 0.96]. The most important interactions account for 14% of all direct exchanges among network’s actors. In CS4, again we have a high level of agreement between stakeholders and experts. In 75% of the significant flows, the stakeholders’ validated ranks coincided with the expert ranks. Differences appear in the case of Coventry University (CUE) when it comes to the ranking of two value flows – acquired data and skilled workforce. Since the service provided by the university to the Network Rail is a written algorithm for analysing big data and visualisation, the experts felt that the knowledgeable and skilful workforce delivers higher value to the network than the data per se. In the case of Government, the experts felt that the compliance with policy direction of inter-governmental agencies should be ranked 1, while the stakeholders gave it a rank 4 (coloured in pale pink in the table 16).

CUE delivers an additional service based on big data analytics to the Network Rail, which main objective is to manage the railway infrastructure in the United Kingdom. As a result, Network Rail is one of the major stakeholders in CS4’ s list of actors, but not the central one in terms of data analytics.

<i>Stakeholder</i>	<i>Value Flow</i>	<i>SCORE</i>	<i>Stakeholders validated rank</i>	<i>Expert rank</i>

1. Coventry University (CUE)	1. Railway acquired data	0.82	1	2
	2. Funding	0.82	1	3
	3. Skilled workforce	0.71	2	1
2. Network Rail	Skilled workforce	0.82	1	1
3. ORR	Policy direction	0.93	1	1
4. Public	Railway improved safety derived products & services	0.89	1	1
5. RSSB	Skilled workforce	0.87	1	1
6. IT service companies (Serco)	Skilled workforce	0.96	1	1
7. Train operator (Virgin Trains)	Franchise contracts	0.67	1	1
8. Train manufacturer (Alstom Transport)	Future plans information	0.62	1	1
9. Government	1. Compliance with policy direction from EU	0.63	1	1
	2. Compliance with policy direction from intergovernmental agencies	0.57	4	1
10. Educators	Science knowledge	0.45	1	1

Table 16: CS4 stakeholders' most important direct value flows

To summarise the quantitative analysis performed on all four case studies in D4.3, we obtained knowledge about the local networks from the stakeholders via surveys, ran ideation workshops to validate the results of these surveys and had a joint discussion with experts. Based on these three iterations of the value network analysis, we managed to clarify a list of the most important value flows in each case study and demonstrate a calculation of value loops that give us a better idea of the value creation and delivery process within each network.

Moreover, only in CS1 we ran an experiment with assigning hypothetical high, medium or low preference to “science-knowledge” in order to explore any dynamic changes taking place within the Barcelona ecosystem. This provided an opportunity for the stakeholders to think about a sequence of three cycles when their roles or functions might be progressing and

changing. For this reason, we planned the three iterations of the quantitative VNA to be having taken place within a period of four months (December 2017 – March 2018), step-by-step, to allow for any adequate understanding and preparation from the network’s actors. This also allowed the NEWBITS consortium to observe the network in terms of any natural market forces that might have triggered further dynamic evolution. However, there was no radical change and as indicated by the stakeholders the identified CS1 value flows were ranked similarly in all three life cycles of the ecosystems, with a few exceptions.

In addition, the drawn value flow maps, having used a specialised software product OmniGraffle, present the complexity of each network since there are many direct interactions among the stakeholders, but also a value chain of transactions, which are not immediately apparent to the actors. The maps also describe the networks in a more distinct way with various types of value flows that illustrate how the value is created. The quantitative measures simplify the demonstrated complexity by allowing us to analyse the value scores, from which we can distil more practical conclusions. However, in order to calculate the total value created in each case, all value loops need to be identified and value scores added, which is beyond the task of this report. The higher-scoring indirect value loops show how the central stakeholders (Table 17) should prioritise their outputs in order to align with these loops:

Case study	Network’s central stakeholder
CS1	UAB Group / Management
CS2	VERONA Municipality
CS3	Platform developer /maintenance (service provider)
CS4	CUE / Coventry university Group

Table 17: NEWBITS cases’ central stakeholders

The low-scoring indirect value loops might be explained not only with the larger number of actors involved in any loop, but also with the participation of stakeholders that are more difficult to communicate with as CS4 proved to be the laborious case of even putting all stakeholders together.

The main purpose of the Value Network Analysis was to equip the four networks’ stakeholders with the right approach to discuss and clarify their needs and roles as they had not performed it before. The quantitative analysis also gave them a more visual picture of the network and its relations. The combined scores provided them with evidence in terms of the most significant value flows and the less important ones. This approach focused the stakeholders to think more *objectively* rather than *subjectively* about the shared value and shared risks of the network.

3.5 All four cases’ business modelling

3.5.1 Introduction

This section 3.5 aims to describe a more simplified stakeholder model for each of the NEWBITS case studies in order to elaborate on the business modelling. During the workshops' discussions, each network described their envisioned business model and this information was supplied in D4.2. However, in D4.3 we will base the business models on the identified direct value flows and some value loops. Any information extracted from D4.2 functions as complementary components to clarify the more conceptual analysis in D4.3.

	CS1	CS2	CS3	CS4
Size of network (number of stakeholders)	10	9	13	10
Direct value flows	More than 100	Less than 100	More than 120	Less than 100
Indirect value loops	More than 1,000	Less than 1,000	More than 1,200	Less than 1,000
Primary stakeholders:	Aslogic, UAB Management, UAB LOGA, UAB CORE, UAB Mobility unit, FrontierCities, Members of community, Websays	VERONA municipality, Swarco Mizar, AUDI, Telecomitalia, ATV, Citizens, Taxi operators	Platform developer, TNO, Information service provider, Shipper, Warehouse operator, Inland terminal, Port of Rotterdam, Portdat, FleetM, LIOF, Dinalog	CUE, Network Rail, ORR, RSSB, Public, IT service companies (Serco), Train manufacturer (Alstom), Train operator (Virgin train)
Secondary stakeholders:	Government, Educators	Government, Educators	Government, Educators	Government, Educators

Table 18: Summary of NEWBITS cases' networks

3.5.2 Unique value propositions

The crafting of each case's value proposition was done by the local debates, which process was described in D4.2¹³, and here only a summary will be presented (an extract of D4.2):

Case study	Value proposition
CS1	<p>Key benefits of using ITS to assist development of carpooling at university are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reduction in travel time and time taken to find parking spaces 2) Increase flexibility because the App will allow users to choose among their preferred options 3) ITS allows drivers, cars to be rated for building trust and confidence 4) Reduction in costs for those sharing cars and allows to obtain a source of income, if it is the case, for those who provide the vehicle 5) Improvement of students network contacts 6) Building of friendship 7) Reduction in mental health problems through sharing experiences 8) Allowing the university to develop <u>supporting skills in psychology and sociology</u>. These are skills with current shortages in the transportation sector
CS2	<p>TLA service allows drivers to avoid unnecessary stops and waiting times at urban signalised intersections by undertaking corrective driving actions aimed at regulating current cruise speed; such corrective actions are informed by the speed advice and the information on remaining time to catch up green light at next signalised intersection, which are both delivered to the end-user (either through a smartphone application or directly projected on the car dashboard).</p> <p>The value proposition lies in opportunity to travel along congested urban corridors at a minimum cost, with a reduced travel time and improved comfort level, while allowing drivers to generate a much lower environmental impact, thus contributing to the realization of a greener, more efficient and sustainable mobility.</p>
CS3	<p><u>Warehouse L</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. More satisfied customer = more business 2. Unique Selling Point (USP) = more business 3. Increased value added and higher operational efficiency = more business

¹³ NEWBITS D4.2 “NEWBITS Workshops”, April 2018

	<p><u>TrackT (Information service provider)</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. User knows exactly where the container is in the supply chain and what the estimated time of arrival is 2. Shipper, forwarder, operator, carrier and terminal have the same real-time, fact-based view of the situation 3. Deep / short sea operation will be connected to the inland operation and visible in one view <p><u>ICT dev</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transport transparency (= delays) to the underlying clients 2. Better planning 3. Cost reduction due to reduction in slack (e.g. less container rental)
CS4	<p>A set of benefits that a data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring or predictive maintenance initiative can deliver to satisfy the needs of the railway industry and its customer.</p> <p>The key benefits of implementing a successful data- and knowledge-based infrastructure monitoring initiative include:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Move away from traditional maintenance towards intelligent predictive maintenance, thus avoiding the ‘stop and repair’ traditional approach to maintenance. 2) Optimise the allocation of human resources to the implementation of the maintenance strategy only when required 3) Optimise the timely replacement of potentially faulty equipment before the network and its customers are affected. 4) Reduce/avoid unscheduled maintenance and therefore minimise the costs associated to it. 5) Decrease disruptions to train services and unnecessary delays 6) Develop new products with the resources that are freed from the unplanned maintenance 7) Increase the safety of the railway network 8) Offer better quality of service to their customers

Table 19: Summary of value propositions extracted from D4.2

3.5.3 Description of networked business models

In NEWBITS, and particularly in WP4 T4.2, the business model is understood as a network of actors. The previous sections of this deliverable attempted to depict in more details how value

is created by a number of stakeholders over a period of time. And at a conceptual level, the model used is based on the value network approach, which is applied in D4.3. Therefore, at a conceptual level, each case's business model is presented as a stakeholder network model with the important value flows that are channeling value throughout the network¹⁴.

However, in D4.2 at a more operational level, the business model's components of each case study has been discussed and explained via the use of a lean business model canvas, which led to crafting value propositions and business model visions. This was done in participation of the major stakeholders with a moderator. These visions are presented in the table below as extracts of D4.2. They are complementary to the more conceptual value network model.

Case Study	Business model vision
CS1	CS1, VaoPoint, exemplifies how the <i>sharing economy</i> has gained momentum in recent days and increased the collaborative consumption of some segments in our modern societies. At this stage, the model planned and applied targets those customers that are more adaptive to the new ways of collaborative consumption rather than solely rely on individual means and pure ownership of goods (vehicles). This task appears to be complex as such segments in the societies are not so clearly defined and requires the use of both new business techniques and modern means of social communication. It requires a large amount of social science knowledge, including marketing, psychology and behavioral economics, to understand the collaborative mindset of human-beings and influence their decisions. There are, of course, benefits and challenges ahead of such a novel business model facilitated by the ITS platform.
CS2	CS2 represents a C-ITS city platform to manage drivers' behaviour. Its applied model is based on recent developments of <i>Internet of Things</i> and demonstrates how the public authorities in Italy (the municipality of Verona) use these opportunities to monitor traffic on the roads, drivers' behaviour and subsequently reduce road accidents, CO2 emissions and congestion. The model improves the efficiency of city's services and offers the opportunity to develop a range of ancillary new services (for example, a text informing the driver to stop at the petrol station for filling-up the gas tank) by making use of the available data.
CS3	CS3 presents how <i>data-sharing</i> and smart data-use can offer benefits to a network of interdependent partners, particularly in container logistics. The service is targeted at a group of stakeholders connected through logistic activities of container

¹⁴ NEWBITS D4.1: Formalization of NEWBITS modelling method and systemic business dynamics, Submitted on 22/12/2017 as part of WP4, No: 723974

	transportation and data sharing. The different stakeholders involved can benefit from the platform-service in many ways via storing, organizing and optimizing the data-use. The challenge is to establish the added value of such service and create a business case for the service provider. There are benefits and challenges facing such a complex business structure and modelling.
CS4	CS4: A networked approach for railway safety – The business model applied is based on <u>Big Data Predictive Analytics and Visualisation</u> . As a result of increased interconnectedness of devices and objects, the networked sensors in the Internet of Things serve to monitor the railway infrastructure assets via “smart trains”. These devices are a key source of data that are feeding big data analytics and predictive maintenance of the infrastructure. The business model constructed relies solely on reduction of unexpected and unplanned repairs of tangible assets.

Table 20: Summary of business model visions extracted from D4.2

The customer groups of each case have been described in the analysis of D3.1, where a very detailed market research has been executed. In a more traditional marketing way, D3.1 described the customer groups (i.e. for CS1, CS2) by age, gender, demographic characteristics, income, employment status, etc. as well as the business customers (CS3, CS4) by the market characteristics. However, what has been noticed in various analytical methods applied in different deliverables of NEWBITS is that all four cases are based on technological change in the fields of Internet of Things and Big Data analytics and as such they establish new markets with new market elements and a new level of complexity. As shown in the table below, in CS1, the customers prefer to have a good identification of the other users, while in CS2 the younger drivers prefer to have more technical features in the information delivered. These novel types of preference do shape customer groups but in a more uncommon and blurred way, which makes the targeting of such customers increasingly laborious. It requires the use of algorithms that can depict information through the use of social media or various mobile apps.

In CS3 and CS4, the business preferences are more traditional as collected by the conjoint analysis, however, the level of complexity in both cases requires a lot of differentiation and price discrimination. In CS3, regional or local small and medium sized enterprises are more likely to use the service and offering them particular packages at differing prices will be a good option for the service provider while the larger companies more often can afford their own internal data platforms. In CS4, Network Rail as a natural monopoly already applies price discrimination such as off-peak and on-peak hour tickets, weekend railway tickets, etc., so the model is well-explored in the United Kingdom. When it comes to the big data analytics service offered by Coventry university in CS4 to Network Rail, apparently there is more competition as European railway providers have recently penetrated various segments of the British market.

Case Study	User-preferences (from the conjoint analysis)
CS1	<u>PREFERENCES:</u> a dedicated parking space; a proper identification of the service's users; and communication tools for users
CS2	<u>PREFERENCES:</u> end-users expect the received information to be directly usable; younger users value more the technical features of the system
CS3	<u>PREFERENCES:</u> business users' decisions are affected by the tracking capabilities of the service and the price per container
CS4	<u>PREFERENCES:</u> end-users value the increased safety of the railway's journeys and the financial improvements in terms of value for money and journey reliability

Table 21: Results from the conjoint analysis extracted from D3.3¹⁵

When describing the revenue model and cost structure of these novel business models, it becomes apparent that in CS1 and CS2, there are no expectations for a solid revenue stream, on the contrary in CS1 the users expect to be rewarded for choosing the carpooling service on the way to the university's campus; and in CS2 the infrastructure/service of C-ITS platform has been maintained by the municipality as end-users do not pay any additional fees.

In CS3 and CS4 as these are B2B services, there is expectation for more substantial revenue streams and the cost structure is based on cost-sharing among all stakeholders.

In continuation of this work, T5.1 will focus more on the opportunities of monetising these models via performing a cost-benefit analysis.

3.5.4 Actors, major interactions and channelling of value

Summarising the analysis in section 3.4, one can see the major value flows that bring the highest value to each of the described network. It is noticeable that the major exchanges of high-level value in all cases depend on:

- Scientific /technical knowledge,
- Acquired data,
- Policy direction,
- Skilled workforce,
- Public funding or
- Future commercial contracts.

Most of these value exchanges have been validated by the stakeholders. With this summary the aim is to simplify the initial value maps and place more focus on the major direct

¹⁵ NEWBITS D3.3 "Conjoint analysis on case studies", submitted 30/Apr as part of WP3, No: 723974

interactions. Furthermore, with the short analysis of the value loops in section 3.4, what is presented is the indirect role of some of the stakeholders such as the public, educators or the national government which deliver value throughout the network, even if it is not directly apparent since these three actors are not involved into the operational processes of the specific activities. However, their role is significant as they facilitate many of the supportive activities (legislative, regulatory, educational, etc.) that add and transfer value to the major activities (transport-related, ITS innovation-related). In addition, the public is involved into the feedback mechanism that each network ideally needs to receive back from their customers.

Case study	Type of value flows ranked 1 (or 2) by the primary stakeholders
CS1	<p>Mobility data; Access to EU-research programmes; Technology transfers; Policy collaboration engaging members of community;</p> <p>EU funding; Informative & entertaining content; Collaborative platform and Rewards for users</p>
CS2	<p>Innovative ITS services; Mobility data; Skilled workforce;</p> <p>Access to traffic data; Sustainable mobility services from the municipality</p> <p>Transit signal priority; General knowledge</p>
CS3	<p>Technical knowledge; Authorisation to include container status;</p> <p>Funding; Demonstrated pilot results; Skilled workforce;</p> <p>Authorisation to share-data of port community system from the deep-sea terminal; Authorisation to share-data of port community system from the sea shipping company;</p> <p>Higher predictability logistics process; Pilot results; Shared policy goals;</p> <p>More reliable container release time at deep-sea terminal</p>
CS4	<p>Railway acquired data;</p> <p>Funding; Skilled workforce; Policy direction; Railway improved safety derived products & services;</p> <p>Franchise contracts and Future plans</p>

Table 22: Type of value flows ranked 1 or 2

Naturally, there are specific technicalities in each case study that have been discussed in previous sections as well as in D4.2¹⁶, but notably all four networks are knowledge-intensive depending very much on highly skilled labour. This means that the central stakeholders should possibly be in a situation to attract younger people to pursue careers not only in engineering and technology, but also in social sciences that can influence the opinions of the public. Also, they should take more advantage of internally training their workforce for the future.

Channelling of high-level value among the primary and secondary stakeholders of all four networks involves transfers of data, knowledge, skilled workforce, contracts, policy collaboration and public-private funding.

3.5.5 Conclusions

This section describes the major conclusions that relate to each of our business models described as networks via the stakeholder network model or also called VNA-model (see Fig. 45). Through this report, it was illustrated how stakeholders in a network can cooperate and collaborate effectively by following a step-by-step procedure such as identifying their needs, understanding the needs and inputs of other stakeholders, undertaking a particular role within the group and executing specific functions that add value to the network as a whole.

Figure 45: Novel business model design (VNA-model)

¹⁶ D4.2 “WP4 NEWBITS workshops” submitted on 30/04/2018 as part of WP4, No: 723974

In this scheme, it is essential that the distinct network has regular meetings or discussions, and they appoint a formal or informal leader, who is usually one of the major actors and may have even orchestrated the establishment of the network. The leader does have very good broader knowledge about the functioning of the network as well as the interactions among all actors. The leader or the central stakeholder lays out the foundation (the rules) for the governance of the network. As seen in Fig.45 above, the description of the five-step-procedure can be smoothly visualised in a diagram.

The value loop scores calculated in section 3.4 demonstrate how the central stakeholder of each network can have more influence over some outputs and create greater value than they can have over other outputs.

Case study	Central stakeholder's influence over
CS1	UAB Group have the greater potential for creating value via its power to affect the inputs from its research units (UAB LOGA, UAB Smart Cities CORE, UAB Mobility unit)
CS2	Verona Municipality can prioritise its outputs to Swarco Mizar, who is the stakeholder providing the ITS services
CS3	The Platform developer can prioritise its outputs (real-time information about the container status) to the Inland terminal operator and the Warehousing logistics operator
CS4	CU Group have the greater potential for creating value via prioritising the outputs from the data analytics to the Train operator (Virgin train) and Train manufacturer (Alstom Transport), but no priority over the data analytic content that goes to the public

Case study	Central stakeholder's collaboration with
CS1	UAB Group can achieve significant collaboration with the Members of university community (end-users) by increasing the outputs going to the end-users (science knowledge and any other informative content). Policy collaboration via engaging the end-users in all processes of CS1 should lead to a better ability to increase the inputs coming from the end-users in order to improve the value creation.
CS2	VERONA municipality can achieve better collaboration with the citizens of Verona by increasing the outputs going to them (online mobile apps based on valuable services). Although not apparent, the public has an important role in delivering value through the expression of public opinions and voting in local elections of Italy.
CS3	The Platform developer / operator in CS3 does not have a direct relation with the business clients and customers of the Warehouse operator. The operator deals directly with the Shipper. In the future, the platform developer /service operator shall intensify its direct

	communication with the Shipper in order to consider the value-added of the Shipper's business clients/ customers or establish a suitable feedback mechanism to understand the requirements of the service.
CS4	CU Group can achieve greater collaboration with the public by increasing the outputs going to them (railway improved safety derived products & services). This will lead to more favourable public opinions, choosing the railway as a better and safer option for transportation and generating political support for ITS applications in the United Kingdom.

Case study	Central stakeholder shall:
CS1	UAB Group shall develop ITS science-related educational material for Educators (colleges, schools, departments) in order to inspire more students pursuing careers in engineering, technology but also in behavioural sciences and business studies. This can help to create a critical mass for the foundation of the necessary political support for ITS applications in Spain.
CS2	VERONA Municipality does not have a direct relation with the Educators in Italy. However, the municipality participates in EU-funded Research & Innovation projects and shall develop ITS-related material that can be used by colleges, schools and universities to inspire younger people in studying ITS-related subjects.
CS3	The Platform developer/operator shall cooperate with TNO with the intention of delivering more inputs to the Educators such as providing them with business case studies, ITS existing challenges, educational material that can lead to the provision of cutting-edge solutions to current ITS issues (see fig. 39 and the value flows of educators).
CS4	CU Group shall develop ITS science-related educational material for Educators (colleges, schools) in order to inspire more students in the UK to pursue careers in engineering, technology but also in behavioural sciences and business studies.

The conclusions listed above point out to two major outcomes:

- 1) Each network should provide innovative products & services based on ITS applications such as platforms for commercial use, but also for educational and public use;
- 2) To improve the political support for the ITS / C-ITS markets, each network needs to produce the necessary informative scientific content supplied to national governments or relevant governmental departments with the intention of improving the communication with policy-makers.

4 Recommendations and future challenges

This final section of the report presents a set of recommendations that was formulated based on the results and insights of the tailor-made VNA, in particular, the stakeholder analysis and model explained in previous sections. There are four types of recommendations presented here related to:

- Knowledge-intensity of networks based on scientific/ technical knowledge and acquired mobility data;
- Skilled workforce or workforce trained at universities, academies or colleges;
- ITS industry-government cooperation, incl. local authorities or other public bodies;
- Collaboration with the end-users;

If we start with the knowledge-intensity of all networks, and then continue with the skilled workforce as these are the categories of exchange flows that deliver high-value and have been ranked highly by stakeholders in all NEWBITS cases (Table 7, 10, 13, 16):

1) ITS innovations are knowledge-dependent, which requires a constant value flow of newly invented knowledge and technology transfers. Central stakeholders in all four networks of NEWBITS should formulate and proceed with innovative approaches to attract younger people to choose careers in engineering and social sciences. Moreover, stakeholders should cooperate with scientists and educators (incl. schools, colleges) to develop the necessary interest towards their activities, provide inputs to educational material under the form of case studies or existing ITS/ C-ITS challenges and deliver internship opportunities for students to apply the VNA. The students then can derive useful experience from learning how a networked business model operates, what the major interactions are, what it means to create shared value and assess shared risks among all actors, but also understand the importance to complement their competences with the knowledge of other partners through cooperative mechanisms.

2) The ITS innovative networks depend on skilled workforce and stakeholders should train their labour for the future, deriving data and technology from the knowledge transfers between all actors. Also, networks should use marketing, branding, social media or other means to inform recipients of knowledge within their organisations or users of their ITS products and services outside the network. They should specify the particular stakeholder within the network that the longer knowledge value chains originated with an output from. CS4 demonstrates well how stakeholders consider the shortage of trained workforce a major issue in the railway network, and thus, this value flow has been ranked highly. The public and any other beneficiaries need to be better informed about the outputs produced by the stakeholders in order to gain public support and relevant funding for their knowledge accumulated and innovative activities. As already mentioned, this also leads to a better political support for ITS-related initiatives.

3) It is well understood that the industry-government cooperation is vital for the successful execution of all innovative activities of the described networks in NEWBITS.

In particular, CS2 and CS3 demonstrate how the partnership between the local authority of Verona and the commercial companies, or between a research organisation TNO and commercial logistic operators in a government-funded project can produce valuable services and commercial agreements for public data access and private data sharing among stakeholders. Distribution of data is increasingly important in these cases. CS1 and CS4 demonstrate how the public bodies such as universities can essentially lead public-private partnerships to establish successful ITS / C-ITS networks. In the latter partnership, the industry-government cooperation has been indirectly materialised via the leadership of an educational body. However, both classes of industry-government cooperation provide hugely innovative solutions to current issues in the ITS industry of Europe and valuable lessons learnt.

4) The public or the end-users (customers or business clients) need to be engaged in the development of the ITS applications from the initial stages of any designing of apps.

Stakeholders should cooperate fully with the end-users in order to regularly receive the necessary feedback. A properly developed feedback mechanism appears to be of utmost importance in NEWBITS CS1 (Barcelona), but similarly for the rest of the cases, to minimise the acceptability risk and foster early adopters.

Summarising and deriving from the recommendations, the future challenges are specific to any of the networks, since they operate within the business and legal framework of various EU member states, however the common future challenge ahead of them is the type of funding that can be guaranteed for their operational processes. While the stakeholders do cost-sharing on projects, many of them also rely on EU or national public funding. One critical finding of the analysis is that the digital ITS applications are not a huge generator of revenue streams, in CS1 and CS2 is particularly difficult to monetise the business model. By the same token, in CS1 the customers expect to be rewarded for the use of carpooling services in the metropolitan area of Barcelona. In CS2, private drivers pay only the communication fees for the delivered messages through their monthly charges by the telecom operator in Italy. While theoretically there is a justification for developing such cutting-edge ITS apps that lead to less congestion on the European roads, less accidents and pollution, plus maintain the European leadership role in innovation, however, in monetary quantitative terms such justification is less plausible.

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6 Appendixes

6.1 Supporting Material of CS1

6.1.1 CS1 Stakeholders' profiles

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Funding (Government) 2. Cost sharing (UAB Management) 3. Policy Collaboration (Municipality and other Public Administration (excl. universities)) 4. Mobility Planning (Transport Operators, UAB Management, other Public Administration) 5. Future Plans Information Exchange (UAB Management, other Public Administration, Operators) 6. Monetary rents (Commercial Operators) 7. Skilled workforce (Educators) 	<p style="text-align: center;">UAB Mobility Unit</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: Transport Authority</p> <p>Role: Provide technical support to the UAB management (governing) body on the design of UAB mobility policy as well as the appropriate planning and management tools to maximise accessibility to the campus in the most sustainable, efficient and integrative way possible.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Act at the same level as a public transport authority *Plan and manage the territorial mobility within the university campus *Promote sustainable mobility values and solutions for the university campus <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Promote car pooling linked to incentives *Ensure high occupancy vehicles (strategic line) *Subsidise collective public transport <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to funding 2. Mobility Unit coordination/ management 3. Resources to implement its objectives (budgetary, human, technical) 4. Launch new mobility services within the campus 5. Access to facilities / mechanisms to fund its parking services <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Annually costs reach €6 million *Average annual maintenance costs for a parking space - €70 *Expenses are covered by the university management for road improvement, transport, security and lighting <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *No existing revenue model *No generation of income *Public institutions' funding sources *And parking rent for commercial buses <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Designed Mobility Plans 2. Informative and disseminative content of VAOPoint practices to European universities through the EU funded LIFE project and at CRUE level 3. Know-how on mobility systems 4. Expert output on mobility needs, technical issues and users' perceptions 5. General information (technical, social, etc.)
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<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Funding (Government, Students, Commercial) 2. Cost sharing (UAB Mobility Unit) 3. Policy Collaboration (UAB Management, City Halls and other Public Administration (excl. universities)) 4. Mobility Planning and know-how (UAB Mobility Unit) 5. Future Plans Information Exchange (UAB Mobility Unit, Public Administration (excl. universities), Operators) 6. Skilled workforce (Educators) 	<p style="text-align: center;">UAB Management Group: CITY - GOVERNMENT</p> <p>Role: Responsible for organisation and management of infrastructure readiness for all services, and facilitating the acquisition of licences for deployment.</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Govern the university services *Plan and develop educational programmes *Make decisions regarding territorial management of the infrastructure, facilities, and services within the campus *Cooperate with other institutions & agencies to make most effective use of resources by avoiding any duplication of effort *Provide fully functional innovative solutions to ensure sustainable mobility on campus *Reduce the number of vehicles on campus *Seek and encourage the commercial use of university's services (incl. parking space) <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Access to funding 2. University Coordination/ management 3. Resources to implement its objectives (budgetary, human, technical) 4. Launch services 5. Access to facilities / mechanisms to fund the efficient running and maintenance of platform <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Annual 2015/16 expenditure €312 million of which: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 66.61% accounts for personnel costs; 15.3% for purchase of current assets and services; 10.48% for investments; 5.16% for current transfers; 2.43% for a variation of assets, financial liabilities and capital transfers <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *UAB's income spreads over teaching (tuition fees), research (public funding grants), and transfer activities (patents, transfer of research results to industry) *Annual 2015/16 report outlines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 72% increase in resources obtained within the framework of EU Horizon 2020 for research with almost €14.5 million, and over €22 million obtained in the National Plan *Turnover of above €25 million for offered services and signed 640 agreements with commercial companies and public institutions <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Funding acquisition to support continuous service existence 2. Educational programmes 3. Public and private partnerships
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<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Acquired mobility data (Other stakeholders and partners) 2. Cost sharing (UAB Management) 3. ITS Science funding (UAB) 4. Future Plans Information Exchange (UAB Mobility Unit, UAB Management) 5. Skilled workforce (Educators) 6. Access to existing research programmes 7. Informative content (Social networks, Media) 	<p style="text-align: center;">UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: Academia</p> <p>Role: Responsible for designing and developing decision support algorithms for both tactical and operational planning problems on the platform according to the policies defined by the network</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Logistics modelling, simulation and optimisation *Transfer Unit's invented technologies to provide necessary support to strategic and operational decision-making in industrial & transport activities *Commercialisation of technological solutions <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Research Funding 2. Resources (human, technical) 3. Mobility acquired data 4. Other complementary data 5. Knowledge of UAB Mobility Unit objectives and future plans 6. Knowledge of UAB Management objectives and policies 7. Access to existing and future logistics programmes 8. General information (scientific, technical, social, etc.) <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">The same as for the UAB Management</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *LOGA does not generate revenue *The budget is centrally managed by the university governing body <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Science-related knowledge 2. State-of-the-art decision support 3. Analysed mobility data 4. Algorithms
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UAB Smart Cities Core
Group: ACADEMIA (Research Network on Smart & Sustainable Cities)

Role: Responsible for facilitating the deployment of university's services and acting as an intermediary between the IT Services Unit and UAB Management

Objectives:

*Produce useful research and knowledge through collaboration of existing departments, research centres and campus infrastructures

*Create new multidisciplinary research activities

*Increase the visibility of technological transfer in the fields of energy management and urban mobility

*Provide advice to other organisations

*Support citizen participation policies in the smart city context

Specific Needs:

1. Collaboration with other stakeholders
2. Smart City acquired data
3. Other requisite complementary data
4. Innovative solutions for smart and sustainable cities
5. Skilled and motivated workforce

Cost Structure:

*Annual 2015/16 expenditure €312 million of which:

66.61% accounts for personnel costs;

15.3% for purchase of current assets and services;

10.48% for investments;

5.16% for current transfers;

2.43% for a variation of assets, financial liabilities and capital transfers

Revenue Model:

*Annual 2015/16 report outlines:

72% increase in resources obtained within the framework of EU Horizon 2020 for research with almost €14.5

million, and over €22 million obtained in the National Plan

*Turnover of above €25 million for offered services and signed 640 agreements with commercial companies and public institutions

Outputs:

1. Stakeholder acquisition of licences
2. Support of smart cities environment
3. Negotiation between internal stakeholders

Inputs:

1. Smart City acquired data (Other stakeholders and partners)
2. Cost sharing (UAB Management)
3. Policy Collaboration (UAB Management, IT Services Unit, Network Stakeholders)
4. Future Plans Information Exchange (UAB Management, IT Services Unit, Network stakeholders)
5. Skilled workforce (Educators)
6. Technology transfers (Network stakeholders)

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products (UAB Mobility Unit, FrontierCities, Aslogic) 2. Employment (UAB Management, UAB Mobility Unit, UAB Smart Cities Core, UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit, etc.) 3. Informative & entertaining content (Social Media, Websays) 4. Science knowledge (UAB, Educators) 5. Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options (FrontierCities) 	<p style="text-align: center;">Members of the University community (students and employees)</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: End-users</p> <p>Role: The general Spain-based end-users as a whole. In the context of the university, this group consists of current and potential students, administrative and academic personnel</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Enhance sustainable mobility values *Encourage general mobility efficiency and flexibility *Reduce commuting costs - monetary fees vs leisure time *Reduce greenhouse gas emissions *Promote social welfare <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. General knowledge and information about mobility options 2. Good governance of offered services 3. Continuous management of websites information 4. Flexible mobility services 5. Teaching and lecturing 6. Jobs <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure: Not applicable</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model: Not applicable</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Enhanced university market for sustainable mobility services
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<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compliance with policy direction (EU and other government agencies) 2. Plans and reports of progress (UAB Mobility Unit, UAB Management) 3. Science knowledge (UAB) 4. Public opinions (Community) 5. Informative & disseminative content (Social media, Websays, FrontierCities) 6. Taxes (Community) 	<p style="text-align: center;">GOVERNMENT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: City / Government</p> <p>Role: This includes municipalities (local authority), city authorities, public administration, government agencies and central departments. It is responsible for the provision of policy-making and policy direction</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Provide oversight of public programmes/ agencies *Appropriate funds to public programmes/ agencies *Evaluation of activities with respect to sustainable transportation and mobility *Promote actions that will reduce pollution, accidents and congestion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustain political support (central or local) *Introduce fair and good legislation <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources to implement objectives (budgetary) 2. Progress reports on activities 3. Data from government-funded programmes 4. Expert scientific, technical and policy advice 5. Knowledge of policy-direction of other public bodies, and inter-governmental agencies 6. General information (scientific, technical, social, etc.) 7. Political support (through voting) <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure: Central budgeting or local budgeting</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model: Public taxation</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Policy-making documentation and public funding
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6.1.2 CS1 Surveys' questions

Quantitative Analysis – December 2017, NEWBITS

WP4 Value Flow Scoring Questions

INSTRUCTIONS:

The intent of this analysis is to identify the highest value-producing interactions between the most important stakeholders in each of our four case studies, and subsequently map value flows of the major relationships. We need to develop insight into the **specific needs** of stakeholders and how **they are fulfilled**. In WP3, partners identified a number of stakeholders that interact with each other in all four case studies. In WP4, we continue deepening the understanding of the nature of such specific needs of each major stakeholder, and their preferred source of fulfilment.

We plan to run two surveys, one after another, each contains a series of questions regarding the specific needs of each stakeholder, divided into sections by stakeholder. When answering these

questions, please think of yourself as a representative from that particular stakeholder group, for instance academia, industry association, mobility operator or policy-maker.

Satisfaction / Regret

Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfillment of this need?

Responses: A response of A, B, C, D or E will be chosen. Answer E corresponds to “must-have” need.

- A. I would be satisfied by its presence, but do not regret its absence
- B. I would be satisfied by its presence, but would somewhat regret its absence
- C. I would be satisfied by its presence and do regret its absence
- D. Its presence is needed
- E. Its presence is absolutely essential

Importance of Source

Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be?

Responses: A response of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 can be chosen. The response 5 corresponds to “extremely important”.

- 1. Not important
- 2. Somewhat important
- 3. Important
- 4. Very important
- 5. Extremely important

Survey I – Case Study 1 (Barcelona, Spain)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
ASLOGIC	1. Acquired Mobility Data	
	2. Commercial Funding	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	5. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
EDUCATORS	1. Educational Material	
	2. Inspired Students	
	3. Informative Content	
	4. Science Knowledge	
	5. Funding	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
FrontierCities (Funder)	1. Acquired Mobility Data	
	2. Cost sharing	
	3. EU funding	
	4. Plans and Reports of progress	
	5. Opinion & support	
	6. Science opinions	
	7. Informative content	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
GOVERNMENT	1. Compliance with policy direction	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	
	4. Public opinions	
	5. Informative & disseminative content	
	6. Taxes	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Members of the University Community (end-users)	1. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products	
	2. Employment	
	3. Informative & entertaining content	
	4. Science Knowledge	
	5. Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
UAB Mobility Unit (Transport Authority)	1. Funding	
	2. Cost Sharing with UAB	
	3. Policy Collaboration	
	4. Mobility Planning	
	5. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	6. Monetary Rents	
	7. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
UAB Management	1. Funding	
	2. Cost Sharing	
	3. Policy Collaboration	
	4. Mobility Planning and Know-how	
	5. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	6. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	1. Acquired Mobility Data	
	2. Cost Sharing with UAB	
	3. ITS Science funding	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	5. Access to Existing Research Programmes	
	6. Skilled Workforce	
	7. Informative content	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
UAB Smart Cities CORE	1. Smart City Acquired Data	
	2. Cost Sharing with UAB	
	3. Policy Collaboration	
	4. Technology Transfers	
	5. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	6. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
WEBSAYS	1. Skilled Workforce	
	2. Future Mobility Plans info	
	3. Informative Content & Entertaining Content	
	4. Science Knowledge	
	5. Mobility Acquired Data from UAB campus, others	

Survey II – Case Study 1 (Barcelona, Spain)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
ASLOGIC	1. Acquired Mobility Data	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders
	2. Commercial Funding	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders;
		<i>from</i> Commercial clients
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> UAB
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit;
		<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders
5. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
EDUCATORS	1. Educational Material	<i>from</i> UAB	
	2. Inspired Students	<i>from</i> Members of Community	
	3. Informative Content	<i>from</i> Social Media	
	4. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> UAB	
	5. Funding	<i>from</i> Government (Public taxes)	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
FrontierCities (Funder)	1. Acquired Mobility Data	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	
	2. Cost sharing	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
		<i>from</i> UAB LOGA	
	3. EU funding	<i>from</i> Public taxes	
	4. Plans and Reports of progress	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
		<i>from</i> UAB Management	
	5. Opinion & support	<i>from</i> Members of Community	
		<i>from</i> European Cities	
	6. Science opinions	<i>from</i> UAB	
7. Informative content	<i>from</i> Social Media		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
GOVERNMENT	1. Compliance with policy direction	<i>from</i> EU agencies;	
		<i>from</i> other inter-governmental agencies	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	<i>from</i> UAB Management;	
		<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> UAB	
	4. Public opinions	<i>from</i> Members of Community	
	5. Informative & disseminative content	<i>from</i> FrontierCities;	
		<i>from</i> Websays;	
		<i>from</i> Social media	
	6. Taxes	<i>from</i> Members of Community	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
	1. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit;	
		<i>from</i> FrontierCities;	
		<i>from</i> Aslogic	
	2. Employment	<i>from</i> UAB Management	
		<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	

Members of the University Community (end-users)		<i>from</i> UAB LOGA	
		<i>from</i> UAB Smart Cities CORE	
	3. Informative & entertaining content	<i>from</i> Websays	
		<i>from</i> Social media	
	4. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> UAB	
	5. Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	<i>from</i> FrontierCities	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
UAB Mobility Unit (Transport Authority)	1. Funding	<i>from</i> Government	
	2. Cost Sharing	<i>from</i> UAB Management	
	3. Policy Collaboration	<i>from</i> Municipality	
		<i>from</i> other Public Administration (excl. universities)	
	4. Mobility Planning	<i>from</i> Transport Operators	
		<i>from</i> UAB Management	
		<i>from</i> other Public Administration (excl. universities)	
	5. Future Information Exchange	<i>from</i> UAB Management	
		<i>from</i> other Public Administration (excl. universities)	

		<i>from</i> Transport Operators	
	6. Monetary Rents	<i>from</i> Commercial Operators	
	7. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
UAB Management	1. Funding	<i>from</i> Government	
		<i>from</i> Members of Community (students)	
		<i>from</i> Operators	
	2. Cost Sharing	UAB Mobility Unit	
	3. Policy Collaboration	<i>from</i> UAB Units	
		<i>from</i> other Public Administration (excl. universities)	
	4. Mobility Planning and Know-how	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
	5. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
		<i>from</i> Public Administration (excl. universities)	
		<i>from</i> Operators	
	6. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
	1. Acquired Mobility Data	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	

UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	2. Cost Sharing with UAB	<i>from</i> UAB Management	
	3. ITS Science funding	<i>from</i> UAB	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> UAB Mobility Unit	
		<i>from</i> UAB Management	
	5. Access to Existing Research Programmes	<i>from</i> EU programmes	
	6. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	
	7. Informative content	<i>from</i> Social media	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
UAB Smart Cities CORE	1. Smart City Acquired Data	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	
	2. Cost Sharing with UAB	UAB Management	
	3. Policy Collaboration	<i>from</i> UAB	
		<i>from</i> IT Services Unit	
		<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	
	4. Technology Transfers	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	
	5. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> UAB Management	
		<i>from</i> IT Services Unit	
		<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders	
	6. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
WEBSAYS	1. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators
	2. Future Mobility Plans info	<i>from</i> UAB Management
	3. Informative Content & Entertaining Content	<i>from</i> Social media
	4. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> UAB
	5. Mobility Acquired Data from UAB campus, others	<i>from</i> Members of Community

Lastly, please identify any specific needs that you consider having been missed from this survey.

6.2 Supporting Material of CS2

6.2.1 CS2 Stakeholders' profiles

<p>Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Skilled workforce (Educators) 2. Partial Funding (FP7 Research funding) 3. Future plans information (Municipality) 4. Mobility acquired data (Telecom Italia, Swarco Mizar) 5. General knowledge (scientific, technical, social) 	<p style="text-align: center;">AUDI</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: Automotive Supplier</p> <p>Role: Interact directly with the Municipality of Verona, and rely on launching innovative services and products, based on public-private partnerships. During the pilot trial, AUDI delivered cars equipped with a specific OBU</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Provide high-quality jobs in the car industry *Penetrate new markets *Respond to new market and technological opportunities *Benefit from Municipality's technology investment (funded under COMPASS4D project) for improving public services *Polishing its branding <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical) 2. Launch innovative car services 3. Expert knowledge on scientific & technical issues 4. General information about Municipality's plans and objectives <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Annual Financial Report 2015 - Cost Structure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Intangible Assets (IPRs, licences, concessions) - €978 million *Property, plant and equipment - €24,589 million *Long-term financial investments (investments in affiliated companies, borrowings to affiliated companies, participations) - €6,228 *Other particulars: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Cost of materials - €34,482 million *Personnel costs - €5,438 million *Other operating expenses, net interest, income tax expenses, other taxes <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle business sales - 80% of revenue Vehicle export business - 77% of revenue Other revenue (goods and services supplied to affiliated companies; sales to third parties) - 20% of revenue <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Produced vehicles 2. Launched innovative software products & services 3. Signed affiliations and partnerships
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<p>Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transit Signal Priority service (Swarco Mizar, Municipality) 2. Funding (Municipality of Verona) 3. Workforce (Educators) 4. Traffic acquired data (Telecom Italia) 5. General knowledge (technical, social) 	<p style="text-align: center;">ATV</p> <p>Group: Transport Operator</p> <p>Role: Interact directly or indirectly with the municipality of Verona (Italy), utilised the Transit Signal Priority provided by the pilot, rely on funding and contracts from the municipality</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Better utilisation of vehicles *Reduce travel time *Provide jobs in the local area *Benefit indirectly from the municipality’s technology investment <p>Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical) 2. Digital infrastructure to deliver real-time data 3. Growing physical infrastructure 4. Expansion of bus fleet and services 5. Data analysis to provide the knowledge about citizens needs and expectations <p>Cost Structure:</p> <p>Cost categories - vehicles; fuel and personnel</p> <p>Costs registered on the pilot - €40,000 to improve central and onboard systems; €150,000 to merge urban and suburban networks with coherent rules; €40,000 to improve cartography</p> <p>Revenue Model:</p> <p>Revenue model relies on two streams of income - fare collection from end-users, and a specific public payment from the municipality</p> <p>Outputs:</p> <p>Offered public bus transport services</p>
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Municipality of Verona (Italy)

Group: City / Government

Role: Responsible for providing funding, pilot trial coordination/cooperation; provide general policy directions at Italy-based local level

Objectives:

- *Ensure traffic smoothness
- *Ensure safety and security on roads
 - *Reduce travel time
- *Reduce accidents, pollution and congestion
- *Improve knowledge & understanding of sustainable transportation and mobility, technological forces bringing changes
- *Manage the municipality to be highly skilled, accountable, modern, citizen-centred and result-oriented

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, technical, human)
2. Launch services
3. Programmes management and cooperation
4. Motivated workforce
5. General technological knowledge

Cost Structure:

Public budgeting for maintaining roads and public transport services, including an acquired ITS platform

Revenue Model:

General Public Taxation

The pilot trial pursued social and environmental objectives

Outputs:

1. Maintained road capacity
2. Managed C-ITS platform acquired from COMPASS4D project
3. Traffic and mobility acquired and analysed data
4. Facilitated pre-existing ITS services
5. Policy-making documentations
6. Launched public-private partnerships

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Mobility acquired data (Telecom Italia, AUDI)
3. Innovative ITS services (Swarco Mizar)
4. Cost sharing (Network stakeholders)
5. Future Plans information (Network stakeholders)

SWARCO MIZAR

Group: ITS Provider

Role: Interact directly with the Municipality of Verona, and rely on EU research funding, commercial contracts and launch of innovative products (for ex., ITS hardware, controllers, UTC) and services (control methods, algorithms). Provided scientific systems (for ex., signalisation, UTC and all ITS hardware) during the pilot trial

Objectives:

- *Provide jobs in the industry
- *Develop new markets
- *Respond to new market and technological opportunities
- *Business Consolidation
- *Benefit from Municipality's technology investments with spin-off technology, indirect jobs & business

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical)
2. Launch innovative products & systems (e.g. traffic management as a service TMaaS)
3. Expert knowledge on ITS and other mobility-related scientific developments
4. General information of Municipality plans & objectives
5. Knowledge of policy directions in the field of transportation, smart cities, sustainable mobility and corporate, social, environmental responsibility

Cost Structure:

Annual Review 2010 - Financial Structure:

- Current Assets - 55.95%
- Long-term Assets - 44.05%
- Current Liabilities - 45.07%
- Long-term Liabilities - 26.33%
- Equity - 28.60%

Revenue Model:

Slowing down with expansion projects; focusing on business consolidation

- *Gross Profit - 28.56% of revenue
- Cash flow - 4.04% of revenue
- EBIT + EBITDA - 11.65% of revenue

Revenue Stream from the Pilot trial:

Direct payments from the Municipality of Verona for provided service and for future market developments

Outputs:

1. Innovative ITS services
2. Trained workforce (Swarco Academy)
3. Launched innovative products & systems
4. Partnerships and consolidations

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators, Swarco Academy)
2. Partial funding (FP7 Research funding)
3. Acquired traffic and work data (through ITS platform)
4. Future plans information (Municipality)
5. Science knowledge (Educators, Swarco R&D department)
6. Public mobility services (Municipality)

Taxi Operators

Group: Transport Operator

Role: Interact directly or indirectly with the municipality of Verona (Italy). They provide taxi services in the local area.

During the pilot trial a certain number of taxis were equipped with specific OBUs and utilised services provided by the pilot

Objectives:

- *Reduce travel time
- *Reduce congestion, traffic accidents and fuel costs
- *Provide jobs in the local area
- *Benefit indirectly from the municipality's technology investment

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. A certain number of available fleet
3. Growing physical infrastructure
4. Digital infrastructure to utilise real-time data

Cost Structure:

Cost categories - vehicles and fuels

Revenue Model:

Private stream of revenues from the fares

Outputs:

Offered private taxi services

Inputs:

1. Pre-existing and innovative ITS services (Swarco Mizar, Municipality)
2. Workforce (Educators)
3. Real-time data (Telecom Italia, AUDI)
4. General information (technical, social)

TELECOM ITALIA

Group: ICT Service Provider

Role: Interact directly or indirectly with the Municipality of Verona, rely on commercial contracts for mobile communication services. Provided a long-range communication option (4G mobile connectivity) during the pilot trial

Objectives:

1. Provide jobs in the industry
2. Enter new market niches
3. Respond to new market and technological opportunities
4. Polish its branding
5. Benefit indirectly from Municipality's technology investments

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical)
2. Launch new mobile services
3. Expert knowledge on mobile connectivity
4. Knowledge of Municipality plans & objectives
5. General knowledge (scientific, technical, social, etc.)
6. Information about policy directions in smart services for the public sector

Cost Structure:

Annual Financial Report 2016

*Intangible assets - €36,563 million

*Property, plants and equipment - €16,360 million

*Investments in affiliates and joint ventures - €18 million

*Employee benefits - €1,355 million

*Other operating expenses, income tax expenses, other tax expenses, net interest

Revenue Model:

Reduce transaction costs; improve allocation of production factors, and seek new markets / new consumers

Revenues - €19,025 million

Operating profit - €3,722 million

Profit before tax - €2,799 million

Profit for the year - €1,966 million

Outputs:

1. Enhanced mobile connectivity
2. Launched new mobile services
3. Increased network coverage (4G)

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Future plans information (Municipality)
3. Policy directions in smart services for the public sector (Municipality, policy-makers)
4. Science knowledge (Educators, Telecom Italia R&D department)
5. Sustainable mobility services (Municipality, Swarco Mizar, Citizens)

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compliance with policy direction (EU and other government agencies) 2. Plans and reports of progress (Municipality) 3. Science knowledge (Educators) 4. Public opinions (Citizens) 5. Informative & disseminative content (Municipality) 6. Taxes (Citizens) 	<p style="text-align: center;">GOVERNMENT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: City / Government</p> <p>Role: This includes public administration, government agencies and central departments. It is responsible for the provision of policy-making and policy direction</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Provide oversight of public programmes/ agencies *Appropriate funds to public programmes/ agencies *Evaluation of activities with respect to sustainable transportation and mobility *Promote actions that will reduce pollution, accidents and congestion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Sustain political support (central or local) *Introduce fair and good legislation <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources to implement objectives (budgetary) 2. Progress reports on activities 3. Data from government-funded programmes 4. Expert scientific, technical and policy advice 5. Knowledge of policy-direction of other public bodies, and inter-governmental agencies 6. General information (scientific, technical, social, etc.) 7. Political support (through voting) <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure: Central budgeting or local budgeting</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model: Public taxation</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Policy-making documentation and public funding *Introduced new legislation
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Educators: Italy-based organisations

Group: Academia

Role: Teach students, produce skilled community members, build enthusiasm and motivation for learning and developing in the labour market

Objectives:

*Provide academic excellency and life skills to all students

*Design and implement educational programmes that will provide relevant choices to prepare the students for college, the community and the workplace

Specific Needs:

1. Financial resources
2. Inspired students
3. Excellent educational content
4. Science & engineering knowledge
5. General knowledge and information (scientific, technical, social, etc)

Cost Structure:

University model

Revenue Model:

University model

Outputs:

1. Motivated, inspired and skilled workforce
2. Science knowledge

Inputs:

1. Educational material (Educators)
2. Inspired students (Citizens)
3. Policy directions (Government)
4. Science knowledge (Educators)
5. Funding (Public taxation - Government)

<p>Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products (Municipality of Verona) 2. Employment (Municipality, AVT, Telecom Italia, AUDI etc.) 3. General knowledge and information (Educators) 4. Online mobile applications (Municipality, Swarco Mizar) 	<p>Citizens</p> <p>Group: End-users</p> <p>Role: The Italy-based customers of the service and society as a whole</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Insure domestic /local reduction of accidents, congestion and pollution *Use online mobile applications (APP) in order to benefit from the pilot's services *Promote social welfare <p>Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Jobs 2. Domestic safety and security 3. Sustainable management of the mobility services 4. General knowledge (technical, social) 5. Information about the mobility service options <p>Cost Structure: Not applicable</p> <p>Revenue Model: Not applicable</p> <p>Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Enhanced local market for sustainable mobility services based on an acquired ITS platform
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6.2.2 CS2 Surveys' questions

Quantitative Analysis – December 2017, NEWBITS

WP4 Value Flow Scoring Questions

Case Study 2 – Verona, Italy

INSTRUCTIONS:

The intent of this analysis is to identify the highest value-producing interactions between the most important stakeholders in each of our four case studies, and subsequently map value flows of the major relationships. We need to develop insight into the *specific needs* of stakeholders and how *they are fulfilled*. In WP3, partners identified a number of stakeholders that interact with

each other in all four case studies. In WP4, we continue deepening the understanding of the nature of such specific needs of each major stakeholder, and their preferred source of fulfilment.

We plan to run two surveys, one after another, each contains a series of questions regarding the specific needs of each stakeholder, divided into sections by stakeholder. *When answering these questions, please think of yourself as a representative from that particular stakeholder group, for instance academia, industry association, mobility operator or policy-maker.*

Satisfaction / Regret

Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfilment of this need?

Responses: A response of A, B, C, D or E will be chosen. Answer E corresponds to “must-have” need.

- A. I would be satisfied by its presence, but do not regret its absence
- B. I would be satisfied by its presence, but would somewhat regret its absence
- C. I would be satisfied by its presence and do regret its absence
- D. Its presence is needed
- E. Its presence is absolutely essential

Importance of Source

Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be?

Responses: A response of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 can be chosen. The response 5 corresponds to “extremely important”.

- 1. Not important
- 2. Somewhat important
- 3. Important
- 4. Very important
- 5. Extremely important

Survey I – Case Study 2 (Verona, Italy)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
ATV	6. Transit Signal Priority service	
	7. Funding	
	8. Traffic acquired data	
	9. General Knowledge (technical, social)	
	10. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
AUDI	1. Partial Funding	
	2. Knowledge (scientific, technical, social)	
	3. Mobility acquired data	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	5. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
EDUCATORS (Italy)	6. Educational Material	
	7. Inspired Students	
	8. Policy Direction	
	9. Science Knowledge	
	10. Funding	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Municipality of Verona	8. Acquired Mobility Data	
	9. Cost sharing	
	10. Innovative ITS services	
	11. Future Plans Information	
	12. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
GOVERNMENT (Italy)	7. Compliance with policy direction	
	8. Plans and reports of progress	
	9. Science Knowledge	
	10. Public opinions	
	11. Informative & disseminative content	
	12. Taxes	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
CITIZENS (end-users)	6. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products	
	7. Employment	
	8. General Knowledge and Information	
	9. Online mobile applications	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Swarco Mizar	8. Partial Funding	
	9. Acquired traffic and work data	
	10. Science Knowledge	
	11. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	12. Public Mobility Services	
	13. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Taxi Operators	7. Pre-existing and innovative ITS services	
	8. Real-time Data	
	9. General Information	
	10. Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Telecomitalia	8. Policy Directions in Smart services for the Public Sector	
	9. Sustainable Mobility Services	
	10. Science knowledge	
	11. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	12. Skilled Workforce	

Survey II – Case Study 2 (Verona, Italy)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
ATV	4. Transit Signal Priority service	<i>from Swarco Mizar</i>	
		<i>from Municipality of Verona</i>	
	5. Funding	<i>from FP7 Research funding</i>	
	6. Traffic acquired data	<i>from Telecom Italia</i>	
	6. General knowledge (technical, social)	<i>from Network's stakeholders</i>	
	7. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
AUDI	1. Partial Funding	<i>from FP7 Research funding</i>	
	2. Knowledge (scientific, technical, social)	<i>from Network's stakeholders</i>	
		<i>from AUDI R&D department</i>	
	3. Mobility acquired data	<i>from Telecom Italia</i>	
		<i>from Swarco Mizar</i>	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from Municipality</i>	
5. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
EDUCATORS	6. Educational Material	<i>from</i> Educators
	7. Inspired Students	<i>from</i> Citizens
	8. Policy Directions	<i>from</i> Government
	9. Science Knowledge	<i>From</i> Educators
	10. Funding	<i>from</i> Government (Public taxes)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
Municipality Verona	8. Cost Sharing	<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders (incl. FP7 COMPASS4D project)
	9. Mobility Acquired Data	<i>from</i> Telecom Italia
		<i>from</i> AUDI
	10. Innovative services	<i>from</i> Swarco Mizar
	11. Future information Plans	<i>from</i> Government
		<i>from</i> Network's stakeholders
	12. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
GOVERNMENT	7. Compliance with policy direction	<i>from</i> EU agencies	
		<i>from</i> other inter-governmental agencies	
	8. Plans and reports of progress	<i>From</i> Municipality	
	9. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> Educators	
	10. Public opinions	<i>from</i> Citizens	
	11. Informative & disseminative content	<i>from</i> Municipality	
	12. Taxes	<i>from</i> Citizens	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
CITIZENS (end-users)	6. Sustainable mobility-derived services & products	<i>from</i> Municipality of Verona	
	7. Employment	<i>from</i> Municipality	
		<i>from</i> AVT	
		<i>from</i> Telecom Italia	

		<i>from</i> AUDI	
	8. General Knowledge and Information	<i>from</i> Educators	
	9. Online mobile applications	<i>from</i> Municipality	
		<i>from</i> Swarco Mizar	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
Swarco Mizar	8. Partial Funding	<i>from</i> FP7 Research Funding
	9. Acquired traffic and work data	<i>from</i> ITS platform
		<i>from</i> Municipality
	10. Public Mobility Services	<i>from</i> Municipality's strategic plan
	11. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> Municipality
	12. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> Swarco Mizar R&D department
		<i>from</i> Educators
13. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
		<i>from</i> Swarco Mizar

Taxi Operators	7. Pre-existing and innovative services and ITS	<i>from</i> Municipality of Verona	
	8. General Information (technical, social)	<i>from</i> Municipality	
	9. Real-time Data	<i>from</i> Telecom Italia (messages)	
		<i>from</i> AUDI (cars)	
	10. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow (inputs)	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Telecomitalia	8. Policy Direction in smart services for the Public Sector	<i>from</i> Municipality	
		<i>from</i> Government	
	9. Sustainable Mobility Services	<i>from</i> Municipality	
		<i>from</i> Swarco Mizar	
		<i>from</i> Citizens	
	10. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> Educators	
		<i>from</i> Telecom Italia R&D department	
	11. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from</i> Municipality	
	12. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

Lastly, please identify any specific needs that you consider having been missed from this survey.

6.3 Supporting Material of CS3

6.3.1 CS3 Stakeholders' profiles

<p>Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Cost Sharing (Network stakeholders)2. Future project plans (Network stakeholders)3. Skilled workforce (Educators)4. Science systems (TNO, FleetM, ICTdev, Portdat, TrackT)5. Policy direction (Government)	<p>Dinalog</p> <p>Group: Funding body</p> <p>Role: Responsible for research support and coordination; managing innovative programme aimed at private-public research projects in logistics</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">*Increase logistics efficiency*Ensure sustainable and environmental economic growth*Ensure a proper programme management*Ensure purposeful knowledge gathering*Comply with regulatory requirements for obtaining necessary subsidies <p>Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Resources (budgetary, human)2. Programme coordination and management3. Data to support objectives4. General knowledge and information (policy, social, technical)5. Strong logistics sector <p>Cost Structure: publicly funded</p> <p>Revenue Model: publicly funded</p> <p>Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Provided financial funds
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Fleet M

Group: ITS/ICT providers

Role: Use data and derived knowledge to develop innovative services. It develops software, hardware and services for transport sector. The special focus is on fleet management systems, which it provided for trucks of ITO

Objectives:

*Use data for commercial purposes and increase offered services for customers

*Serve its client ITO

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Data to support objectives
3. New customers and business expansion
4. Science and technical knowledge

Cost Structure:

Direct operational costs and personnel expenses

Revenue Model:

Sales of ICT services

Outputs:

1. Delivered truck geographical location

Inputs:

1. Sharing of data (ITO)
2. Truck identification - number plates (ITO)
3. Skilled workforce (Educators)

ICTdev

Group: ITS/ICT service provider

Role: Responsible for IT service provisions. It offers software and hardware solutions with a special focus on telecommunications

Objectives:

*Offer IT knowledge to new areas

*Launch new services

Specific Needs:

1. Resources

2. New business

3. New customers

4. Science and technical knowledge

5. General information (policy, social, economic)

Cost Structure:

not available

Revenue Model:

Set up software and hardware

Outputs:

1. APIs to allow for communication of the different data sources for inland shipping route

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)

2. Future plans information (PoR, ITO, ShipperElectronics)

3. AIS-datalink of ship movements (PoR)

4. Science knowledge (TNO)

5. Collaboration and commitment (Network stakeholders)

ITO (Inland Terminal Operator)

Group: Terminal Operators

Role: Use real time data to generate information / knowledge applicable to planning activities. ITO is an inland terminal/transport company, operational in the Netherlands and Belgium as they own barge services, container storage facilities and truck services

Objectives:

- *Use real time data for commercial planning
- *Visualise complex information in a simplified mechanism
- *Find causes for delays (loading/unloading time, transshipment times on terminal)
- *Smooth the logistics processes
- *Reduce the need for coordination
- *Offer better service to shippers
- *Increase profitability via business expansion

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Real time acquired data to support objectives
3. Vessels and sea terminal information
4. Transshipment information (technical, economic)

Cost Structure:

Two categories - direct costs of terminal operations and personnel costs

Revenue Model:

Revenues from offered terminal and related services

Outputs:

1. Provided planning information; status of container on the inland terminal and truck location via FleetM
2. Shipment of container from PoR to the inland route - provided barge ID for AIS tracking

Inputs:

1. Track and trace service information - estimated arrival times (ITO, IST provider)
2. Information of handling container at deep sea terminal (PoR, IST provider)
3. Skilled workforce (Educators)
4. Technical knowledge, regulatory rules (TNO, Government)

LIOF

Group: Regional Development Company

Role: With logistics defined as one of the top sectors in the regional area of Limburg (the Netherlands), LIOF has acquired knowledge and a broader network in it. LIOF offers help to entrepreneurs in the form of knowledge/ algorithms, network and finances

Objectives:

- *Launch new services for regional clients
- *Manage resources to promote responsible use
- *Improve knowledge and understanding of regional economy

Specific Needs:

1. Resources to implement its objectives
2. Create new businesses for local entrepreneurs
3. Expert input on logistics & technical issues
4. Knowledge and information (policy, social, economic)

Cost Structure:

Direct costs and personnel expenses

Revenue Model:

LIOF is half funded by the Dutch state and half by the province of Limburg

Outputs:

1. Provided network and business support to local entrepreneurs
2. Promotion of the project to obtain new partners for scaling it up

Inputs:

1. Funding (Government, Province)
2. Skilled workforce (Educators)
3. Business opportunities (Network stakeholders)
4. Science knowledge (TNO)

PoR (Port of Rotterdam)

Group: Port Authority

Role: The responsible body, Port of Rotterdam (in Dutch - Havenbedrijf Rotterdam) is governing the deep sea port of Rotterdam, the largest one in Europe. Its main tasks are to ensure high-quality of services and sustain competitiveness of the port.

Objectives:

- *Improve provided services for port stakeholders
- *Generate knowledge and algorithm
- *Adapt to future market needs
- *Optimise hinterland transport
- *Reduce shipment times
- * Provide jobs in the industry

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical, budgetary)
2. Expert knowledge on technical issues
3. Willingness to commit to the pilot project
4. Well-defined added value services

Cost Structure:

Total costs of the port of Rotterdam are about €450 million (contrasting €660 million in revenues). Main costs are personnel, depreciations of assets, exploitation costs and costs for loans. Each are about 1/4 of total costs.

Revenue Model:

The port of Rotterdam main revenues are from contracts (rents) and port dues. All around €300 million.

Outputs:

1. Delivered port operations
2. Delivered relating knowledge

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Science knowledge and system (TNO)
3. Improved efficiency of hinterland transport (ShipperElectronics, ITO, WarehouseL)
4. Real time data (ITS providers)

Portdat (Port Data Provider)

Group: ITS/ICT service providers

Role: Use port derived data to develop innovative services. It's a port community system allowing companies to benefit from a multitude of intelligent services for simple and efficient information exchange between stakeholders of the port community in Amsterdam and Rotterdam.

Objectives:

- *Use port derived data for commercial purposes
- *Improve services for port community
- *Search for additional features
- *Optimal re-use of information

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Science and technical knowledge
3. Port community data
4. General information (policy, social, etc.)

Cost Structure:

Operational costs and personnel expenses

Revenue Model:

Portdat is a non-profit organisation. Companies only pay a fee for the use of services with demonstrable added value. These costs are fairly minor compared to the advantages offered by the services. Financial support for services of particular strategic importance to the port is obtained from the general revenues of Port of Rotterdam and Port of Amsterdam shareholders.

Outputs:

1. Designed data platform of port operations
2. Delivered services for port operations

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Data of individual port users (PoR)
3. Science and technical knowledge (TNO)

Shipper

Group: Shippers

Role: This company represents the end-users of the logistics system. They are active in electronic high-value consumer goods and ship products from China to a warehouse in Limburg (the Netherlands). During the pilot trial, they were the facilitator of this service

Objectives:

- *Optimisation of integrated logistics chain (from 10 to 6/7 days)
- *Reduce hidden costs in transport chain
- *Optimise planning and reliability due to better information
 - *Lower available stock of goods
 - *Better service provision

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Information of shipment
3. Information of inland terminal's times
4. Knowledge of estimated times and actual times
5. Decrease of delays
6. Science and technical knowledge

Cost Structure:

Two categories - direct costs from operational activities and personnel costs

Revenue Model:

Sales of electronic equipment

Outputs:

1. Delivered electronic goods
2. Report of shipment information
3. Provided planning data
4. Provided feedback during the pilot phase to help any development of this new service

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Track and trace service information (PoR, ITO)
3. Handling information, estimated time of arrival (PoR, ITO, ITS provider)
4. Technical knowledge (TNO)

TNO

Group: Research Organisation

Role: A Dutch research organisation that generates science knowledge, develops applied scientific research in the areas of: energy, industry, healthy living, defence, security, safety and urbanisation; provides technical knowledge expertise to the government and commercial organisations

Objectives:

- *Produce useful knowledge and information
- *Develop services for operationalisation
- *Gain better efficiency performance via applications of smart data
- *Provide advice to others on matters of scientific research and science systems

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, human)
2. Collaboration of all stakeholders
3. Acquired smart data
4. Interested parties that are willing to implement the service
5. Access to existing and future clients
6. General knowledge and information (scientific, technical, economic, etc.)
7. Information about policy directions

Cost Structure:

Two categories - direct project costs (€70 million) and personnel expenses (€270 million)

Revenue Model:

Three sources of revenues - the Dutch Government (€176 million); an adviser to commercial companies and international governments (€255 million); and subsidiaries' contributions (€100 million)

Outputs:

1. ITS-driven services based on a data platform
2. Delivered scientific and technical know-how, and project management
3. Tracking and tracing services on container transport from deep sea to warehouse in hinterland.

Inputs:

1. Future plans information (ITO, Shipper electronics, PoR)
2. Skilled workforce (Educators)
3. GPS/AIS acquired data
4. Funding (Government, Commercial)
5. Collaboration and commitment (Network stakeholders)
6. Policy documentation (Government)

TrackT

Group: ITS provider

Role: Responsible for using real time data and derived traffic information in primary business processes to develop innovative IT services and products

Objectives:

- *Use acquired data for commercial purposes
- *Potential expansion of data coverage to inland shipping
- *Create innovative ways of applying data

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Real time data to map actual movements
3. Funding
4. Science and technical knowledge

Cost Structure:

not available

Revenue Model:

not available

Outputs:

1. Designed visual mapping of real time transport information

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. ITS-derived data (TNO, ICTdev)
3. Real time fleet monitoring information (FleetM)
4. Future plans information (Network stakeholders)
5. Science knowledge (TNO)

Warehouse L

Group: Warehouse Operators

Role: Use real time data to better plan its activities and derive information from them to develop innovative services. Thus they offer additional services to their clients.

Objectives:

- *Use real time data for optimising transport services
- *Use efficiently its own resources
- *Reduce hidden costs due to slack and ad hoc communication
- *Smooth the steady stream of goods
- *Increase time for dealing with actual emergencies
- *Match requests of customers with transport flexibility
- *Create innovative ways of using the data

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, human)
2. Real-time data acquired to support objectives
3. General information (technical, economic, etc.)
4. Motivated workforce

Cost Structure:

Two categories - direct costs of warehouse operations; and personnel costs

Revenue Model:

Revenues from offered logistics services

Outputs:

1. Delivered planning data as input for warehousing services (unloading containers, emptying containers, and setting-up goods for a pick-up)
2. Provided feedback during the pilot scheme in order to improve any development of the service

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Real time acquired data (ITS providers)
3. Information about ATA container arrival (PoR)
4. Science knowledge (TNO)
5. Information on arrival of container at inland terminal (ITO)

<p style="text-align: center;">Inputs</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Compliance with policy direction (EU and other government agencies) 2. Plans and reports of progress (TNO, Dinalog, LIOF) 3. Science knowledge (TNO, LIOF) 4. Informative & disseminative content (LIOF) 5. Corporate Taxes (PoR, ShipperElectronics, ITO, etc) 6. Skilled workforce (Educators) 7. Cost sharing (Network stakeholders) 	<p style="text-align: center;">GOVERNMENT</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group: City / Government</p> <p>Role: This includes Dutch municipalities, city authorities, public administration, government agencies and central departments. It is responsible for the provision of policy-making & policy direction</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Provide oversight of public programmes/ agencies *Appropriate funds to public programmes/ agencies *Evaluation of activities with respect to sustainable and safe transport industry *Promote actions that will improve safety and security of the public *Sustain political support (central or local) *Introduce fair and good transport/ logistics legislation <p style="text-align: center;">Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources to implement objectives (budgetary) 2. Progress reports on activities 3. Data from government-funded programmes 4. Expert scientific, technical and policy advice 5. Knowledge of policy-direction of other public bodies, and inter-governmental agencies 6. General information (scientific, technical, legal, etc.) 7. Political support (through voting) <p style="text-align: center;">Cost Structure: Central budgeting or local budgeting</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Revenue Model: Public taxation</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Policy-making documentation 2. Ensured public funding 3. Legislation documentation
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6.3.2 CS3 Surveys' questions

Quantitative Analysis – December 2017, NEWBITS

WP4 Value Flow Scoring Questions

Case Study 3 – Rotterdam, the Netherlands

INSTRUCTIONS:

The intent of this analysis is to identify the highest value-producing interactions between the most important stakeholders in each of our four case studies, and subsequently map value flows of the major relationships. We need to develop insight into the *specific needs* of stakeholders and how *they are fulfilled*. In WP3, partners identified a number of stakeholders that interact with each other in all four case studies. In WP4, we continue deepening the understanding of the nature of such specific needs of each major stakeholder, and their preferred source of fulfilment.

We plan to run two surveys, one after another, each contains a series of questions regarding the specific needs of each stakeholder, divided into sections by stakeholder. When answering these questions, please think of yourself as a representative from that particular stakeholder group, for instance academia, industry association, mobility operator or policy-maker.

Satisfaction / Regret

Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfillment of this need?

Responses: A response of A, B, C, D or E will be chosen. Answer E corresponds to “must-have” need.

- A. I would be satisfied by its presence, but do not regret its absence
- B. I would be satisfied by its presence, but would somewhat regret its absence
- C. I would be satisfied by its presence and do regret its absence
- D. Its presence is needed
- E. Its presence is absolutely essential

Importance of Source

Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be?

Responses: A response of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 can be chosen. The response 5 corresponds to “extremely important”.

- 1. Not important
- 2. Somewhat important
- 3. Important
- 4. Very important
- 5. Extremely important

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Shipper	1. Real-time information container transport	
	2. Higher predictability logistic process	
	3. Earlier delivery to retailers	
	4. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	
	5. Improved contract conditions with sea shipping company (reduction in transport costs, demurrage costs, transport time)	
	6. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	
	7. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system to apply the service	
	8. Skilled Workforce - trained employees to use the service	
	9.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Warehousing and logistic services	1. Real-time information container status	
	2. Easier access to order and planning information of container	
	3. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	
	4. New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (e.g. transport time)	
	5. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	
	6. Higher predictability of container arrival at warehouse.	
	7. Faster/ earlier container arrival at warehouse	
	8. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system to apply the service.	
	9. Skilled Workforce- trained employees to use the service	
	10.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Inland terminal operator	1. Neutral/ transparent way of sharing container status information with partners.	
	2. Improved real-time information on container status at deep sea terminal	
	3. Total logistic chain visibility (information from all partners at once).	
	4. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	
	5. New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (e.g. transport time)	
	6. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	
	7. Earlier container pick-up at deep sea terminal	
	8. More reliable container release time at deep sea terminal	
	9. Technical knowledge on information /processes/system in relation to the service	
	10. Skilled Workforce- trained employees to use the service	
	11.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Information service provider	1. Flexibility with respect to platform functionality and information sources	
	2. Contract conditions with platform developer (costs, payment structure)	
	3. Contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	
	4. Technical knowledge on information /processes/system in relation to the service	
	5. Skilled Workforce	
	6. Importance of pilot project for market introduction	
	7.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization
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		(A B C D E)
Platform developer/ maintenance	1. Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	
	2. Planning and container status information in hinterland transport	
	3. Container status at deep sea terminal (handling, customs)	
	4. Vessel arrival information from sea shipping companies (ETA/ATA)	
	5. Authorization to include container status data in the platform	
	6. Agreements to share/use deep sea terminal data	
	7. Contract conditions with information service provider (costs, payment structure)	
	8. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system in relation to the service	
	9. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	
	10.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Portdat	1. Data of individual port users	
	2. Shared policy goals with Port of Rotterdam	
	3. Authorization to share data of port community system with platform developer	
	4. Technical knowledge of the functionality (how to feed the service with data)	
	5. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	
	6.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
FleetM	1. Authorization for data sharing with platform	
	2. Technical knowledge of the functionality (how to feed the service with data)	
	3. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Port of Rotterdam	11. Operational service Real-time data on hinterland container transport	
	1. Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	
	12. Understanding of the functioning of the service	
	13. Skilled Workforce	
	14.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
LIOF (Regional Development Company)	1. Technical and economic information about the service to support market introduction	
	2. Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	
	3. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	
	4. Funding (from government)	
	5.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
TNO	1. Knowledge of policy directions	
	2. Market information for business case development in pilot project	
	3. Stakeholder input for development of functionalities service	
	4. Skilled Workforce	
	5. Project funding for pilot (to TNO representing the stakeholder group)	
	6.	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Dinalog	1. Pilot results to build on for new projects	
	2. Cost Sharing in pilot phase (co financing of projects)	
	3. Skilled Workforce	
	4. Policy Directions	
	5.	

Note: Cost Sharing – sharing of costs by two or more stakeholders of the network

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
EDUCATORS (universities/schools)	1. New Educational Material related to ITS challenges	
	2. Inspired Students	
	3. Science Knowledge on ITS	
	4. Funding	
	5.	

Note: Educators (universities, colleges) are the source of skilled workers

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
GOVERNMENT	1. Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport, modal split)	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	
	3. Science Knowledge (service related)	
	4. Informative & disseminative content	
	5. Skilled Workforce	
	6. Corporate Taxes	
	7.	

Note: Government – this includes Dutch municipalities, city authorities, public administration, government agencies and central departments. It is responsible for the provision of policy-making and policy directions.

Survey II – Case Study 3 (Rotterdam, the Netherlands)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Shipper	1. Real-time information container transport	From platform service provider	
	2. Higher predictability logistic process	From Warehouse L	
		From ITO	
		From Deep sea terminal	
	3. Earlier delivery to retailers	From Warehouse	
		From ITO	
		From Deep sea terminal	
	4. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	From Warehouse	
		From ITO	
	5. Improved contract conditions with sea shipping company (reduction in transport costs, demurrage costs, transport time)	From sea shipping company/ITO	
	6. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	From Platform service provider	
		From ITO	
		From Warehouse L	
	7. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system to apply the service	From TNO	
		From platform service provider	
	8. Skilled Workforce – trained employees to use the service	From educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Warehousing and logistic services	1. Real-time information container status	<i>From platform service developer</i>	
	2. Easier access to order and planning information of container	<i>From platform service developer</i>	
	3. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	<i>From Shipper</i>	
		<i>From ITO</i>	
	4. New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (e.g. transport time)	<i>From Shipper</i>	
		<i>From ITO</i>	
	5. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	<i>From platform service provider</i>	
		<i>From Shipper</i>	
		<i>From ITO</i>	
	6. Higher predictability of container arrival at warehouse.	<i>From ITO</i>	
	7. Faster/ earlier container arrival at warehouse	<i>From ITO</i>	
	8. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system to apply the service	<i>From TNO</i>	
<i>From platform service provider</i>			
9. Skilled Workforce- trained employees to use the service	<i>From educators</i>		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Inland terminal operator	1. Neutral/ transparent way of sharing container status information with partners.	<i>From Platform service developer</i>	
	2. Improved real-time information on container status at deep sea terminal	<i>From Platform service developer</i>	

3. Total logistic chain visibility (information from all partners at once).	<i>From Platform service developer</i>	
4. Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	<i>From Shipper</i>	
	<i>From Warehouse L</i>	
	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
5. New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (e.g. transport time)	<i>From Shipper</i>	
	<i>From Warehouse L</i>	
6. Formal contract and other agreements for the use of the service	<i>From platform service provider</i>	
	<i>From Shipper</i>	
	<i>From Warehouse L</i>	
7. Earlier container release at deep sea terminal	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
8. More reliable container release time at deep sea terminal	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
9. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system in relation to the service	<i>From Platform operator</i>	
	<i>From TNO</i>	
10. Skilled Workforce- trained employees to use the service	<i>From educators</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
	1. Flexibility with respect to platform functionality and new information sources	<i>From Platform developer</i>
	2. Contract conditions with platform developer (costs, payment structure)	<i>From Platform developer</i>
	3. Contract conditions for service with end-users (costs, payment structure)	<i>From Shipper</i>
		<i>From Warehouse L</i>

Information service provider		<i>From ITO</i>	
	4. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system in relation to the service	<i>From Platform operator</i>	
		<i>From TNO</i>	
	5. Skilled Workforce	<i>From educators</i>	
	6. Importance of pilot project for market introduction	<i>From TNO</i>	
		<i>From LIOF</i>	
		<i>From Logistical partners</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Platform developer/maintenance	1. Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	<i>From FleetM</i>	
		<i>From AISHUB</i>	
		<i>From NDW</i>	
	2. Planning and container status information in hinterland transport	<i>From ITO</i>	
		<i>From Warehouse L</i>	
		<i>From Shipper</i>	
	3. Container status at deep sea terminal (handling, customs)	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
		<i>From Portdat</i>	
	4. Vessel arrival information from sea shipping companies (ETA/ATA)	<i>From sea shipping terminal</i>	
		<i>From Portdat</i>	
	5. Authorization to include container status data in the platform	<i>From sea shipping company</i>	

		<i>From Portdat</i>	
	6. Agreements to share/use deep sea terminal data	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
		<i>From Portdat</i>	
	7. Contract conditions with information service provider (costs, payment structure)	<i>From Information service provider</i>	
	8. Technical knowledge on information/processes/system in relation to the service	<i>From Platform operator</i>	
		<i>From TNO</i>	
	9. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	<i>From educators</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Portdat	1. Data of individual port users	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
		<i>From ITO</i>	
		<i>From sea shipping terminals</i>	
	2. Shared policy goals with Port of Rotterdam	<i>From Port of Rotterdam</i>	
	3. Authorization to share data of port community system with platform developer	<i>From Deep sea terminal</i>	
		<i>From Sea shipping company</i>	
		<i>From ITO</i>	
	4. Technical knowledge of the functionality (how to feed the service with data)	<i>From Platform operator</i>	
		<i>From TNO</i>	

	5. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	From educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
FleetM	1. Authorization for data sharing with platform	From ITO	
	2. Technical knowledge of the functionality (how to feed the service with data)	From Platform operator	
		From TNO	
	3. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	From educators	

Note: Skilled Workforce – technically skilled and educated/trained employees

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Port of Rotterdam	2. Operational service Real-time data on hinterland container transport	From Platform	
	3. Shared policy goals (e.g. synchromodal transport)	From Portdat	
		From Government	
From Platform			
		From TNO	
	4. Understanding of the functioning of the service	From platform	
		From TNO	
	5. Skilled Workforce	From educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
LIOF (Regional Development Company)	1. Technical and economic information about the service to support market introduction	From TNO	

		<i>From Platform</i>	
	2. Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	<i>From TNO</i>	
		<i>From Platform</i>	
	3. Skilled Workforce/ trained employees	<i>From educators</i>	
	4. Funding	<i>From Government</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
TNO	1. Knowledge of policy directions	<i>From Dinalog</i>	
		<i>From Government</i>	
		<i>From Port of Rotterdam</i>	
	2. Market information for business case development in pilot project	<i>From consortium</i>	
	3. Stakeholder input for development of functionalities service	<i>From consortium</i>	
	4. Skilled Workforce	<i>From educators</i>	
	5. Project funding for pilot (to TNO representing the stakeholder group)	<i>From Dinalog</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Dinalog	1. Pilot results to build on for new projects	<i>From TNO</i>	
	2. Cost Sharing in pilot phase (co financing of projects)	<i>From consortium</i>	
	3. Skilled Workforce	<i>From educators</i>	
	4. Policy Directions	<i>From Government</i>	
		<i>From industry</i>	
5.			

Note: Cost Sharing – sharing of costs by two or more stakeholders of the network

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
EDUCATORS (universities/ schools)	1. New Educational Material related to ITS challenges	From TNO	
		From industry	
	2. Inspired Students interested in ITS	From society	
		From industry	
	3. Science Knowledge on ITS	From industry	
		From academics	
	4. Funding	From government	

Note: Educators (universities, colleges) are the source of skilled workers

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
GOVERNMENT	1. Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport, modal split)	From Port of Rotterdam	
		From Dinalog	
		From TNO	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	From TNO	
		From Dinalog	
	3. Science Knowledge (service related)	From TNO	
		From Dinalog	
	4. Informative & disseminative content	From Dinalog	
		From TNO	
	5. Skilled Workforce	From educators	
6. Corporate Taxes	From Industry		

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Note: Government – this includes Dutch municipalities, city authorities, public administration, government agencies and central departments. It is responsible for the provision of policy-making and policy directions

6.4 Supporting Material of CS4

6.4.1 CS4 Stakeholders' profiles

<p>Inputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Skilled workforce (Educators)2. Funding (Public, commercial)3. Future plans information (CUE, Network Rail)4. New services (CUE, Alstom R&D)5. Data analytics technology (CUE)	<p>Alstom Transport</p> <p>Group: Train Manufacturer</p> <p>Role: Interact directly or indirectly with CUE, develop and marketise system equipment/services for the transport sector; rely on public funding and commercial contracts; offer a complete range of solutions, customised services (maintenance, modernisation), infrastructure, signalling and digital mobility solutions.</p> <p>Objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">*Provide jobs in the manufacturing industry*Reinforce worldwide presence*Satisfy local customers*Ensure flawless contract execution*Provide the most comprehensive range of systems, signalling equipment and services in each area of the rail industry.*Innovate to achieve differentiation and gain a competitive edge <p>Specific Needs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical)2. Partnerships with local actors to gain joint ventures3. Launch new services4. Expert knowledge on scientific & technical issues5. General information of policy directions <p>Cost Structure:</p> <p>For 2016/17, Alstom booked €10.0 billion of orders (51% from Europe) leading to a new record-breaking backlog of €34.8 billion. Over the same period, sales were up 6%, amounting to €7.3 billion (56% from Europe). Net income (Group share) reached €289 million. Alstom invested €150 million in capital expenditures in fiscal year 2016/17. The majority of orders (55%) and sales (43%) comes from rolling stock.</p> <p>Revenue Model:</p> <p>Alstom is a French multinational corporation with a majority of revenues originating from sales</p> <p>Outputs:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Equipment and services in urban and main line transport (trains, signalling, services and infrastructure)2. Public-private partnerships
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Network Rail

Group: Rail Infrastructure Manager

Role: Responsible for operating/managing the railway infrastructure in England, Wales and Scotland on behalf of the public. It is a natural monopoly that operates as a public company reporting to the UK Government through the Department for Transport (DfT), devolved into 9 geographically-based businesses called routes. Each route manages the railway network in their local area and works closely with their local train operators.

Objectives:

- *Operate, maintain and develop Britain's rail infrastructure
- *Manage the national rail timetables and 18 of the largest stations in England, Scotland and Wales
- *Deliver safer, reliable railway with greater capacity and efficiency
- *Connect more people to more places, safely and quickly
- *Fund the practical implementation of the KEEP SAFE project

Specific Needs:

1. Policy direction
2. Resources to implement its objectives
3. KEEP SAFE project coordination/management
4. Cooperate with local train operators and other partners
5. Access to facilities
6. Expert input on scientific & technical issues
7. Knowledge of regulations and standards
8. Information about agency/commercial partners needs, capabilities & objectives

Cost Structure:

- From Annual Report 2016
- *Operating Costs - £2,712 million
 - *Capital expenditure - £6,684 million
 - *Net debt - £41.60 billion
- "KEEP SAFE" project's cost - £50,000

Revenue Model:

The income is a mixture of direct grants from the UK and Scottish Governments, charges levied on train operators that use the network, and income mainly from commercial property estate.

- From Annual Report 2016:
- Revenues - £6,098 million
 - Profit before tax - £411 million

Outputs:

1. Managed railway infrastructure
2. Managed national rail timetables
3. Managed 18 rail stations

Inputs:

1. Funding (grants from DfT and Transport Scotland)
2. Commercial charges (Virgin Trains, properties)
3. Cost sharing (CUE about "Keep Safe" project)
4. Skilled workforce (Educators)
5. Policy & Regulatory advice (ORR, RSSB)
6. Science knowledge (CUE)
7. Science systems (Alstom Transport)

Office of Rail and Road

Group: Regulatory body

Role: As an independent regulator (non-ministerial government department), responsible for protecting the interests of rail and road users in the UK by improving the safety, value and performance of railways and roads.

Objectives:

- *Ensure safer railway and road in the UK
- *Ensure better customer service
- *Improve efficiency and boost value for money for taxpayers
- *Promote dynamic and commercially sustainable rail sector
- *Ensure high-performing regulation: develop and apply proportionate, risk-based regulation

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (budgetary, human, technical)
2. Collaboration with stakeholders in the sector
3. Monitoring data (fares, prices, charges) to support objectives
4. Policy direction
5. General knowledge (scientific, social, etc.)

Cost Structure:

According to ORR Business Plan 2016/17, they have distinct lines of funding: a safety levy, which pays for all health and safety work; an economic licence fee, which pays for economic regulation; and a direct grant from the Department for Transport for the work on highways regulation.

70% of outgoings are pay. As part of their overall turnover, £2.55 million is set aside for their work as the Highways Monitor. They also generate income beyond the UK rail industry levy and government funding for the Highways Monitor.

Revenue Model:

The total income from their rail and roads functions was £31.4 million in 2016-17: 51% rail safety; 41% rail economic; 8% roads. ORR is funded by the rail industry via licence fees and safety levies.

Outputs:

1. Rail regulations (health and safety)
2. Economic regulations (regulating Network Rail)
3. Promoting competition (investigating companies)
4. Protecting consumers
5. Issuing licences, publications and consultations

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Financial resources (levies, licence fees from Network Rail, Virgin Trains)
3. Grant from the DfT (Government)
4. Railway acquired data (Network Rail)
5. Scientific knowledge (technical, economic, social)
6. Policy direction (Government)

Inputs:

1. Railway improved safety-derived products & services (CUE, Network Rail, Virgin Trains)
2. Employment (Network Rail, Alstom, Virgin Trains, etc.)
3. Health & safety protection (ORR, RSSB, Government)
4. Science knowledge (Educators)
5. Data analysed content (CUE)
6. Railway fair prices (ORR)

Public

Group: Citizens (indirectly end-users)
Role: The general UK population and society

Objectives:

- *Promote social welfare
- *Provide for the existing and potential public funding
- *Insure domestic safe and reliable transportation

Specific Needs:

1. Jobs
2. Educational knowledge
3. National safety and security on trains
4. Information about transport applications
5. Good governance of the railway network
6. Good customer services
7. Reliable train operation
8. Sustainable management of the industry

Cost Structure:
not applicable

Revenue Model:
not applicable

Outputs:

1. Provided taxation

Railway Safety and Standard Board

Group: Rail Industry Board

Role: Through research, standards, analysis and insight, RSSB supports members and stakeholders in driving improvements in health and wellbeing, and delivering a safer, more efficient and sustainable rail system

Objectives:

*Supporting the initial KEEP SAFE project

*Health & Safety - establish a framework and systems that promote health and safety collaboration and inform decisions to reduce risk and harm

*More efficiency - update standards, modernise systems and publish research yielding benefits

*Sustainability - embed sustainable principles in industry strategies, collate and share best practise to publicly show rail as a sustainable system

Specific Needs:

1. Resources to implement its objectives
2. Railway-acquired data to support objectives
3. Collaboration with members and stakeholders in the sector
4. Expert input on scientific&technical issues
5. Informative content on new standards
6. Knowledge of policy direction
7. Information on performing research, surveys, consultations

Cost Structure:

According to the last Annual Review 2015-2016, RSSB's operating income grew by 7% to £48.7m (2014/15 £45.5m). The main driver for this increase was income in respect of membership levy and for Innovation.

Operating expenditure increased by 4% to £49.1m. Future Railway activities incurred expenditure approaching £13.4m. R&D activities incurred expenditure approaching £9.5 million.

Staff costs remained the most significant single element of RSSB's cost base with payroll and other staff costs totalling £25.3 million.

Overall there was an operating loss of £0.4 million. The main driver for this loss was the charge for the year relating to the employers share of the net interest on the defined benefit liability of the pension scheme.

RSSB funded the initial KEEP SAFE project: this was £35,000 of UK public funding.

Revenue Model:

RSSB is a not-for-profit company owned by major industry stakeholders. The company is limited by guarantee and is governed by its members and a board. Its income is a mixture of membership levies, grants from DfT and miscellaneous receipts from various goods & services.

Outputs:

1. Tools & models (e.g. CCTV toolkit; Common Safety Targets, Indicators and Methods; Health cost benefit analysis support tool; Vehicle Track Interaction Strategic Model; etc.)
2. Guidance (e.g. Accident investigation; Safety Management System principles; Managing drivers on routes undergoing significant change; etc.)
3. Consultancy & support (e.g. Health & wellbeing resources; Railway Industry Supplier Approval Scheme; Accreditation services; etc.)
4. Science industry systems (e.g. National Incident Reporting Online; Industry Shared Risk Database; Platform distances database; etc.)
5. Technical Reports (e.g. Rail Technical Strategy; Annual Safety Performance Report; Data quality initiatives; etc.)
6. Educational Training (e.g. Train Driver Training programme; Non-Technical Skills Forum; Human factors awareness course for incident investigators; etc.)
7. Standards (e.g. Requirements Management Database; Proposals register; Rule Book and other operational publications; etc.)
8. Research (e.g. Rail Research UK Association; SPARK)
9. News and conferences

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Financial resources (levies from Network Rail)
3. Public funding (Government)
4. Cost sharing (CUE about "Keep Safe" project)
5. Science knowledge and data analytics (CUE)
6. Railway analysed data (CUE)
7. Future policy direction (Government, ORR)

Serco

Group: Organisation delivering services

Role: Responsible for operating government services to citizens; support services to defence organisations, healthcare industry, border control and immigration, justice system and transport industry; rely on public funding and launch new public services

Objectives:

- *Provide jobs in the public sector
- *Deliver superb public services that transform outcomes and make a positive difference for citizens
- *Be a trusted partner of governments

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Joint ventures with commercial partners
3. Expert knowledge on public services
4. Knowledge of policy direction, governments' plans and objectives
5. Strategic partners to deliver services as a Consortium, as prime contractor or a subcontractor
6. Bring together companies with specialised skills

Cost Structure:

Annual Report 2016

The UK Central Government division includes UK operations in Defence, Justice & Immigration and Transport. Revenue for 2016 was £678.6m. Underlying Trading Profit was £52.2m. UK Central Government represented around £300m of the Group's aggregate total value of signed contracts during the year.

The UK & Europe Local & Regional Government division includes UK Health and UK and European Citizen Services sectors. Revenue for 2016 was £696.5m. There was an Underlying Trading Loss of £6.5m. This represented around £750m of the Group's aggregate total value of signed contracts during the year.

Corporate costs relate to typical central function costs of running the Group, including executive, governance and support functions such as HR, finance and IT. These costs in 2016 were £43.5 million.

Revenue Model:

Serco provide public services to citizens funded by tax payers. The Group has three major governmental customers as each represents more than 10% of Group revenues. The customers' revenues were £1,233.7 million for the UK Government, £623.1million for the US Government and £581.4 million for the Australian Government.

Outputs:

1. Delivered advice to policy-makers
2. Designed innovative public solutions
3. Established integrated systems
4. Delivered front-line services

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Financial resources (Government, commercial)
3. Future plans information (Government)
4. International partnerships

Virgin Trains

Group: Train Operator

Role: Interact directly with Network Rail, CUE, and rely on commercial contracts to provide passenger train services on the West Coast Main Line (serving London, Birmingham, Manchester, Liverpool and Glasgow)

Objectives:

- *Provide jobs in the industry
- *Offer passengers faster and better train journeys
- *Benefit from Network Rail's V2I technology investment
- *Reduce accidents, delays and other technical problems

Specific Needs:

1. Resources (human, technical)
2. Franchise contracts for the routes
3. Launch new services via franchising
4. Expert knowledge on technical issues
5. General knowledge (scientific, social, etc)

Cost Structure:

From the ORR report 2014/15:
Virgin Trains West Coast Operating Costs - £874.2 million
Allocated Network Grant - £420.4 million
The general industry expenditure is - personnel costs, rolling stock, network rail charges and others

Revenue Model:

The general revenue streams are passenger fares, others (car parking, on train catering, etc.); government grants and other sources (property, station retails, freight, etc.)

Outputs:

1. Offered train services
2. Collected data on trains via sensors to support objectives

Inputs:

1. Skilled workforce (Educators)
2. Franchise contracts (Government via DfT)
3. Future plans information (CUE, Network rail)
4. Science systems (Alstom Transport)
5. Data analytics (CUE)

UK GOVERNMENT

Group: City / Government

Role: This includes local authorities, city authorities, public administration, government agencies and central departments (e.g Department for Transport, Transport Scotland). It is responsible for the provision of policy-making & policy direction

Objectives:

- *Provide oversight of public programmes/ agencies
- *Appropriate funds to public programmes/ agencies
- *Evaluation of activities with respect to sustainable and safe railway industry
- *Promote actions that will improve safety and security of UK public
 - *Sustain political support (central or local)
 - *Introduce fair and good transport legislation

Specific Needs:

1. Resources to implement objectives (budgetary)
2. Progress reports on activities
3. Data from government-funded programmes
4. Expert scientific, technical and policy advice
5. Knowledge of policy-direction of other public bodies, and inter-governmental agencies
6. General information (scientific, technical, legal, etc.)
7. Political support (through voting)

Cost Structure:

Central budgeting or local budgeting

Revenue Model:

Public taxation

Outputs:

1. Policy-making documentation
2. Ensured public funding
3. Legislation documentation

Inputs

1. Compliance with policy direction (EU and other government agencies)
2. Plans and reports of progress (ORR, RSSB, Network Rail, Serco, Virgin Trains, Alstom)
3. Science knowledge (CUE)
4. Public opinions (Public)
5. Informative & disseminative content (ORR, RSSB)
6. Taxes (Public)
7. Policy advice (Serco)
8. Skilled workforce (Educators)
9. Railway analysed data (CUE)

Coventry University Enterprise Unit

Group: Research Organisation

Role: Use UK-based railway infrastructure data to generate science knowledge, develop predictive maintenance systems, and inform decision-making process of the infrastructure owner as well as provide opinions to the Railway Safety & Standards Board

Objectives:

*Produce useful knowledge and information for the UK railway industry

*Achieve international professional recognition

*Analyse raw data and provide advice to the railway industry, government agencies and regulators on matters of scientific interest

*Seek business partnerships

Specific Needs:

1. Railway acquired data from monitoring trains via sensors placed on trains

2. Other complementary data

3. Funding

4. Skilled workforce

5. Knowledge of ORR and Railway Safety & Standards Board objectives and future plans

6. General knowledge of policy direction

Cost Structure:

Public university cost structure: 1) personnel costs - 53%;

2) other operating expenses (buildings, materials) - 40%

3) depreciation, tax expenses - 7%

Revenue Model:

Annual Report 2016 - a reported surplus of £28.60 million

1) Tuition fees and educational contracts (77%)

2) Funding body grants (10%)

3) Research grants and contracts (3%)

4) Other income (9%)

5) Investment income (1%)

Outputs:

*Scientific research and products

*Scientific data-based systems

*Offered business services

Inputs:

1. Funding (public, Network Rail)

2. Costs sharing (Network Rail about "Keep Safe" project)

3. Skilled workforce (Educators)

4. Railway acquired data (Network Rail, Virgin Trains, Alstom Transport)

5. Information on regulations and standards (ORR, RSSB)

6.4.2 CS4 Surveys' questions

Quantitative Analysis – December 2017, NEWBITS

WP4 Value Flow Scoring Questions

Case Study 4 – Coventry, UK

INSTRUCTIONS:

The intent of this analysis is to identify the highest value-producing interactions between the most important stakeholders in each of our four case studies, and subsequently map value flows of the major relationships. We need to develop insight into the *specific needs* of stakeholders and how *they are fulfilled*. In WP3, partners identified a number of stakeholders that interact with each other in all four case studies. In WP4, we continue deepening the understanding of the nature of such specific needs of each major stakeholder, and their preferred source of fulfilment.

We plan to run two surveys, one after another, each contains a series of questions regarding the specific needs of each stakeholder, divided into sections by stakeholder. When answering these questions, please think of yourself as a representative from that particular stakeholder group, for instance academia, industry association, mobility operator or policy-maker.

Satisfaction / Regret

Question: How would you categorise the presence or absence of fulfillment of this need?

Responses: A response of A, B, C, D or E will be chosen. Answer E corresponds to “must-have” need.

- A. I would be satisfied by its presence, but do not regret its absence
- B. I would be satisfied by its presence, but would somewhat regret its absence
- C. I would be satisfied by its presence and do regret its absence
- D. Its presence is needed
- E. Its presence is absolutely essential

Importance of Source

Question: If this need were to be fulfilled, how important would this source be?

Responses: A response of 1, 2, 3, 4, or 5 can be chosen. The response 5 corresponds to “extremely important”.

- 1. Not important
- 2. Somewhat important
- 3. Important
- 4. Very important
- 5. Extremely important

Survey I – Case Study 4 (Coventry, UK)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
ALSTOM TRANSPORT	1. Data Analytics Technology	
	2. Funding	
	3. New launched services	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	5. Skilled Workforce	

Note: Skilled workforce – technically skilled and educated/trained employees

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
CUE (Coventry University Enterprises Ltd)	1. Funding	
	2. Costs Sharing	
	3. Railway Acquired Data (real-time data)	
	4. Information Exchange on Regulations & Standards	
	5. Skilled Workforce	

Note: Cost Sharing – sharing of costs by two or more stakeholders of the network;

Funding – money provided from one stakeholder to another

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
EDUCATORS	1. Educational Material	
	2. Inspired Students	
	3. Science Knowledge	
	4. Funding	

Note: Educators (universities, colleges) are the source of skilled workers

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Network Rail	1. Funding	
	2. Commercial Charges	
	3. Skilled Workforce	
	4. Policy & Regulatory Advice	
	5. Science Systems	
	6. Science Knowledge	

Note: Science knowledge combines all technical (e.g. ITS solutions), economic (e.g. economic indicators) and business knowledge generated by the scientists

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
GOVERNMENT (UK)	1. Compliance with policy direction	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	
	4. Public opinions	
	5. Informative & disseminative content	
	6. Taxes	
	7. Policy Advice	
	8. Railway Analysed Data	
	9. Skilled Workforce	

Note: Government – includes local authority, city authority, public administration, government agencies and central departments (e.g. Department for Transport, Transport Scotland). It is responsible for the provision of policy-making & policy directions

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
ORR (Office of Rail and Road)	1. Policy Direction	
	2. Financial Resources	
	3. Grant from Government	

	4. Scientific Knowledge	
	5. Railway Acquired Data	
	6. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
RSSB (Railway Safety and Standard Board)	1. Financial Resources	
	2. Cost Sharing	
	3. Public Funding	
	4. Science Knowledge and Data Analytics	
	5. Railway Analysed Data	
	6. Future Policy Direction	
	7. Skilled Workforce	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Public (UK)	1. Railway improved safety-derived products & services	
	2. Employment	
	3. Health & Safety Protection	
	4. Science Knowledge	
	5. Data Analysed Content	
	6. Railway Fair Prices	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
	1. Skilled Workforce	
	2. Financial Resources	

Serco	3. International Partnerships	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	

Note: Future Plans Information Exchange – information about the organization’s plans for future business expansions, research or technological inventions

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Need Characterization (A B C D E)
Virgin Trains	1. Skilled Workforce	
	2. Franchise Contracts	
	3. Future Plans Information Exchange	
	4. Science Systems	
	5. Data Analytics	

Survey II – Case Study 4 (Coventry, UK)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)
ALSTOM TRANSPORT	1. Data Analytics Technology	<i>from CUE</i>
	2. Funding	<i>from Government</i>
		<i>from Commercial clients</i>
	3. New Launched Services	<i>from CUE</i>
		<i>from Alstom R&D</i>
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from CUE</i>
		<i>from Network Rail</i>
5. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
CUE (Coventry University Enterprises Ltd.)	1. Funding	<i>from</i> Government	
		<i>from</i> Network Rail	
	2. Cost Sharing	<i>from</i> Network Rail about “Keep Safe” project	
	3. Railway Acquired Data (real-time data)	<i>from</i> Network Rail	
		<i>from</i> Virgin Trains	
		<i>from</i> Alstom Transport	
	4. Information Exchange on Regulations & Standards	<i>from</i> ORR	
		<i>from</i> RSSB	
	5. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
EDUCATORS	1. Educational Material	<i>from</i> CU Group	
	2. Inspired Students	<i>from</i> Public	
	3. Science Knowledge	<i>from</i> CUE	
	4. Funding	<i>from</i> Government (Public taxes)	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Network Rail	1. Funding	<i>from</i> Grants from Department for Transport	
		<i>from</i> Transport Scotland	
	2. Commercial Charges	<i>from</i> Virgin Trains	
		<i>from</i> Properties	
	3. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators	
	4. Policy & Regulatory Advice	<i>from</i> ORR	
		<i>from</i> RSSB	
	5. Science systems	<i>from</i> Alstom Transport	
6. Science knowledge	<i>from</i> CUE		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
	1. Compliance with policy direction	<i>from</i> EU agencies;	
		<i>from</i> other inter-governmental agencies	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	<i>from</i> ORR	
		<i>from</i> RSSB	
		<i>from</i> Network Rail	
		<i>from</i> Alstom	

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GOVERNMENT (UK)		<i>from Serco</i>	
		<i>from Virgin Trains</i>	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	<i>from CUE</i>	
	4. Public opinions	<i>from Public</i>	
	5. Informative & disseminative content	<i>from ORR</i>	
		<i>from RSSB</i>	
	6. Taxes	<i>from Public</i>	
	7. Policy Advice	<i>from Serco</i>	
	8. Railway Analysed Data	<i>from CUE</i>	
9. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
ORR (Office of Rail and Road)	1. Policy Direction	<i>from Government</i>	
	2. Financial Resources	<i>from levies, license fees from Network Rail</i>	
		<i>from Virgin Trains</i>	
	3. Grant from Government	<i>from DfT</i>	
		<i>from Transport Scotland</i>	
	4. Scientific Knowledge	<i>from Educators (CU Group)</i>	
	5. Railway acquired data	<i>from Network Rail</i>	
6. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
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D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

RSSB (Railway Safety and Standard Board)	1. Financial Resources	<i>from</i> levies from Network Rail	
	2. Cost Sharing	<i>with</i> CUE about "Keep Safe" project	
	3. Public Funding	<i>from</i> Government	
	4. Science knowledge and data	<i>from</i> CUE	
	5. Future Policy Direction	<i>from</i> Government (Department for Transport)	
		<i>from</i> Transport Scotland	
		<i>from</i> ORR	
	6. Railway Analysed Data	<i>from</i> CUE	
7. Skilled Workforce	<i>from</i> Educators		

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Public (UK)	1. Railway improved safety-derived products & services	<i>from</i> CUE	
		<i>from</i> Network Rail	
		<i>from</i> Virgin Trains	
	2. Employment	<i>with</i> Network Rail	
		Alstom Transport	
		<i>with</i> Virgin Trains	
	3. Health & Safety Protection	<i>from</i> ORR	
		<i>from</i> RSSB	

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		<i>from Government</i>	
	4. Science Knowledge	<i>from Educators</i>	
	5. Data Analysed Content	<i>from CUE</i>	
	6. Railway Fair Prices	<i>from ORR</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Serco	1. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	
	2. Financial Resources	<i>from Government</i>	
		<i>from Commercial Clients</i>	
	3. International Partnerships	<i>from Government</i>	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from Government</i>	

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	Importance of Source (1 2 3 4 5)	
Virgin Trains	1. Skilled Workforce	<i>from Educators</i>	
	2. Franchise Contracts	<i>from Government via DfT</i>	
	3. Future Plans Information Exchange	<i>from CUE</i>	
		<i>from Network Rail</i>	
	4. Science Systems	<i>from Alstom Transport</i>	
	5. Data Analytics	<i>from CUE</i>	

Lastly, please identify any specific needs that you consider having been missed from this survey.

6.5 Supporting Material of Joint Ideation workshop in Barcelona

6.5.1 CS1 Experts' ranking

Project Acronym: **NEWBITS**
Project Title: New business models for ITS
Project Number: 723974
Topic: **MG.6.3-2016**
Type of Action: **CSA**

D4.3 Validation of Quantitative Results

Expert Ranking 22 March 2018

(Version 1.0, 05/03/2018)

NEWBITS Project

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem.

In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective.

I. Introduction:

The performed NEWBITS WP4 Surveys in December 2017 were a basis for the Quantitative Analysis, which objectives are to:

- 1) identify the intensity of any stakeholder's specific need;
- 2) and the importance of any particular source to fulfil this specific need;

All individuals who completed the value flow questionnaires possessed an in-depth understanding of the network and a fairly broad knowledge of the industry. Each individual assigned scores to every value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the importance. However, each scorer did not have detailed knowledge about the specific needs of each of the stakeholders. Therefore, once the combined set of value flow scores was calculated, we consulted with representatives of different groups of stakeholders at a local level (Spain) on 18th January 2018. That's how we determined the pre- and post-validation relative ranks of all value flows.

During the joint event in Barcelona, 22nd of March 2018, we are asking the external experts to evaluate the rankings of the value flows to provide their professional validation of the value flow scores. To avoid any confusion with the model, we are not asking them to validate the absolute combined numeric scores.

In addition, in CS1 to explain the *dynamic evolution* of the business ecosystem, and the distinct network, we assumed that the business ecosystem goes through three cycles:

- I. Cycle 1 – starting-up
- II. Cycle 2 – growing
- III. Cycle 3 – maturing

The main value flow that drives the innovations is the science knowledge, and thus, it can be divided into three categories:

1. ITS-knowledge
2. Transport-wide knowledge
3. Social science knowledge (social media, communication, dissemination)

With the introduction of the preferences for ITS-science knowledge through each cycle, the results for the actor “Aslogic” show how the importance of ITS science knowledge diminishes through the life-cycle of the business ecosystem while the need of other science knowledge accelerates. As such the value flow “ITS Science knowledge” ranks 5 in Cycle 1, and then drops to rank 7 in Cycle 2 and Cycle 3.

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VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank	Cycle 2/Medium Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank	Cycle 3/Low Pr COMBINED Score	Pre-Validation Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	0.80	1	0.80	1
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	0.53	3	0.53	3
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	0.54	2	0.54	2
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.41	5	0.24	7	0.14	7
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	6	0.39	5	0.39	5
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	7	0.37	6	0.37	6
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	0.49	4	0.49	4

II. Validate value flow scores with a dynamic element

ASLOGIC – Cycle 1

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High Pr COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓ Greater Importance	
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	7		
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.41	5	5		
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	6	6	Less	
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	7	2	Importance	

ASLOGIC – Cycle 2

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Medium Pr COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓ Greater Importance	
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	2		
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	5	5		
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	6	6	Less	
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.24	7	7	Importance	

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ASLOGIC – Cycle 3

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 3/Low P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Acquired Mobility Data	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.80	1	1	↓ Less Importance	
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Commercial clients	0.54	2	2		
Commercial Funding	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.53	3	3		
Skilled Workforce	ASLOGIC	Educators	0.49	4	4		
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	UAB Mobility Unit	0.39	5	5		
Future Plans Information Exchange	ASLOGIC	Network's stakeholders	0.37	6	6		
ITS Science Knowledge	ASLOGIC	UAB	0.14	7	7		

Members of University Community (end-users) – Cycle 1

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1	↓ Less Importance	
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	6		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.31	6	4		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	7	7		
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	8	8		
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	9	9		
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	9	9	Less	
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	9	9	Importance	

Members of University Community (end-users) – Cycle 2

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Med P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1	↓ Less Importance	
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	4		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	6	6		
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	7	7		
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	8	8		
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	8	8		
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	8	8	Less	
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.18	9	9	Importance	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

Members of University Community (end-users) – Cycle 3

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 3/Low P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank		
Collaborative platform on sustainable mobility options	End-users	FrontierCities	0.49	1	1		
Rewards	End-users	Network's stakeholders	0.49	1	1		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.46	2	2		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	Aslogic	0.38	3	3		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Social media	0.35	4	4		
Informative & entertaining content	End-users	Websays	0.33	5	5		
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	End-users	FrontierCities	0.26	6	6		
Employment	End-users	UAB Mobility Unit	0.25	7	7		
Employment	End-users	UAB LOGA	0.23	8	8		
Employment	End-users	SmartCities CORE	0.23	8	8		
Employment	End-users	UAB Management	0.23	8	8	Less	
Science Knowledge	End-users	UAB	0.108	9	9	Importance	

Websays – Cycle 1

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 1/High P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank		
Informative Content & Entertaining Content (social media)	WEBSAYS	Social media	0.73	1	1		
Mobility Acquired data from UAB campus, others	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.43	2	2		
Funding	WEBSAYS	Operators	0.34	3	3		
Skilled workforce	WEBSAYS	Educators	0.34	3	3		
Future Mobility Plans info	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.29	4	4		
Funding	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.28	5	5		
Funding	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5		
Policy Collaboration (engaging the end-users)	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5		Less
Science Knowledge	WEBSAYS	UAB	0.27	6	6	Importance	

Websays – Cycle 2 and Cycle 3

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	Cycle 2/Med P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Cycle 3/Low P	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert	
			COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank	COMBINED Sco	Rank	Rank			Importance
Informative Content & Entertaining Content (social media)	WEBSAYS	Social media	0.73	1	1	0.73	1	1			
Mobility Acquired data from UAB campus, others	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.43	2	2	0.43	2	2			
Funding	WEBSAYS	Operators	0.34	3	3	0.34	3	3			
Skilled workforce	WEBSAYS	Educators	0.34	3	3	0.34	3	3			
Future Mobility Plans info	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.29	4	4	0.29	4	4			
Funding	WEBSAYS	UAB Management	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5			
Funding	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5			
Policy Collaboration (engaging the end-users)	WEBSAYS	Members of Community	0.28	5	5	0.28	5	5		Less	
Science Knowledge	WEBSAYS	UAB	0.16	6	6	0.09	6	6		Importance	

III. Validate rankings for the rest of stakeholders without cycles**GOVERNMENT and FRONTIERCITIES**

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Public Opinions	GOVERNMENT	Members of Community	0.75	1	1	
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	EU agencies	0.60	2	2	
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	Other intergovernmental agencies	0.60	2	2	
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	UAB Mobility Unit	0.49	3	3	
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	UAB Management	0.46	4	4	
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	FrontierCities	0.38	5	5	
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Websays	0.38	5	5	
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Social media	0.36	6	6	
Taxes	GOVERNMENT	Members of Community	0.35	7	3	
ITS Science Knowledge	GOVERNMENT	UAB	0.30	8	7	
Opinion & Support	FrontierCities	Members of Community	0.49	1	3	
EU funding	FrontierCities	Public taxes	0.49	1	1	
Plans and reports of progress	FrontierCities	UAB Mobility Unit	0.47	2	2	
Plans and reports of progress	FrontierCities	UAB Management	0.47	2	2	
Acquired Mobility Data	FrontierCities	Network's stakeholders	0.46	3	3	
Opinion & Support	FrontierCities	European Cities	0.46	3	3	
Science opinions	FrontierCities	UAB	0.31	5	5	
Informative content	FrontierCities	Social media	0.41	4	4	
Cost sharing	FrontierCities	UAB Mobility Unit	0.30	6	6	
Cost sharing	FrontierCities	UAB LOGA	0.30	6	6	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

UAB MOBILITY UNIT and UAB MANAGEMENT

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Funding	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Government	0.41	6	6	
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.28	10	10	
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Municipality	0.59	1	4	
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.52	3	3	
Policy Collaboration (incl. end-users' engagement)	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Members of Community	0.59	1	1	
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Transport operators	0.57	2	2	
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.41	6	6	
Mobility Planning	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.48	4	1	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	UAB Management	0.39	7	7	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Other Public Administration	0.37	8	8	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Transport operators	0.44	5	5	
Monetary rents	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Commercial operators	0.15	11	11	
Skilled workforce	UAB MOBILITY UNIT (Transport Authority)	Educators	0.36	9	9	
Funding	UAB Management	Government	0.53	3	4	
Funding	UAB Management	Members of Community	0.14	10	10	
Funding	UAB Management	Operators	0.45	5	5	
Cost sharing	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.21	9	9	
Policy Collaboration	UAB Management	UAB Unit	0.62	1	1	
Policy Collaboration	UAB Management	Other Public Administration	0.54	2	2	
Mobility Planning and know-how	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.47	4	3	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	UAB Mobility Unit	0.43	6	6	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	Public Administration	0.39	7	7	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Management	Operators	0.39	7	7	
Skilled workforce	UAB Management	Educators	0.38	8	8	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

EDUCATORS, UAB LOGA and UAB Smart Cities CORE

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED Scores	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Educational Material	EDUCATORS	UAB	0.61	1	1	
Inspired students	EDUCATORS	Members of Community	0.52	3	3	
Informative content	EDUCATORS	Social Media	0.39	4	4	
Science Knowledge	EDUCATORS	UAB	0.58	2	2	
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government (Public taxes)	0.35	5	5	
Acquired Mobility Data	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Network's stakeholders	0.55	3	3	
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Management	0.38	7	7	
ITS Science funding	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB	0.57	2	2	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Mobility Unit	0.43	4	4	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	UAB Management	0.41	6	6	
Access to existing Research programmes	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	EU programmes	0.78	1	1	
Skilled workforce	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Educators	0.42	5	5	
Informative content	UAB Logistics and Aeronautics Unit	Social media	0.28	8	8	
Smart City Acquired data	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.44	4	4	
Cost sharing with UAB	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB Management	0.21	9	9	
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB	0.55	2	2	
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	IT Service Unit	0.52	3	3	
Policy Collaboration	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.52	3	3	
Technology transfers	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.73	1	1	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	UAB Management	0.31	6	6	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	IT Service Unit	0.26	8	8	
Future Plans Information Exchange	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Network's stakeholders	0.33	5	5	
Skilled workforce	UAB Smart Cities CORE	Educators	0.29	7	7	

6.5.2 CS2 Experts' ranking

NEWBITS

Project Acronym: **NEWBITS**
Project Title: New business models for ITS
Project Number: 723974
Topic: **MG.6.3-2016**
Type of Action: **CSA**

D4.3 Validation of Quantitative Results

Expert Ranking 22 March 2018

(Version 2.0, 07/03/2018)

NEWBITS Project

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem.

In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective.

I. Introduction:

The performed NEWBITS WP4 Surveys in December 2017 were a basis for the Quantitative Analysis, which objectives are to:

- 1) identify the intensity of any stakeholder's specific need;
- 2) and the importance of any particular source to fulfil this specific need;

All individuals who completed the value flow questionnaires possessed an in-depth understanding of the network and a fairly broad knowledge of the industry. Each individual assigned scores to every value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the importance. However, each scorer did not have detailed knowledge about the specific needs of each of the stakeholders. Therefore, once the combined set of value flow scores was calculated, we consulted with representatives of different groups of stakeholders at a local level (Verona, Italy) on 22nd February 2018. That's how we determined the pre- and post- validation relative ranks of all value flows.

During the joint event in Barcelona, 22nd of March 2018, we are asking the external experts to evaluate the ranking of the value flows to provide their professional validation of the value flow scores. To avoid any confusion with the model, we are not asking them to validate the absolute combined numeric scores.

II. Validate value flow scores

ATV, AUDI, MUNICIPALITY OF VERONA AND EDUCATORS

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED SCORE	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Municipality of Verona	0.56	1	1	↓ Less	
Transit Signal Priority	ATV	Swarco Mizar	0.50	2	2		
General knowledge (technical, social)	ATV	Network's stakeholders	0.31	3	3		
Skilled Workforce	ATV	Educators	0.30	4	4		
Funding	ATV	FP7 Research funding - European	0.25	5	5		
Traffic acquired data / purchase of traffic data	ATV	Telecom Italia	0.06	6	6		Importance
Mobility acquired data (AUDI purchase of Skilled Workforce)	AUDI	Swarco Mizar	0.76	1	1	Greater	
	AUDI	Educators	0.76	1	1	Importance	
Mobility acquired data (AUDI purchase of Science knowledge (technical, social))	AUDI	Telecom Italia	0.54	2	2	↓ Less	
Science knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	Network's stakeholders	0.35	3	3		
Science knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	AUDI R&D department	0.35	3	3		
General knowledge (technical, social)	AUDI	Municipality	0.18	4	4		Less
Partial funding	AUDI	FP7 Research funding - European	0.15	5	5	Importance	
Innovative ITS services	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Swarco Mizar	0.49	1	1	Greater	
Future Plans information	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Network's stakeholders	0.29	2	2	Importance	
Future Plans information	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Government	0.28	3	3	↓ Less	
Skilled Workforce	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Educators	0.15	4	4		
Cost sharing	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Network's stakeholders (incl. FP7 COMPASS4D project)	0.12	5	5		
Mobility acquired data	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	Telecom Italia	0.04	6	6	Less	
Mobility acquired data	MUNICIPALITY-VERONA	AUDI	0.04	6	6	Importance	
Educational material	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.47	1	1	Greater	
Policy direction	EDUCATORS	Government	0.37	2	2	Importance	
Science knowledge	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.27	3	3		
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government (public taxes)	0.27	3	3	Less	
Inspired students	EDUCATORS	Citizens	0.22	4	4	Importance	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

GOVERNMENT, CITIZENS, SWARCO MIZAR, TAXI-OPERATORS AND TELECOMITALIA

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED SCORE	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Taxes	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.49	1	1	↓	
Public opinions	GOVERNMENT	Citizens	0.47	2	2		
Innovative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.28	3	3		
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	EU agencies	0.21	4	4		
Compliance with policy direction	GOVERNMENT	Other intergovernmental agencies	0.21	4	4		
Science knowledge	GOVERNMENT	Educators	0.19	5	5		Less
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	Municipality	0.18	6	6		Importance
General knowledge and information	CITIZENS (end-users)	Educators	0.57	1	1	Greater	Expert
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.57	1	1	Importance	Rank
Online mobile applications	CITIZENS (end-users)	Swarco Mizar	0.52	2	2	↓	
Sustainable mobility-derived services&products	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.42	3	3		
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AUDI	0.40	4	4		
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Municipality	0.37	5	5		
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	Telecom Italia	0.36	6	6		Less
Employment	CITIZENS (end-users)	AVT	0.33	7	7		Importance
Skilled Workforce	SWARCO MIZAR	Educators	0.86	1	1		Greater
Traffic data access	SWARCO MIZAR	Verona Municipality	0.70	2	2	Importance	Rank
Traffic data access	SWARCO MIZAR	ITS platform	0.34	3	3	↓	
Science knowledge	SWARCO MIZAR	Swarco Mizar R&D department	0.31	4	4		
Science knowledge	SWARCO MIZAR	Educators	0.31	4	4		
Public Mobility Services	SWARCO MIZAR	Municipality's strategic plan - Verona	0.30	5	5		
Partial funding	SWARCO MIZAR	FP7 Research funding - European	0.28	6	6		Less
Future Plans information exchange	SWARCO MIZAR	Municipality	0.14	7	7	Importance	
Pre-existing and innovative ITS services	TAXI-OPERATORS	Swarco Mizar	0.23	1	1	Greater	Expert
Real-time data	TAXI-OPERATORS	AUDI (cars)	0.22	2	2	Importance	Rank
Pre-existing and innovative ITS services	TAXI-OPERATORS	Municipality	0.19	3	3	↓	
Real-time data	TAXI-OPERATORS	Telecom Italia (messages)	0.15	4	4		
General information	TAXI-OPERATORS	Municipality	0.14	5	5		Less
Skilled workforce	TAXI-OPERATORS	Educators	0.03	6	6		Importance
Skilled Workforce	TELECOMITALIA	Educators	0.86	1	1		Greater
Policy directions in smart services for the public sector	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.26	2	2	Importance	Rank
Policy directions in smart services for the public sector	TELECOMITALIA	Government	0.26	2	2	↓	
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.23	3	3		
Future Plans information exchange	TELECOMITALIA	Municipality	0.22	4	4		
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Swarco Mizar	0.21	5	5		
Science knowledge	TELECOMITALIA	Educators	0.18	6	6		
Science knowledge	TELECOMITALIA	Telecom Italia R&D department	0.14	7	7		Less
Sustainable Mobility services	TELECOMITALIA	Citizens	0.12	8	8		Importance

6.5.3 CS3 Experts' ranking

NEWBITS

Project Acronym: **NEWBITS**
Project Title: New business models for ITS
Project Number: 723974
Topic: **MG.6.3-2016**
Type of Action: **CSA**

D4.3 Validation of Quantitative Results

Expert Ranking 22 March 2018

(Version 3.0, 08/03/2018)

NEWBITS Project

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During the joint event in Barcelona, 22nd of March 2018, we are asking the external experts to evaluate the ranking of the value flows to provide their professional validation of the value flow scores. To avoid any confusion with the model, we are not asking them to validate the absolute combined numeric scores.

II. Validate value flow scores

PORTBASE

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1		
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Sea-shipping company	0.57	1	1		
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Deep-sea terminal	0.52	2	2		
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Sea-shipping terminals	0.49	3	3		
Authorisation to share data of port-community system with platform developer	Portdat	Inland terminal operator	0.45	4	Deleted Flow		
Data of individual port users into port community system	Portdat	Inland terminal operator	0.43	5	4		
Technical knowledge of the functionality	Portdat	Platform operator	0.37	6	5		
Shared policy goals with Port of Rotterdam	Portdat	Port of Rotterdam	0.34	7	6		
Skilled Workforce	Portdat	Educators	0.34	7	6		Less
Technical knowledge of the functionality	Portdat	Platform operator	0.24	8	7		Importance

PORT OF ROTTERDAM

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchronodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Portdat	0.45	1	1		
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchronodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Government	0.44	2	3		
Understanding of the functioning of the service to disseminate to others	Port of Rotterdam	Platform developer	0.42	3	4		
Skilled Workforce	Port of Rotterdam	Educators	0.34	4	5		
Operational service: real-time data about hinterland container transport	Port of Rotterdam	Platform developer	0.32	5	2		
Understanding of the functioning of the service to disseminate to others	Port of Rotterdam	TNO	0.31	6	6		Less
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchronodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	Platform service provider	0.28	7	7		Importance
Shared policy goals (e.g. synchronodal transport)	Port of Rotterdam	TNO	0.24	8	8		

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

PLATFORM DEVELOPER / MAINTENANCE

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Greater	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Importance	Rank
Technical knowledge	Platform developer/maintenance	Platform operator	0.75	1	6		
Authorisation to include container status data in the platform	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.71	2	1		
Agreements to share/use deep-sea terminal data	Platform developer/maintenance	Deep-sea terminal	0.69	3	2		
Authorisation to include container status data in the platform	Platform developer/maintenance	Sea-shipping company	0.69	3	2		
Agreements to share/use deep-sea terminal data	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.67	4	3		
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Inland terminal operator	0.58	5	4		
Technical knowledge	Platform developer/maintenance	TNO	0.57	6	7		
Container status at deep-sea terminal (handling, customs)	Platform developer/maintenance	Deep-sea terminal	0.50	7	5		
Container status at deep-sea terminal (handling, customs)	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.50	7	5		
Skilled Workforce	Platform developer/maintenance	Educators	0.48	8	8		
Vessel arrival info from sea shipping companies	Platform developer/maintenance	Sea-shipping terminal	0.41	9	9		
Vessel arrival info from sea shipping companies	Platform developer/maintenance	Portdat	0.41	9	9		
Future contract conditions with info service provider (costs, payment structure)	Platform developer/maintenance	Information service provider	0.40	10	10		
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	AISHUB	0.39	11	11		
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.39	11	11		
Planning and container status info in hinterland transport	Platform developer/maintenance	Shipper	0.37	12	12		
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	FleetM	0.37	12	12	Less	
Real-time data from trucks, ships and traffic	Platform developer/maintenance	NDW	0.36	13	13	Importance	

Note: AISHUB – Provides ship positioning data to the network;

NDW – provides publicly available data about traffic information of Dutch road networks

III. Validate rankings for the rest of stakeholders without change in pre- and post-validation ranking provided by stakeholders' representatives

INLAND TERMINAL OPERATOR

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Rank
Neutral/transparent way of sharing container status info with partners	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.42	4	4	
Improved real-time info on container status at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.55	2	2	
Total logistic chain visibility (information from all partners at once)	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.43	3	3	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.37	6	6	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.39	5	5	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.36	7	7	
New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (transport time)	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.18	14	14	
New agreements on performance with shipper and warehouse (transport time)	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.22	12	12	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Platform service developer	0.36	7	7	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Shipper	0.23	11	11	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Inland terminal operator	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.23	11	11	
Earlier container pick-up at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.32	9	9	
More reliable container release time at deep-sea terminal	Inland terminal operator	Deep-sea terminal	0.57	1	1	
Technical knowledge	Inland terminal operator	Platform operator	0.26	10	10	
Technical knowledge	Inland terminal operator	TNO	0.20	13	13	
Skilled Workforce	Inland terminal operator	Educators	0.33	8	8	

INFORMATION SERVICE PROVIDER

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Scores	Rank	Rank	Rank
Flexibility with respect to platform functionality and information sources	Information service provider	Platform developer	0.47	6	6	
Future contract conditions with platform developer (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Platform developer	0.59	2	2	
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Shipper	0.42	9	9	
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.45	8	8	
Future contract conditions for service with users (costs, payment structure)	Information service provider	Inland terminal operator	0.46	7	7	
Technical knowledge	Information service provider	Platform operator	0.60	1	1	
Technical knowledge	Information service provider	TNO	0.40	10	10	
Skilled Workforce	Information service provider	Educators	0.60	1	1	
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	TNO	0.52	4	4	
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	LIOF	0.50	5	5	
Importance of pilot project for market introduction	Information service provider	Logistic Partners	0.58	3	3	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

SHIPPER

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Rank
Real-time information container transport	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.22	13	13	
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.57	1	1	
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.43	4	4	
Higher predictability logistic process	Shipper	Deep-sea terminal	0.39	6	6	
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.49	2	2	
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.31	8	8	
Earlier delivery to retailers (trade goods delivery)	Shipper	Deep-sea terminal	0.29	10	10	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.47	3	3	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.40	5	5	
Improved contract conditions with sea shipping company (reduction in costs and time)	Shipper	Sea-shipping company/Inland operator	0.33	7	7	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.24	11	11	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Inland terminal operator	0.30	9	9	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Shipper	Warehouse/Logistic operator	0.31	8	8	
Technical knowledge	Shipper	TNO	0.14	15	15	
Technical knowledge	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.17	14	14	
Skilled Workforce	Shipper	Educators	0.24	12	12	
MONITORING OF THE DELIVERY PROCESSES, MOSTLY INDICATION OF POTENTIAL	Shipper	Platform service provider	0.06	16	16	N

WAREHOUSING/ LOGISTIC SERVICES

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Rank
Real-time information container status	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service developer	0.42	4	4	
Easier access to order and planning container info	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service developer	0.49	2	2	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.37	5	5	
Reduced discussion on delays or non-conformance of transport time	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.48	3	3	
New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (transport time)	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.18	12	12	
New agreements on performance with shipper and inland terminal (transport time)	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.21	10	10	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service provider	0.30	7	7	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Shipper	0.22	9	9	
Future contracts and other agreements for the use of services	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.23	8	8	
Higher predictability of container arrival at warehouse	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.53	1	1	
Faster/earlier container arrival at warehouse	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Inland terminal operator	0.31	6	6	
Technical knowledge	Warehousing/Logistic Services	TNO	0.17	13	13	
Technical knowledge	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Platform service provider	0.22	9	9	
Skilled Workforce	Warehousing/Logistic Services	Educators	0.20	11	11	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

TNO and DINALOG

VALUE FLOW	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Rank
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Dinalog	0.32	6	6	
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Government	0.36	5	5	
Knowledge of policy directions	TNO (RESEARCH)	Port of Rotterdam	0.32	6	6	
Market awareness of business case development of the pilot project	TNO (RESEARCH)	Consortium/Network	0.43	4	4	
Stakeholder input for development of service functionalities	TNO (RESEARCH)	Consortium/Network	0.61	2	2	
Skilled Workforce	TNO (RESEARCH)	Educators	0.48	3	3	
Project funding for pilot (TNO representing the Stakeholders Group)	TNO (RESEARCH)	Dinalog	0.64	1	1	
Pilot results to build-on for new projects	DINALOG	TNO	0.57	1	1	
Cost-sharing in pilot phase (co-financing of projects)	DINALOG	Consortium/Network	0.47	2	2	
Skilled Workforce	DINALOG	Educators	0.36	3	3	
Policy Directions	DINALOG	Consortium/Network	0.24	5	5	
Policy Directions	DINALOG	Government	0.32	4	4	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

LIOF, EDUCATORS, GOVERNMENT AND TRANSICS

VALUE FLOW (INPUTS)	TO STAKEHOLDER	FROM SOURCE	COMBINED	Pre-Validation	Post-Validation	Expert
			Score	Rank	Rank	Rank
Technical and economic info about the service to support market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	TNO	0.43	3	3	
Technical and economic info about the service to support market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Platform developer	0.37	4	4	
Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	TNO	0.61	1	1	
Demonstrated pilot results to promote market introduction	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Platform service operator	0.56	2	2	
Skilled workforce/ trained employees	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Educators	0.23	6	6	
Funding (from Government)	LIOF (Regional Development Company)	Government	0.34	5	5	
New Educational material related to ICT/ITS challenges	EDUCATORS	TNO	0.18	5	5	
New Educational material related to ICT/ITS challenges	EDUCATORS	Other Consortium Partners	0.14	6	6	
Inspired students for ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Citizens	0.2	4	4	
Science knowledge of ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Educators	0.23	2	2	
Science knowledge of ICT/ITS	EDUCATORS	Other Consortium Partners	0.21	3	3	
Funding	EDUCATORS	Government	0.28	1	1	
Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	Port of Rotterdam	0.47	1	1	
Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.47	1	1	
Compliance with policy direction (synchromodal transport; modal split)	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.47	1	1	
Informative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.40	2	2	
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.38	3	3	
INformative & disseminative content	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.35	4	4	
Plans and reports of progress	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.33	5	5	
Science knowledge (service related)	GOVERNMENT	TNO	0.23	6	6	
Skilled Workforce	GOVERNMENT	Educators	0.21	7	7	
Science knowledge (service related)	GOVERNMENT	Dinalog	0.20	8	8	
Corporate taxes and public taxation	GOVERNMENT	Consortium/Network	0.11	9	9	
Authorisation for data sharing with platform	FleetM	Inland terminal operator	0.72	1	1	
Technical knowledge of the functionality	FleetM	Platform developer	0.48	2	2	
Skilled Workforce	FleetM	Educators	0.43	3	3	
Technical knowledge of the functionality	FleetM	TNO	0.34	4	4	

6.5.4 CS4 Experts' ranking

NEWBITS

Project Acronym: **NEWBITS**
Project Title: New business models for ITS
Project Number: 723974
Topic: **MG.6.3-2016**
Type of Action: **CSA**

D4.3 Validation of Quantitative Results

Expert Ranking 22 March 2018

(Version 4.0, 16/03/2018)

NEWBITS Project

In NEWBITS, it is highly acknowledged that the successful execution and deployment of ITS innovations involving multiple stakeholders requires efficient cooperation, interacting with each other and feeding each other with knowledge as parts of an interconnected ecosystem.

In other words, the deployment of ITS initiatives should be analysed from a business ecosystem viewpoint, rather than an individual organisation perspective.

I. Introduction:

The performed NEWBITS WP4 Surveys in December 2017 were a basis for the Quantitative Analysis, which objectives are to:

- 1) identify the intensity of any stakeholder's specific need;
- 2) and the importance of any particular source to fulfil this specific need;

All individuals who completed the value flow questionnaires possessed an in-depth understanding of the network and a fairly broad knowledge of the industry. Each individual assigned scores to every value flows in accordance with their interpretation of the importance. However, each scorer did not have detailed knowledge about the specific needs of each of the stakeholders. Therefore, once the combined set of value flow scores was calculated, we consulted with representatives of different groups of stakeholders at a local level (Coventry, UK) between 2nd - 12th March 2018. That's how we determined the pre- and post- validation relative ranks of all value flows.

During the joint event in Barcelona, 22nd of March 2018, we are asking the external experts to evaluate the ranking of the value flows to provide their professional validation of the value flow scores. To avoid any confusion with the model, we are not asking them to validate the absolute combined numeric scores.

II. Validate rankings for all stakeholders – for some pre- and post-validation ranks have not changed

NETWORK RAIL (UK)

VALUE FLOW	To Stakeholder	From Source	Cycle 1 High Pr	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater Importance	Expert Rank
Railway Infrastructure Owners (e.g. Network Rail)	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.82	1	1	↓	
	Policy&Regulatory Advice	from RSSB	0.70	2	2		
	Science knowledge	from CUE	0.68	3	3		
	Policy&Regulatory Advice	from ORR	0.67	4	4		
	Funding	from Transport Scotland	0.66	5	5		
	Funding	from Grants, DfT	0.66	5	5		
	Commercial charges	from Properties	0.43	6	6		
	Commercial charges	from Virgin Trains	0.37	7	7		Less
	Science systems	from Alstom Transport	0.25	8	8	Importance	

ALSTOM TRANSPORT

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Train Manufacturers (e.g. Alstom Transport)	Future Plans Information Exchange	from Network Rail	0.62	1	1	Importance	
	Data Analytics Technology	from CUE	0.61	2	2	↓	
	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.58	3	2		
	Funding	from Commercial Clients	0.49	4	3		
	Funding	from Government	0.47	5	4		
	New Launched Services	from Alstom R&D	0.45	6	5		
	Future Plans Information Exchange	from CUE	0.33	7	6		Less
	New Launched Services	from CUE	0.27	8	7		Importance

ACADEMIC INSTITUTIONS

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Academic Institutions (e.g. Coventry University)	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Virgin Train	0.82	1	2	Importance	
	Funding	from Government	0.82	1	3		
	Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.71	2	1		
	Funding	from Network Rail	0.67	3	3		
	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Alstom Transport	0.64	4	4		
	Exchange on Regulation	from RSSB	0.59	5	5		
	Day Acquired Data (real-time)	from Network Rail	0.55	6	6		
	Cost sharing	from Network Rail about "Keep Safe" project	0.46	7	7	Less	
	Exchange on Regulation	from ORR	0.37	8	8	Importance	

EDUCATORS

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Educators	SCIENCE Knowledge	from CUE	0.45	1	1	Importance	
	Funding	from Government (Public taxes)	0.35	2	2		
	Inspired students	from Public	0.20	3	3		
	Educational material	from CU Group	0.13	4	4	Less	

D4.3 Report on Value Network Analysis for NEWBITS

Virgin Trains

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Greater	Expert Rank
Train Operators (e.g. Virgin Trains)	Franchise contracts	from Government via DfT	0.67	1	1	Importance	
	Data analytics	from CUE	0.51	2	2		
	Skilled workforce	from Educators	0.44	3	3		
	Future Plans Info Exchange	from Network Rail	0.43	4	4		
	Science systems	from Alstom Transport	0.21	5	5		
	Future Plans Info Exchange	from CUE	0.15	6	6	Less	

SAFETY REGULATORS (RSSB)

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
	1. Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.87	1	1	
	2. Science Knowledge & data	from CUE	0.84	2	2	
	3. Future Policy Direction	from ORR	0.72	3	3	
	4. Future Policy Direction	from Transport Scotland	0.68	4	4	
SAFETY REGULATORS	5. Future Policy Direction	from Government (Department for Transport)	0.68	4	4	
(RSSB)	6. Financial Resources	from levies from Network Rail	0.66	5	5	
	7. Public funding	from Government	0.60	6	6	
	8. Railway analysed data	from CUE	0.60	6	6	
	9. Cost sharing	with CUE about "Keep safe" project	0.28	7	7	

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GOVERNMENT, ORR

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Government Institutions	1. Compliance with policy direction	from EU agencies;	0.629	1	1	
		from other inter-governmental agencies	0.566	4	1	
	2. Plans and reports of progress	from ORR	0.241	12	11	
		from RSSB	0.394	8	7	
		from Network Rail	0.401	7	6	
		from Alstom	0.206	13	12	
		from Serco	0.206	13	13	
		from Virgin Trains	0.276	11	10	
	3. ITS Science Knowledge	from CUE	0.201	14	14	
	4. Public opinions	from Public	0.451	6	5	
	5. Informative & dis-seminative content	from ORR	0.603	2	2	
		from RSSB	0.576	3	3	
	6. Taxes	from Public	0.464	5	4	
7. Policy Advice	from Serco	0.31	10	9		
8. Railway Analysed Data	from CUE	0.139	15	15		
9. Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.37	9	8		
Rail Regulators (e.g. Office of Rail and Road)	1. Policy Direction	from Government	0.93	1	1	
	2. Financial Re-sources	from levies, license fees from Network Rail	0.63	2	2	
		from Virgin Trains	0.45	6	6	
	3. Grant from Government	from DfT	0.60	3	3	
		from Transport Scotland	0.48	4	4	
	4. Scientific Knowledge	from Educators (CU Group)	0.46	5	5	
	5. Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.46	5	5	
6. Railway acquired data	from Network Rail	0.24	7	7		

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Serco, the Public

To Stakeholder:	Value Flow	From Source	SCORES	Pre-Validation Rank	Post-Validation Rank	Expert Rank
Public	1. Railway improved safety derived products & services	from Network Rail	0.89	1	1	
		from CUE	0.40	7	6	
		from Virgin Trains	0.74	4	4	
	2. Employment	with Network Rail	0.36	8	7	
		Alstom Transport	0.34	9	8	
		with Virgin Trains	0.32	10	9	
	3. Health & Safety Protection	from ORR	0.82	3	3	
		from RSSB	0.64	6	3	
		from Government	0.67	5	5	
	4. Science Knowledge	from Educators	0.26	11	10	
	5. Data Analysed Content	from CUE	0.02	12	11	
	6. Railway Fair Prices	from ORR	0.84	2	2	
IT Service companies (e.g. Serco)	1. Skilled Workforce	from Educators	0.96	1	1	
	2. Financial Resources	from Commercial Clients	0.69	2	2	
		from Government	0.32	5	5	
	3. International Partnerships	from Government	0.41	3	3	
	4. Future Plans Information Exchange	from Government	0.4	4	4	